

**A STUDY OF ETHNIC CONSUMER ONLINE BUYING
BEHAVIOUR OF GROCERIES**

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Abstract

Online grocery shopping has a very strong growth in the UK and the size of the online grocery market is rising faster. Online shopping and online grocery shopping are different due to the variability of the products. Most of the previous studies has focused on online shopping in general, but this is essential to study ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. Because ethnic consumer (BAME) in the UK is an integral part of the economy and are completely necessary to ensure businesses can function. The purpose of this study is to investigate how ethnic consumers behave when they shop online groceries. Four research objectives have developed to understand the characteristics, behaviour, trust and adoption to the online platform of the ethnic consumer. This study is aimed to contribute the findings to the business practitioners in the UK to develop a market strategy focusing on the ethnic consumer. Other parties, such as marketing executives, corporate management, government agencies, web developers can be benefitted from the findings of the study.

This study has developed hypotheses that have then been tested and compared to previous studies and models. Theories and Models used in this study are - The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). A conceptual framework has been formulated in this research to help businesses market better to ethnic minorities. The research provides insights into ethnic consumers' online grocery buying behaviour and the relationship between online grocery buying behaviour and purchase intentions, using a theoretical framework. The research model was created and then tested on ethnic consumers in the U.K. The research is based on primary data that has been collected from surveys which have then been analysed through inferential and descriptive statistics. The descriptive research design used in this study with the self-completion survey (365 data collected). The Multiple Regression and ANOVA analysis used as the statistical tools in order to get a valid significance level for each variable influencing ethnic online grocery shoppers purchasing behaviour.

This research has indicated that age, attitudes, intentions, trust, satisfaction and technology play an important role in the ethnic consumer online grocery buying behaviour. This study found there is no significant difference between ethnicity and online grocery shopping, same as gender and online grocery shopping. Moreover, the research has found ethnic consumers tend to trust websites less than non-ethnic people. Trust in online shopping is increased through quality services, high-quality products, an increase in the reputation of a given business, familiarity with the business organisation, and its uses. Previous experience with online grocery shopping is found to be an important factor in ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour. Cultural satisfaction is very important among ethnic consumers. Traditional cultural values and a products' cultural/countries origin also play an important role in ethnic consumers' online buying decisions. Furthermore, Perceived risk (security of transaction and privacy, perceived complexity, unavailability to judge the products quality, postage and packing) has a negative effect on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping.

As empirical research, the study is focused on field surveys as well as evidence from previous research and literature. The findings of this research are that e-retailers need to develop strategies to market better to ethnic consumers. The findings are a blueprint for the businesses, government organisation (e.g., trade ministry, planning ministry) in the UK. However, the findings of the study can be used to develop an online business strategy in ethnic origin countries. In the conclusion, some limitations, suggestions and recommendations added.

Keywords - Ethnic Consumer, Online Shopping, Buying behaviour, Online Grocery shopping, Privacy and Security, Culture, Technology.

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ACRONYMS

ATM - Automated Teller Machine
BAME - Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic
BBC – British Broadcasting Corporation
C2C – Customer to Customer
CDCP – Centre for Disease Control and Prevention
CRE – Commission for Racial Equality
ECPIM - Ethnic Consumer Purchase Intent Model
EEA – European Economic Area
EU – European Union
OGS – Online Grocery Shopping
PEOU – Perceived Ease of Use
PSI – Policy Studies Institute
PU – Perceived Usefulness
TAM – Technology Acceptance Model
TPB – Theory of Planned Behaviour
TV - Television
UAE – United Arab Emirates
UK – United Kingdom
URL – Uniform Resource Locator
USA – United State of America
WWW – World Wide Web

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

This chapter discusses topic titles. It elaborates on the background of this research. This chapter highlights the research aim, objectives, and research questions of this dissertation. It also discusses the rationale of the research and problem statements.

1.1 RESEARCH BACKGROUND

Online grocery shopping in the UK is growing fast (Harris et al., 2017). Pleasant (2015) described the percentage of ethnic consumer online shopping in the UK is not rising faster. Some consumers had to stop doing online grocery shopping as it does not meet the required expectations. Schiffman and Kanuk (2006) indicated culture influences on ethnic consumer products purchase decision. Omar et al. (2004) highlighted ethnic consumer prefers to buy fruit, vegetables, rice, meat and fish and show greater importance of buying their national brand. Pleasant (2015) indicated the importance of researching ethnic consumer online buying behaviour to make a marketing strategy. Kotler et al. (2016) categorize ethnic consumer by distinguishing the beliefs and attitudes, and the minority status. They defined ethnic consumers migrated from different country and their culture and behaviour is different from the majority (Black, Asian and Minority Ethnic – BAME).

Social scientists and marketing researchers have highlighted that the ethnic category brings an important change to the consumer buying process (Hamlett et al., 2008; Burton, 1996; Chaudhury and Crick, 2004; Lopez, 2005). Same as Appiah (2004) stated categorising ethnic market is important to sell the products. They also highlighted that, due to the changing of the global environment, Asian ethnic consumer food shopping pattern has changed in the British retail industry. Because of this, international marketers are highly focused on cross-cultural research is done into the subculture of the national culture.

Shopping patterns for consumers are changing dramatically. Once people tended to go to the shop to buy their desired products, but now people mostly prefer to buy online (Skrovan, 2019). Buying daily life essentials is now just a few clicks away for most. If someone wants to book a ticket, wants to visit somewhere, or needs medical help, this all can be done online within a matter of seconds. As a result, daily life has become easier because of this internet facility. However, there are some disadvantages to the usages of online services. These include the payment system, the risk of personal information theft, spamming, virus threats, delay in the delivery of the products and wrong items delivered.

Brumbaugh and Rosa (2009) demonstrated on promotional products. They stated ethnic consumers are highly likely to attract with the promotional offers. Same as Jamal et al. (2012) supported their statement saying promotional offers works as a stimulus for the ethnic consumers. Due to the massive market potential, the marketers need to focus on the ethnic consumer marketing strategy to find how the ethnic market will be better engaged with online shopping.

The researcher as a minority ethnic consumer has faced some difficulties while doing online shopping in the UK (e.g., less trust, perceived risk, experience). Moreover, the researcher experience in managing and working in an online shopping business in the UK for a few years. The online shopping obstacles and difficulties face by the researcher have motivated to study ethnic consumer online buying behaviour in the UK. This research has focuses on the online shopping behaviour of ethnic consumer from the online grocery sector.

1.1.1 Concept of online shopping

Online shopping is an electronic facility which allows buyers and sellers to buy and sell products or services using the internet. Consumers search for their desired products or services using the internet and compare products and pay via the internet. Products can be found by searching on websites and it is possible to compare prices among different stores. In some cases, consumers pay on delivery. Online shopping can be done from anywhere if one has access to the internet. Nowadays, people do most of the online shopping through the use of smartphones, computers, laptops and tablets.

1.1.2 History of online shopping

In developing the internet, selling products was one of the key factors in helping with the funding of technological advancements. Initially, it was called an “American phenomenon” but not long after many other countries started using online services. Countries including China and the United Kingdom are now very advanced in the use of online sectors. The growth of the internet and secure online systems has been developing since 1994. In the first stage of the development of the internet, companies only posted product information online. With the advancement of secure online systems, product information developed to the creation of online buying channels.

Michael Aldrich (an English entrepreneur) developed online shopping in 1979 (Moore, 2019). At first, he connected domestic TV to a real-time transaction processing computer via a domestic processing line. He also used high-capacity telecommunication links to the home. In 1994, with the sale of a Sting Album, the development of internet shopping began. Thereafter,

with the advancement of technological innovation and the world wide web, internet shopping has reached a high level of effectiveness and efficiency.

The Statistical Portal (2018) reported in 2018 that the volume of online sales is soon expected to reach \$653 billion U.S. dollars. China has the biggest online economy in the world and its biggest online market is on Alibaba.com. In March 2018 Alibaba recorded online sales of \$20.8 billion U.S dollars (Statistic, 2018). The fastest growing online markets are currently India and Indonesia followed by Mexico and China. The growth of online shopping depends on the efficiency of an e-commerce system, and the availability of the product online. History of the online market development shown in table 1.1.

Table 1:1 History of online market development

1960	Electronic data interchange
1979	First online shopping developed by Michael Aldrich
1981	Business to the business transaction by the UK based Thomson Holidays
1990	First worldwide web server and browser developed
1992	First online bookstore developed
1994	First pizza sold online
1995	Amazon, eBay, and online banking launched
1996	Over 40 million people have internet access and online sales surpass \$1 billion
1998	Google launched as a search engine to find a product easily
1999	PayPal launched for online payment systems; China introduced the biggest online site named Alibaba
2001	The European Union began to highlight online crime, Amazon launched mobile services
2003	Apple launched the iTunes store
2004	Credit card companies create PCI data security standards
2005	YouTube was launched
2006	Facebook begins selling advertisements
2008	Online purchase made on mobile phones
2009	Bitcoin became the first decentralized cryptocurrency
2010	Smartphone card reader launched; China hits the highest internet users record
2012	E-commerce sales hit \$1 trillion for the first time
2015	Amazon.com records a booming sale
2016	Alibaba entered India

(Source: Moore, 2019; Narusyte, 2016)

Joshua (2018) wrote in a blog on how online shopping spending differed throughout the world. The UK is in the number one position of completing online transactions and Germany is in number 10 (table 1.2). The Statistical Portal (2018) published a report on selected products purchased online. Results show that the highest number (57%) of internet users bought clothing online with the second-highest buying shoes (47%), and the third highest (40%) buying electronics. A smaller percentage was spent on gardens accessories and pet's products (13%).

Table 1:2 Biggest online shopping spending by top ten countries (2018)

Rank	Country	Ecommerce spend per capita
1	United Kingdom	\$4201
2	United States	\$3428
3	South Korea	\$2591
4	France	\$1946
5	China	\$1855
6	Australia	\$1764
7	Canada	\$1746
8	Japan	\$1488
9	Israel	\$1361
10	Germany	\$1283

(Source: Joshua, 2018)

1.1.3 Online shopping in the UK

British online shoppers spend more than any other countries online shoppers (Clark et al., 2015). The BBC (2017) reported that the UK is higher than Norway, the USA, and Australia with online card payments. The report also suggested that payment system security and delivery efficiency of the British online infrastructure leads the online shopping world. A large portion of the spending in the UK goes to entertainment tickets, food orders online. The UK was the third-largest e-commerce market in the world in 2015, and 80% of the British internet users use online shopping, which is the highest internet shopping percentage in Europe (Statistical portal, 2018).

The Financial Times (2018) reported that the sales of non-food items online in the UK have increased from 11.6% in 2012 to 24.1% in December 2017. It also reports that clothing sales have steadily decreased from 2016, but offline spending on clothing has increased. Popularity has risen in online products largely thanks to same day or next day delivery. Some sellers have also provided a service in which the customers can choose and compare (e.g., customers can order five shirts, try them all, on, and then send four back). This has led to further popularity of online shopping.

The Statistics Portal (2018) reported that in the UK at least 81.2% of the consumer look at the products online first, then later goes to the store to find the best deal. Twenty-three percent of consumers reported that they do a lot of research before they buy anything either online or on the high street. More than half of people tend to buy from the same retailers.

1.1.4 Online grocery shopping

Online grocery shopping is gaining popularity in the UK. Morganosky et al. (2000) explained that online grocery shopping does not depend on the number of people living in the household, but that children and gender are far more important factors in buying online grocery products.

Age is also an important factor in online grocery shopping. The age bracket of the over 50's is far less likely to use online services compared to younger people.

According to retail analysts IGD, online grocery shopping in the UK is currently the fastest-growing purchase channel in terms of value and growth. In 2016, average online grocery sales reached £141.9 million, which is double the amount of 2010 (Statistical portal, 2018). There are home delivery and online collection services available from online sellers. Some of the most advanced online grocery sellers in the UK are Tesco, ASDA, and Sainsbury's. There is a website called mysupermarket.com, which collates all online grocery retailers into one platform, which allows consumers to compare prices. It is forecasted that the United Kingdom will be the second-largest online grocery market by 2020 after China. Consumer behaviour has shifted to buying cheaper grocery products because of the post-Brexit uncertainty (Statistical Portal, 2018).

1.2 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Researcher in this section describes about the research problem and explain the personal journey of doing this study. The researcher discovered the importance of researching the ethnic consumer market in the UK while managing and working with the online business sector. Because businesses are neglecting ethnic minority consumers. Seventy-seven percent of British Asians and seventy-eight percent of Black British consumers think that companies' marketing policies are not focusing on them (Stirling, 2017; Campaign, 2019). It is normally stated by marketers that the ethnic community market is very small in the UK (Roberts et al., 2003). However, data has proven that the number of ethnic consumers is increasing day by day. The Office for National Statistics (2019) states in a report from the 2011 census that the percentage of the ethnic minority population in London is increasing rapidly and showed a decrease in the white population. The white population in the 2011 census is 86% of the population, whereas in 1991 it was 94.1%. Considering a large number of ethnic populations in the UK, there are not many studies measuring the behaviour of ethnic people.

Second, the researcher has experienced the problem and difficulties faced by the ethnic consumer to do online shopping in the UK. They face the problem of doing online shopping because of language, education, perceived risk etc. Third, ethnic consumers have cultural limitations (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998) such as buying Halal food, attending British cultural activities. which put them away from the British cultural activities. Due to this fact, the researcher wants to show the significance of researching the ethnic consumer. The researcher wants to emphasise on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour and how the

behaviour change over time. Ethnic consumers have huge market potential and marketers need to address the potential of the ethnic market.

The findings of the study can be used by business retailers in the UK to formulate their business strategy. It will help grocery e-retailers to apply greater time and energy interrogating the purchasing data of the ethnic consumer in order to identify specific aspects of their behaviour that may lead to profitable outcomes. Similarly, grocery e-retailers may find some risk mitigation strategy to overcome the possible loss of their business. Though this research is based in the UK, findings of the study can apply to the ethnic origin countries to frame their online business.

1.3 THE STUDY RATIONALE

In the UK the ethnic consumer is increasing and as a result, some multinational companies are focusing on their behaviour and attitudes to make their business strategy, so that they can sell more of their products. In different situations and cultural contexts, consumers act differently when choosing what to buy online. Companies often create promotional campaigns to attract consumers and the reaction from consumers depends on many factors. However, little research has been done to identify factors related to ethnic consumer online shopping and how to advertise effectively to ethnic consumers in the UK. Research also showed that Asians are the fastest-growing population in the UK. Below are some important points that focus on the importance of studying ethnic consumer behaviour.

Financial portfolio: The ethnic population has a very high financial portfolio in the UK. Stirling (2017) claims that in 2015 the ethnic minority population had a disposable income of £300 billion, but 30% of companies failed to focus in any way on this category of consumer. Similarly, Trudy Simpson (2012) reported that black consumers are worth £300 billion, and the British companies are not showing any effort to focus them.

Young age: Britain's ethnic minorities are younger than the rest of the country. Young consumers tend to contribute to the economy far more than the older generation. The Office for national statistics (2018) published a result based on the 2011 census that 43% of people from Asian ethnic groups and 45% from other ethnic groups are aged 20-39 years old; these were the highest percentages in the age range out of all ethnic groups. Results also indicated that 52.8% of people from Black ethnic groups were aged between 18-49 years.

Growth of ethnic consumer: The percentage of ethnic people is increasing continuously in the UK. Studying ethnic consumer behaviour will help companies to better advertise and as a

result appeal to ethnic minorities more. Ethnic consumers have significant disposable income, and they are likely to spend more than the national average for spending.

Cultural limitation: Ethnic consumers have cultural beliefs that pass from generation to generation. Moreover, ethnic consumers are constantly influenced by Western culture, whether that is in the home, the workplace, or educational institutions. A study by an expert based at the Centre for Social Investigation at Nuffield College, University of Oxford, claims that individuals from ethnic minority backgrounds have to send 80% more applications to get a positive response than a white consumer of British origin (Siddique, 2019). This discrimination put away the majority of the ethnic consumer to get the opportunity to engage with Western culture. Similarly, ethnic communities are often diverted from mainstream culture, often through their own choice. For example, some Asian communities never move away from their traditional culture and all social activity they arrange is in the context of their traditional culture (Maxwell, 2012). However, younger generations are more likely to adapt to mainstream culture because of mixed-gender socialising, workplace and educational institutions.

1.4 THE AIM, RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND OBJECTIVES

1.4.1 Aim of the research

The research aim is to focus on how ethnic consumers behave whilst doing online shopping in the UK. It also attempts to provide a clear idea of ethnic consumer characteristics and ethnic online market in the UK.

The findings of this investigation will help to understand what factors play important role in the adoption of ethnic consumer online shopping. The study will focus on purchasing grocery products online to find out what the online buying habits of ethnic consumers are. A conceptual framework will be developed from the literature review, which helps to show factors relating to online shopping. Primary data has been collected for this study and has been studied to check for any errors.

1.4.2 Research questions

Research questions help to focus on the investigation. Research questions are the fundamental core of research, which guide how to proceed with research (e.g., research methodology, analysis, reporting). There are two research questions in this study:

Q1. Do ethnic consumers behave differently when they shop online?

Q2. How do ethnic consumers accept the technology that is needed when making online purchase decisions?

1.4.3 Research Objectives

Research objectives give a clear structure to help with investigating the variables. The researcher experienced an online business scenario in the UK and the objectives have developed from the knowledge gathered from ethnic consumer online shopping behaviour. Four objectives have been developed to achieve the overarching aim of the research. Significant amounts of research have been undertaken to understand ethnic consumers' buying habits online. Ethnic consumers and mainstream consumers have been categorised to find out the factors that affect ethnic consumers the most.

The objectives are as follows:

Objective-1: To identify and assess the characteristics of the online ethnic consumer

Objective-2: To evaluate how culture affects ethnic consumer online buying behaviour

Objective-3: To examine factors for the ethnic consumer's adoption of technologies

Objective-4: To investigate how ethnic consumers build up their trust in online purchasing with technology

Table 1:3 Research direction

Research aim	Research Questions	Research Objectives
To examine ethnic consumer online buying behaviour in relation to grocery purchasing	Q1. Do ethnic consumers behave differently when they shop online?	Objective-1. To identify and assess the characteristics of online ethnic consumers.
		Objective-2. To evaluate how culture affects ethnic consumer online buying behaviour.
	Q2. How do ethnic consumers accept the technology that is needed when making online purchase decisions?	Objective-3. To examine the factors for the ethnic consumer's adoption of technologies.
		Objective-4. To investigate how ethnic consumers built up their trust in online purchasing with technology.

1.5 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study makes use of field research. This study has developed a hypothesis and it draws a conceptual model with many factors. These include demographic, culture, trust, satisfaction. The hypotheses are tested through scientific paradigms and theories in a context. Data has been collected through highly structured questionnaires (survey methods) and quantified data. Self-administered questionnaires and online questionnaires have also been used to collect the data. Convenience sampling methods used from the randomly chosen respondents. The majority of responses came from London. Descriptive and inferential statistics are used to analyse the data.

1.6 DISSERTATION STRUCTURE

To achieve the research objectives, this dissertation has been structured into six chapters. The summary of each chapter is presented in diagram 1.1.

Figure 1:1: The dissertation Structure

Chapter 1: Chapter 1 discuss the introduction to online grocery shopping and the background of online shopping. The history of online shopping has also been discussed in this chapter insignificant detail. Some statistical information has been provided to help better understand and put into context how online shopping works in the UK and around the world. Chapter 1 has been designed to fully explain the depth of online shopping. Research aims and objectives

have been developed to understand the actual scenario of the research. This chapter also reviews a brief methodology of the research.

Chapter 2: This chapter provides detailed information on ethnic consumers. This chapter explains the ethnic-marketing environment for ethnic consumers. Additionally, how ethnic communities developed in the UK is explained in this chapter. Comparisons have been made between different ethnic groups in this chapter. Cultural practices of ethnic consumers are also highlighted in this chapter.

Chapter 3: A critical review of selected literature relating to online grocery shopping and ethnic consumers is discussed in this chapter. Consumer behaviour is discussed in broad strokes along with different stages of the consumer buying process and all the related factors. The definition of an ethnic consumer is discovered through research from different literature. Problems and opportunities for online shopping and online grocery shopping are also discussed. A conceptual framework is developed. The Technology Acceptance Model and the Theory of Planned Behaviour is highlighted in this chapter.

Chapter 4: This chapter describes the research design. The Saunders Research Onion is used in this research. There were a few steps that were followed in the research methodology. These are as follows: philosophy, approach to theory development, methodological approach, research strategy, time horizon, data collection, and data analysis.

Chapter 5: Data analysis is the main focus of this chapter. Primary data is collected and is discussed and analysed in this chapter. The analysis involves inferential and descriptive statistics. The different frequency distribution is shown for the variables. Some crosstabulation is shown among variables. Looking for correlations, normality distribution, and regression analysis is undertaken. A summary of the findings is explained in this chapter.

Chapter 6: This chapter describes the findings of the research. Findings are described according to the hypothesis that has been formulated. This chapter states whether the hypothesis supports the assumption made by the researcher, or whether it contradicts the assumption. There are sections written on demography and online grocery shopping, consumer culture, and online grocery shopping. Ethnicity and online grocery shopping are also discussed in this chapter. This chapter manages to develop an evolving conceptual framework based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. This chapter outlines the conclusion and recommendations of the study. The conclusion is written as per the objectives of the research. The study is summarised, and the findings are stated in this chapter. At the end of this part, some recommendations for future research are highlighted. There was a research gap which, is also mentioned in this chapter.

CHAPTER 2: ETHNIC MINORITY OVERVIEW

This chapter focuses on the increase in the number of people of ethnic minorities in the UK over recent years. The chapter outlines the percentage and number of ethnic people compared to White British or White Irish people. This chapter also discusses the reason behind ethnic migration, the culture and background of ethnic people, and how ethnic marketing is developing as of recent years and as a result is getting more priority in the UK.

2.1 THE ETHNIC-MARKETING ENVIRONMENT

To formulate an effective marketing strategy, environmental marketing analysis is helpful (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). Marketing audience strategies include demographics, lifestyles, culture, education, and employment.

2.1.1 Demographics

It has been found that ethnic people are a relatively younger population of people compared to the white population in the UK. In 2011 in the UK (England and Wales only) a census reported that there was an ethnic population of 14% compared to a white population of 86% (Office for national statistics, 2013). Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) stated that the ethnic market has a very good potential of being the next “marketing battleground”.

2.1.2 Lifestyle

Ethnic groups tend to have a larger family size than the white population. In 2011 National statistics data reported that Asian families of mostly Bangladeshis and Pakistanis often consist of six or more people (Office for National Statistics, 2011). From a qualification and business background, South Asians, particularly Indian communities, are at the most economically advanced position in the UK and Maung et al. (1996) reported that Indians have taken over from the Jewish community and that they are now the most upwardly mobile group.

2.1.3 Education/employment

A survey done by the UK department of education reported that a high percentage of students of an ethnic minority are studying after the age of 16 (at University level). From 2004-2013, amongst ethnic students, the educational improvement was tremendous. As of recent years, Bangladeshi and Pakistani students in the UK have made marked improvements in terms of learning and progressing. In 2003 they scored below British children in terms of grades and overall learning success, but in 2013 they achieved the benchmark set by White children (Strand, 2015). Comparing the educational improvement, the group are continually developing in the job market sector, especially in the fields of medicine, accountancy, computer

consultancy, and legal services (Maung et al., 1996). However, there is some shocking discrimination when searching for jobs, reported on by the Guardian in 2019 (Siddique, 2019). The report says that people of ethnic minorities have to send 80% more job applications compared to the mainstream population. Proportions of students of an ethnic minority are presented in table 2.1.

Table 2:1 Proportion of students of ethnic minority: England 2003 and 2013

Ethnic group	2003		2013		Change % points
	N	%	N	%	
White	5,590,100	85.9	5,207,830	78.3	-7.5
White British	5,418,900	83.2	4,877,300	73.4	-9.9
Irish	26,500	0.4	21,800	0.3	-0.1
Traveller of Irish heritage	3,800	0.1	4,555	0.1	0.0
Gypsy/ Roma	6,000	0.1	16,735	0.3	0.2
Any other White background	134,900	2.1	287,435	4.3	2.3
Mixed	169,000	2.6	306,890	4.6	2.0
White and Black Caribbean	60,700	0.9	92,505	1.4	0.5
White and Black African	15,000	0.2	36,730	0.6	0.3
White and Asian	33,300	0.5	68,605	1.0	0.5
Any other Mixed background	60,000	0.9	109,060	1.6	0.7
Asian	440,600	6.8	678,680	10.2	3.4
Indian	153,800	2.4	175,035	2.6	0.3
Pakistani	175,200	2.7	262,535	3.9	1.3
Bangladeshi	70,300	1.1	107,320	1.6	0.5
Chinese	22,800	0.4	107,815	0.4	0.0
Any other Asian background	41,300	0.6	25,975	1.6	1.0
Black	233,000	3.6	353,915	5.3	1.7
Black Caribbean	97,300	1.5	90,455	1.4	-0.1
Black African	108,400	1.7	220,785	3.3	1.7
Any other Black background	27,300	0.4	42,675	0.6	0.2
Any other ethnic group	54,300	0.8	100,860	1.5	0.7
Classified	6,509,800	100	6,648,195	100	0.0
Unclassified	272,600	4.0	64,450	1.0	-3.1
Minority Ethnic Pupils	1,930,220	16.8	1,770,895	26.6	9.9
All pupils			6,782,400		6,712,645

Note: the data is based on students at compulsory school age (5-16 years).

Source: Strand (2015)

2.2 RISE OF ETHNIC MINORITIES IN BRITAIN

A question which needs to be answered first is who Ethnic people in the UK are being. People (immigrants) who came to the UK, especially workers in the 1950s and 1960s from Southern Europe, the Caribbean, and the Indian subcontinent, have settled into communities with British-born children and grandchildren (Maxwell, 2012). Roberts et al. (2003) stated ethnic minorities

are a relatively small community with a way of life which is different in salient respects from that of the majority, and probably as a result of the communities being of fairly recent foreign extraction.

Segal and Sosa (1983) have pointed out how ethnic research was not prioritised by companies. In the USA there were a few companies who researched ethnic minorities. However, in the UK there were not many companies who looked for a well-structured plan for ethnic consumers (Segal and Sosa, 1983). But marketing practitioners have pointed out that it is necessary to research ethnic marketing (Sills and Desai, 1996). Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) indicated that different cities in the UK have differing percentages of ethnic people. London, Birmingham, Manchester, Bradford and Sheffield have a large number of ethnic populations and the spending of the population ethnic minorities in the UK cannot be neglected.

In Britain “multicultural ethnic” falls into different ethnic groups. Multi-ethnic groups include “White ethnics” (such as Irish, Polish, Greeks and Turks) and “non-white ethnics” (Africans, Asians, people of Caribbean origin, Chinese). The main reason for the increase in ethnic minorities in the UK is because of Britain’s colonial history in Africa, the Caribbean, and Indian Sub-continent (Maxwell, 2017). The percentages of people of ethnic minorities show that this number will rise more dramatically in the future.

Available statistics show that there is currently a steady increase in the percentage of the ethnic population compared to the percentage of ethnically white British people. Social data indicates that between 1981 and 1990 there was a 23% increase in groups of ethnic minorities compared to a 1% rise in the white population (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). The 2011 census has shown that England and Wales have become far more ethnically diverse with groups of ethnic minorities continuing to rise since 1991. The portion of the population that identifies with a white ethnic group has decreased from 94% in 1991 to 86% in 2011. In 2011, 87% of the population (48.6 million people) was born in the UK and 13% of the population (7.5 million people) was born outside of the UK (Office for National Statistics, 2016). Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) identified the major ethnic groups as South Asian and African Black.

Asians – Indians, Pakistanis, and Bangladeshis represent 51% of the ethnic population of the UK according to data collected in 1998. Indians are the single largest group of the ethnic population in the UK. The second-largest ethnic group, 25%, is people of Black African descent. Arabs, Chinese, and mixed-race individuals had a representation of 24%. The percentage of Ethnic populations born in the UK, according to the 2011 census, is presented in table 2.2.

Table 2:2 UK and non-UK born population by ethnicity in England and Wales, 2011

Ethnic Group	The UK born		Non-UK born	
	Number	%	Number	%
White	44,774	92.2	3,435	45.8
British	44,186	91.0	949	12.6
Irish	178	0.4	354	4.7
Gypsy or Irish Traveller	51	0.1	7	0.1
Other White	360	0.7	2,126	28.3
Mixed/Multiple ethnic groups	985	2.0	239	3.2
White and Black Caribbean	401	0.8	26	0.3
White and Black African	113	0.2	53	0.7
White and Asian	271	0.6	71	0.9
Other Mixed	200	0.4	90	1.2
Asian/Asian British	1,770	3.6	2,443	32.6
Indian	606	1.2	807	10.7
Pakistani	631	1.3	493	6.6
Bangladeshi	232	0.5	215	2.9
Chinese	93	0.2	300	4.0
Other Asian	207	0.4	628	8.4
Black/African/Caribbean/Black British	873	1.8	992	13.2
African	323	0.7	666	8.9
Caribbean	358	0.7	237	3.2
Other Black	192	0.4	89	1.2
Other ethnic groups	168	0.3	395	5.3
Arab	64	0.1	167	2.2
Any other ethnic group	105	0.2	228	3.0
		100		100
All	48,571	86.6	7,505	13.4

Source: Office for National Statistics (2016)

2.3 THE REASON BEHIND ETHNIC MIGRATION TO BRITAIN

Britain, like many other Western European countries, received a large number of migrants because of a labour shortage after the Second World War (Maxwell, 2017). The reasons for the labour shortage were:

- rapid industrial economic expansion.
- high immigration rates created acute labour shortages.
- wartime deaths.

Due to the labour shortage, European countries, mainly the British and French, started to show an increasing demand for foreign workers. The migrants that came to Europe came from a variety of countries, and the majority of the migrants decided to go to European countries because of connections from the colonial era and legal privileges. During 1962 people from

the Caribbean did not have to get any legal permission to settle in Britain because the island was not independent.

Same as migrating to Britain was much easier for South Asians for several reasons. The Indian subcontinent got independence from Britain in 1947, and in 1948 the British nationality act created the “New Commonwealth” which included colonies as well as independent Commonwealth countries. The nationality act allowed Indians and Pakistanis to retain their status as British subjects and therefore migrate to Britain without Visas (Maxwell, 2017). Both of these groups (people from the Caribbean and South Asians) were eventually benefited in the 1950s with a new law, but the situation became harder when ‘anti-immigrants’ voices started to rise in Britain. Immigrant restriction laws were implemented during the 1960s, 1970s, and 1980s.

However, the anti-immigrant laws were somewhat restricted by the fact that the family reunification system allowed migrants to bring their partners or family members into Britain. This meant that the percentage of Ethnic minorities continued to increase in Britain even during a clampdown on migration. Immigrants came from a variety of places in Asia. These immigrants included Sikhs from eastern Punjab in the North of India, Hindus from Gujrat (the west of India), and Muslim and Parsees from various locations. Muslim immigrants also came from Pakistan and Sylhet (now Bangladesh). Britain’s population was also boosted dramatically by Indians who came from Kenya. In 1971 in Britain, the total population was 5,347,000 of whom 750,000 had been born in India or Pakistan (Office for National Statistics, 2011).

Figure 2:1 A classification of immigrants to the UK

Source: Stillwell and Ham (2010, p.7)

2.4 THE CARIBBEAN VERSUS SOUTH ASIAN GROUPS

Britain's colonies in the Caribbean lasted for more than 300 years. English was made the official language for all Caribbean colonies and as a result, the main curriculum was formulated prioritising the English education systems and standards. Subjects taught included British history, literature, art, and social traditions. The fact that immigrants from the Caribbean had gone through this education system and had experienced some of the British cultures gave them an edge over other nationalities who migrated to Britain. Caribbean migrants not only got British cultural habits, but they were also often able to maintain a roughly similar daily routine and were able to work in jobs in the public sectors. In contrast, South Asian countries had been colonies for a far shorter period of time and the massive cultural impact that the British had on Caribbean countries was not nearly as large for South Asian countries. Of course, migrants from South Asian countries were socialised and adapted to the British culture, but it took longer, which gave Caribbean immigrants an initial advantage in the job market as well as in adapting to a new culture.

The British East Indian Trading Company was formed in 1600 with the main aim of economic expansion. British rulers employed local bureaucrats to deal with the administration of different areas. In South Asia, people weren't encouraged to speak English. Because of this, South Asian migrants were more likely to speak their native language. Research in 1974 surveying ethnic minorities stated that 15 percentage of South Asians spoke no English at all, comparing to 0 percent of Caribbean migrants. Additionally, 30% of South Asians were fluent in English, compared to 58% of Caribbean migrants (Maxwell, 2012).

2.5 CULTURAL AND RELIGIOUS PRACTICES

Language fluency has influenced cultural and religious practice. Maxwell (2012) describes

“The same colonial-era legacies that shaped language fluency have influenced cultural and religious practices. As a result, of their prior exposure to British culture, Caribbean's have been less likely than South Asian groups to engage in cultural and religious practices that are distinctive from mainstream British practices” (p. 39).

It is considered a distinctive cultural practice when individuals of Caribbean descent practice their culture (culinary customs, artistic practices, and hairstyles). As a result, many Caribbean migrants showed themselves as a proper British culture. Richmond describes a study that was conducted in Bristol in 1965 that asked questions about cultural knowledge and slang and found that less than half of the Pakistani and Indian population answered 17% of the questions, compared to 90% of the Caribbean population (C. et al., 1975).

South Asians are mainly Hindu, Muslim, and Sikh and they have their strong cultural background. During the 1950s and 1960s, Sikhs struggled to find employment because of their long beard and the insistence to cover their heads with turbans. Employers counted this as suspicious behaviour, but this was resolved in 1983 when the House of Lords issued a rule that Sikhs should be considered an ethnic group and as a result might have their cultural practices (Maxwell, 2012).

Muslims are separated from British culture, amongst others because of religious conflicts. Alcohol is prohibited in Islam and other cultural activities that are encouraged or permitted in the West, are not behaviours or attitudes that are permissible in Islam. Most Muslims always consider whether food is Halal before joining any party, and that restricts them from joining in any British cultural activities (Bukhari et al, 2020). Fasting during the month of Ramadan and praying five times daily are also a restriction for Muslims to adjust to British work life and culture. Older generations of Muslims tend to wear traditional clothes and sometimes this was and still is seen with suspicion and distrust by some British people. More recent generations of Muslims tend to wear modern Western clothes, so this is less of a dividing factor than it used to be. Thus, depending on religious practises lifestyle purchase behaviour changes from people to people.

CHAPTER 3: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter aims to show the rationale for undertaking this study. The study focuses on different literature and the theories presented in the literature. By studying other literature, outcomes discovered by other researchers relating to ethnic consumer buying behaviour in the online sector can be analysed. The study draws a conceptual framework and builds up a hypothesis to test the variables.

3.1 CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

Solomon et al. (2014) and Kotler et al. (2016) define consumer buying behaviour as-

The study of the ways of buying and disposing of goods, services, ideas, or experience by the individuals, groups, and organisations to satisfy their needs and wants. Marketers may use the knowledge gained from studying consumer buying behaviour to set their strategies towards offering the right products. Schurr and Ozanne (1985) and Pickton et al. (2015) evaluate the importance of consumer behaviour. They claim that better awareness about consumer buying behaviour is a major positive contributing factor in boosting a country's economy. Consumer demographics, personal characteristics, and attitudes towards buying online relate to each other (Bellman et al, 1996). They judge that if someone has a wired lifestyle and is more concerned about time, they tend to do online shopping

In addition, many marketers can identify the behavioural entities of consumers and as a result, can make policies much better. However, it is also important to consider a country's situation before formulating any strategies. Online shopping facilities are different from country to country and strategies to develop the online business depends on the infrastructure of the country.

Consumer online buying behaviour differs from traditional buying behaviour due to modern technologies such as the internet (Kotler et al., 2016). Bagga and Bhatt (2013) describe in their research that marketers used to market according to the traditional 4P's (products, place, price, and promotion) but that they are now using the internet as a new medium to reach the consumer.

Other researchers also claim that consumer shopping patterns have changed slowly from street shopping to virtual shopping (Kolodinsky et al., 2004; Kim and Park, 2005; Hamlett et al., 2008). Before creating a marketing strategy, companies need to first address the intrinsic and extrinsic factors of consumer buying behaviour. Kotler et al. (2016) claim that every consumer

has an inner mind which leads them to make decisions about what they are going to purchase. Consumers engage in a holistic approach to a marketing effort on part of the marketing strategy that has been proposed by a marketer to make a favourable image of an online marketing strategy. Consumer purchase decisions depend on the brand, price, reputation, source and method of payment (Kotler et al, 2016). A consumer buying behaviour model is explained in figure 3.1.

Figure 3:1 Consumer buying behaviour model or the ‘black box’ model

Source: Kotler et al. (2016)

3.1.1 Stages of the consumer buying process

The Traditional Consumer Decision Model states that consumer purchase decisions normally start with need awareness, then moves onto information search, then alternative evaluations, before deciding to purchase, and lastly post-purchase behaviour (Katawetawaraks and Wang, 2011). This is similar to how Kotler and Armstrong (2015) describe the five stages of the consumer online buying process where they decide which products and services to buy. These showed in figure 3.2.

Figure 3:2 Stages of the consumer buying process

Source: Kotler et al. (2016)

- I. **Need recognition:** the first step of the consumer buying process is need recognition. This is when a consumer desires or needs a product. Consumer needs come from internal or external stimuli. When a consumer needs or desires to buy a particular product from within, it is called internal stimuli, and when they see an advertisement or hear about a product's information from other friends it is called external stimuli. These stimuli lead a consumer to make a purchase decision (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).

Egan (2015) identifies three classes of problem-solving situations when consumers are making a purchase decision.

- a) **Extensive problem solving:** These types of problem-solving are related to alternative options of purchases or purchase with high social visibility (e.g., pieces of jewellery, cars).
- b) **Limited problem solving:** These types of problem-solving are about buying cheaper items which consumers buy on a regular basis (e.g., detergent, fruits, cigar).
- c) **Routinized problem solving:** When consumers make repeat purchases (e.g., milk, biscuit, toiletries).

If the product does not fulfil the desire expectation consumer get dissatisfied. There are a variety of ways in which consumers can be dissatisfied with the products they receive. The problem can arise for a number of reasons with the use of products (regular purchase), due to the service of the products (dissatisfaction), due to new products categories, by changing lifestyle etc.

- II. **Information search:** When a consumer decides to purchase a product, they often search for information about the product. This is the stage of the buying process where the customer is motivated to make a purchase. There are several ways to research a product. These include personal sources (such as family, friends, neighbours, acquaintances), commercial sources (advertising, salespeople, dealer web sites, packaging, displays), public sources (mass media, consumer rating organisations, online searches and peer reviews), and experimental sources (handling, examining, using the product) (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).
- III. **Evaluation of alternatives:** When a customer gets adequate information about a particular product, they then look for alternatives. Researchers call this stage the ‘buyer pre-decision process’. Depending on the customer, this route may take different routes. Consumers sometimes make their decision by getting help from friends or family (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).
- IV. **Purchase decision:** The consumer now makes the choice between products, “the buyer decision about which brand to purchase” (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015). When making this decision, two factors can come between the purchase. These factors are the attitudes of others to the product they may buy as well as unexpected situational factors. These two factors are something the buyer needs to keep into consideration when deciding to purchase something (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015).
- V. **Post-purchase behaviour:** This is the final stage where customer post-purchase behaviour occurs. “*The process in which customers take further action after purchasing, based on their satisfaction or dissatisfaction*” (Kotler & Armstrong, 2015). In this stage, the consumer wants to be sure that they will be satisfied with the product and hope that it will fulfil their needs. If the product(s) is unsatisfactory then the consumer can pass on negative feedback to other consumers quickly and effectively. To be safe from any negative impressions, companies need to make sure they fulfil customers’ needs. This will likely increase the loyalty level customers have towards the products a company sells. They will then pass on positive feedback which will continue to encourage other consumers to buy the product(s).

3.2 FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOUR

Considering what the consumer is likely to be influenced by is the most important factor when marketing products. The consumer’s buying behaviour process has a number of factors. Jobber (2016) and Kotler and Armstrong (2015) suggest that consumer buying behaviour is influenced by four major factors. Details of those factors are shown in figure 3.3 and table 3.1.

1. Cultural factors
2. Social factors
3. Personal factors
4. Psychological factor

Figure 3:3 Factors that influence consumer buying behaviour

Cultural	Social	Personal	Psychological	Buyer
Culture	Reference Group	Age & life Cycle stage	Motivation	
Subculture	Family	Occupational Economic circumstance	Perception	
Social Class	Roles & Status	Lifestyle Personal & Self Concept	Learning Beliefs & Attitudes	

Source: Kotler & Armstrong (2015)

1. **Cultural factors:** it is crucial to understand the needs and behaviours of an individual. Kotler & Armstrong (2015) indicated that human behaviour is a constant learning process throughout each individual’s life. Every individual learns their set belief from the socialisation process of their community and is influenced by their surroundings even if they don’t realise it. Schiffman and Kanuk (2006) list an individual’s values. These include success, achievement, freedom, individualism, youthfulness, and practicality. Cultural factors consist of culture, subculture, and social class.
2. **Social factors:** social factors consist of family, reference groups, roles, and status. Each social culture contains a different subculture. Table 3.1 has a brief description of different social factors that marketers follow to make a policy for customers.
3. **Personal factors:** Kotler et al. (2016) stated that an individual’s age, occupation, income, and lifestyle greatly influence a consumer buying decision-making process. High earning people are, for example, more likely to make purchases more frequently than low-income people.
4. **Psychological factors:** Some businesses use psychological marketing. Whenever an individual seeks any satisfaction from a product by using their sense of humour, they decide the subjectivity and objectivity of the products.

Table 3:1 Factors that influence consumer buying behaviour described

Cultural factors	Culture	Individuals socialise through different processes (family, peer group, different institutions e.g., educational, religious, family). All individuals hold to a set of beliefs and act accordingly.
	Subculture	To specify more easily, individuals are categorised by a subculture group which can include nationalities, racial and geographic regions.
	Social class	A social class group is a group which categorises the power, education, income and property of a particular group of society. British culture has three main categories. These are upper class, middle class, and lower class. Family status nowadays depends mostly on education and income.
Social factors	Reference group	Groups of people can easily influence another person's behaviour. These groups are normally membership or contractual, primary or normative groups, secondary groups, aspiration groups, formal groups.
	Family	Family influence, the individual's personality, characteristics, attitudes, and evaluation criteria. Parents teach children the way they believe is right in response to the culture they live in. When older, children can make their own decisions.
	Roles and status	Groups often have a hierarchical structure. The position of an individual in that hierarchy can heavily influence what happens to them in their life and what person they therefore become.
Personal factors	Age and life cycle stage	People of different ages tend to have different preferences due to experience or the lack of experience. These age groups have often grown up in completely different environments in terms of economic stability for example, which causes people of different ages to have different preferences.
	Occupational economic circumstances	People from differing occupations are likely to have different preferences in terms of products. A doctor may have different preferences to a lawyer because a doctor may know the health risks of a product to a greater extent than a lawyer. Or a lawyer may know about how a particular product was made and might decide not to buy it on ethical grounds whereas a doctor may perhaps be less aware of a particular ethical consideration when buying a product.
	Lifestyle	People have differing lifestyles and depending on those lifestyles their preferences for buying products is likely to change.
	Personal and self-concept	Some people have an unchangeable mindset and will not change their mind no matter the facts presented. Whereas other people are easily led and will change their mind constantly depending on what they have read or been told.
Psychological factors	Motivation	There are two types of motivational factors. The first one is biogenic needs, which are the basic needs that people need to survive such as food and water. The other motivational factor is psychogenic needs (e.g., recognition needs, esteem needs).
	Perception	Different people have differing opinions on the same products due to differing perspectives.
	Learning	Learning from peer groups, the media and entertainment can all influence people when making purchase decisions.
	Beliefs and attitude	Cultural and religious beliefs influence people to make different decisions on what products they buy.
Buyer		

Source: Adapted from ((Schiffman and Kanuk, 2006), (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015) and (Jobber, 2016)).

Motivation to buy certain products can come from several different factors. Motivation could be positive (problem removal, problem avoidance, incomplete satisfaction, mixed approach-avoidance and normal depletion) or it could be negative (sensory gratification, intellectual stimulation, and social conformity). Abraham Maslow in 1943 developed a model called 'Maslow's hierarchy of needs' where he describes the process of human motivations (Maslow, 1943). Maslow described "psychological" needs as basic needs (food, water, and sleep), "safety" needs as shelter and security needs, "belonging" and "love" needs (friendship and a desire for group acceptance), "esteem needs" (status, recognition and self-respect), "self-actualization needs" (the desire for self-fulfilment), and "self-transcendence" to describe human motivations pattern.

3.2.1 Characteristics of online buying behaviour

Wu (2003) identified that there are two types of factors that influence consumer online buying behaviour. These are external and internal factors. External factors include demographic, economic, social, situational, and technological considerations. Internal factors include beliefs and attitudes, learning, motives and needs, personality, perception, and values. Wu's (2003) study mainly focuses on four types of characteristics.

1. **Demographics:** consumer demographic characteristics include gender, age, education, income, interest, and living areas.
- **Gender:** male and female fashion styles are different. Depending on the different lifestyles, buying behaviour is different. In cases of more common items, there are more similarities. Common items include food, movies, entertainment. The research found that in most cases the majority of the buying decisions are taken by women (Wu, 2003; Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017). Liu et al. (2013) explained there is a significant difference between man and women online shopping. Men tend to do more online shopping than women. There are some other studies on online shoppers suggest that men tend to do more online shopping than women (Wood, 2011; Harris et al., 2017). However, Freeman (2009) found that women tend to do more online shopping.
- **Age:** As people grow up, their lifestyle is highly likely to change substantially. Purchase decisions are affected by their lifestyle and needs. Age is one of the most important factors for a consumer buying decision. When people get older, they often choose different brands. This is because they might buy brands that they have always bought but young people are more likely to experiment with new brands. In terms of online and technology use, older people tend to be more demotivated than younger people

(Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017). Marketers nowadays make their marketing strategy partly based on the age of the consumers.

- **Education:** Several studies have highlighted that high education led to greater online shopping intentions (Wu, 2003; Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017; Anesbury et al., 2016). An individual who has been educated is more likely to judge a product on its quality rather than just believing advertising. Less-educated individuals are likely to have less information about trusting advertising and likely haven't had the opportunity to ever think through whether companies can always be trusted when they are advertising (Reynolds and Olson, 2013).
- **Income:** Income is one of the most important factors in the consumer buying process. People considered to be of a higher class tend to be far choosier about the design and quality of products they potentially might buy. However, middle-class and lower-class people have to be far warier of any budgetary constraints. Income level varies by ethnic group. Income level of the different ethnic groups is shown in table 3.2.

Table 3:2 Percentage of households in weekly income bands from under £100 to over £1000, by ethnicity

	Up to £99	£100 to £199	£200 to £299	£300 to £399	£400 to £499	£500 to £599	£600 to £699	£700 to £799	£800 to £899	£900 to £999	£1000 or above
Ethnicity											
All	2	5	11	12	11	9	8	7	6	5	27
Bangladeshi	1	2	6	11	13	13	15	12	5	2	20
Chinese	5	5	9	10	8	10	8	6	4	7	29
Indian	2	3	7	6	7	6	7	7	6	7	42
Pakistani	2	7	7	8	13	12	10	8	6	5	20
Asian other	2	5	8	8	11	11	7	11	4	6	28
Black	4	6	10	15	11	11	9	7	5	4	19
Mixed	3	5	11	13	11	9	7	9	6	4	24
White British	2	5	11	12	11	9	7	7	6	5	26
White other	2	3	7	9	10	10	9	7	6	5	31
Other	3	4	8	13	10	12	7	7	5	4	27

(Source: Family Resource Survey, 2018)

It is generally argued that ethnic consumer online grocery shopping will get affected by demographic components. Kragh (1996) suggested that groceries are the most 'culturally-bound' food. Consumers often carefully choose the food they buy according to their own values and associated meanings. For instance, Muslims only buy meat that has been killed in a particular way and neither Jews nor Muslims eats pork. Hansen (2008) is correct than when he suggests that personal beliefs affect online grocery purchasing. Hansen also highlights how demographic influences can have an effect on what consumers buy.

Therefore, in terms of ethnic consumer demographic components hypothesis can be developed that:

H1a: There is a significant difference between the male and female in the factor influencing for online grocery shopping.

H1b: There is a significant difference between the age group of people and factors influencing for online grocery shopping.

H1c: Those with a higher level of education will have a higher online buying intention than those with a lower level of education.

2. **Purchase preferences:** which includes purchase motivation and preferences. Consumers preferences or tastes sometimes determine their purchase preference. Hobbies, new items or new models on the market push young or aged consumers to buy the product.
3. **Benefit perception:** it is the sum of online shopping advantages or satisfactions that meet an individual's needs or wants. In some cases, the consumer buys unwanted items when they receive any promotional offer or see any additional benefits from the products. These extra beneficial mindsets motivate a consumer to buy a product.
4. **Consumer lifestyle:** is a person's pattern of living. The way of living can determine a consumer's online buying behaviour. A consumer's lifestyle and socialisation are related. If a consumer gets socialisation from high-class society their living standard and expenditure certainly will be higher. Similarly, the lower-class society's living expenditure will be comparatively lower.

3.2.2 Stages of online buying behaviour

Anesbury et al. (2016) describe the stages of the consumer online buying process:

- A) **Category selection time:** When shopping online, some items take longer to find than others do. Anesbury et al. (2016) suggested that supermarkets should make less frequently bought items easier to find. Shampoo, for example, and other related items take a longer time to find on online shopping websites because shampoo is generally bought less frequently by consumers. Additionally, when selecting groceries, consumers often compare prices between different websites before making a purchase. Mysupermarket.com, for example, helps consumers to compare their products from different online companies (such as Tesco, ASDA, Sainsbury's, Liddle, Aldi, Waitrose, Poundland). This allows the consumer to buy the best quality product at the best possible price.

- B) Shopping trip duration online and in-store:** The duration of a shopping trip depends on the number of the items purchased. Offline shopping requires the shopper to physically go to the supermarket. This often means they will need to find a parking slot and they may need to pay for parking fees. Going to the shop also requires far more time management. Online shopping avoids all of these extra actions. Anesbury et al. (2016) stated in their research that in the grocery sector, the online consumer spends an average of 13 minutes to 40 minutes, depending on the internet browsing speed and the number of items purchased.
- C) New shopper learning:** New online shoppers take time to adapt to this new way of shopping. The shoppers who bought a particular item before can easily adapt and purchase the same product online. Frequent buyers or old buyers often know about the quality of products and the fair price for those products which helps them to easily decide what to buy.
- D) The extent of supermarket category page viewing:** When shopping in supermarkets, consumers can view the products they are looking to buy. The products can be viewed from different angles. Online consumers can see the sample of the product, and the online systems of a supermarket have a large number of brands.

Figure 3:4 Stages of the online buying process

3.3 FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMER ONLINE BUYING BEHAVIOUR

Electronic commerce or online C2C (Customer to Customer) business is now very popular all over the world, especially in developed countries (such as USA, Germany, UK) (Clark et al. 2015). Researching online consumer behaviour is very important due to the on-going high demand for the online market. Xu et al. (2010) highlighted some of the factors that online buying behaviour impacts. These are:

- Perceived risk
- Buyer factor: risk attitudes
- Seller factor: seller reputation
- Product factor: product price
- Product type

Perceived risk: This is an important factor for online transactions. The consumer faces risk and has to choose whether they believe they will get their assured warranty or insurance from any particular online transaction (Xu et al., 2010). This is because, in online transactions, people do not have a physical existence. Researchers stated that perceived risk impacts the consumer decision-making process, whether it is with online purchasing or online businesses (Shankar et al., 2002; Ranaweera, 2005; Xu et al, 2010; Solomon et al., 2014).

Buyer factor: risk attitudes: Xu et al. (2010) talk about risk attitudes. They defined that there are three kinds of buyers: risk-seeking, risk-neutral, and risk-adverse. Individuals who have a risk-seeking attitude tend to spend more time to avoid the negative side effect of online transactions and those who are risk adverse focus on negative impacts rather than positive factors (Antony et al., 2006).

Seller factor: seller reputation: Customers sometimes leave feedback for their previous transaction. High rating feedback creates a good reputation for the business.

“In C2C markets, a trader’s reputation score is based on the feedbacks and comments from previous trading experience. A trader can obtain high reputation through good reputation” (Xu et al., 2010, p.515).

Product factor: product price: Price and products are the most important factors in an e-commerce business. Price and product not only impact the physical marketplace but also the online environment. Depending on the product value, the chance of fraudulent activity increases (Xu et al., 2010).

Product Type: In C2C commerce, it is important to choose the right brand and product to ensure that the consumer gets the best value for their money. Online systems allow consumers to easily view a vast quantity of products. However, products can only be properly judged once they have been bought and tried out in person (Xu et al., 2010).

Rohm and Swaminathan (2004) suggest a couple of considerations all online consumers should address. These are the security of the transaction and how likely their privacy would be considered by the website they are buying from. Donthu and Garcia (1999) highlight some other considerations (cited by Browaeys and Price, 2015). These are the importance of avoiding risk, innovativeness of the products they are buying, brand consciousness, price consciousness,

the convenience of buying a product, the impulsiveness of some consumers, variety seeking propensity, attitude toward advertising, attitude toward shopping, and the attitude towards direct marketing. All these factors have a large influence on online shopping behaviour. The ease of navigating online websites is also a large factor in influencing online shopping behaviour according to Donthu and Garcia (1999).

Katawetawaraks and Wang (2011) attempt to categorise the reasons why consumers start to shop online. They categorise the factors into the following four categories:

1. Convenience
2. Information
3. Available products and services
4. Cost and time efficiency

1. Convenience: Online shopping is available 24 hours a day, every day of the week. Some companies that only provide services by phone have time limitations. Additionally, shops are only open at particular times. Shopping online is also far more comfortable for a lot of consumers because they don't have to interact with other people when making a purchase (Merz, 2013).

2. Information: It is far easier for consumers to find information about products they are thinking of buying online. This allows consumers to make purchasing decisions far more efficiently. Physical stores often don't have the same level of information about products and this may lead to consumers having to ask a sales assistant. This is an extra effort that most consumers would rather not have to put themselves through (Maxwell, 2012). Furthermore, online consumers can see other customer reviews which can further help them decide what to buy.

3. Available products and services: Consumers that shop online has a far larger variety of products to choose from. Nowadays most companies also have their store alongside online products. Some companies mostly focus on online products to save store and staff costs.

4. Cost and time efficiency: Online customers can often buy products at the same or a cheaper price compared to offline customers. Compared to street shops, online shopping has more variety which allows consumers to buy the right products at the cheapest price. Wessels and Drennan (2010) believe that time saved, costs saved, and the freedom of doing online transactions has influenced consumers to move to online purchasing.

Additionally, Anesbury et al. (2016) highlighted a few advantages of shopping online:

- Shopping is completed far quicker than if consumers were shopping in a physical store.
- Brands can be selected very quickly.
- Learning how to navigate category selections is very easy.

3.3.1 Consumer attitudes and intentions towards purchasing online

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) wrote: “Attitude refers to a person’s favourable or unfavourable evaluation of an object, beliefs represent the information he has about the object” (p. 12).

Consumer attitudes and intentions have a large influence on online purchasing (figure 3.5). Consumers make purchasing decisions based on their attitudes and intentions (Wang et al., 2006; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012; Pikkarainen et al., 2004; Wessels and Drennan, 2010; Marakarkandy et al., 2017). Wang et al. (2006) demonstrated some customers believe that online banking services, mobile banking, or online purchases cost money and this causes consumers not to use online shopping. They also demonstrated that the cost of not only paying banking or online fees but also internet connection fees was a significant combination of factors that stopped people from purchasing online.

Kotler and Armstrong (2015) suggested that consumer purchasing decisions are mainly influenced by social, cultural, personal, and psychological factors. These factors cannot be controlled at all times. Wu (2003) suggested that external influences also have a large impact on consumers choices. External influences include demographic, social, economic, situational, and technological factors. Internal factors include beliefs and attitudes, motives and needs, learning, personality, perception, and values involved.

Figure 3:5 Consumer characteristics and attitude toward online shopping

Wu (2003) stated that consumers have an increasingly positive attitude toward online shopping. Attitudes towards online shopping are measured by a variety of aspects. Some of these aspects are as follows; the effectiveness of online shopping, as well as how it is more modern, so people perceive it to be better, the convenience of online shopping, how much information is available comparing online shopping to offline shopping, multiform and safety, service quality, delivery speed, homepage design, selection freedom, and company or brand name familiarity. Wu

(2003) has shown how consumer buying behaviour is related to external and internal factors as shown in figure 3.6.

Figure 3:6 Factors of consumer buying behaviour

Source: (Wu, 2003)

Engel et al. (1995) suggest that consumer beliefs and attitudes influence their search behaviour when online shopping. An individual requires a computer or other device and internet accessibility to be able to search for a product. Sainiee (1998) highlights some factors that have an influence on online shopping (cited by Browaeys and Price, 2015). These include language, culture and government regulation. Consumers intentions and motivational factors have been discussed in the Theory of Planned Behaviour (detailed in section 3.10.2). Some researchers have indicated that, for consumers shopping online, past behaviour is a key factor in how consumers behave. Experience can lead consumers to behave similarly or differently depending on their levels of satisfaction from the last time they made a purchase. Liang and Huang (1998) indicated that experience acts as a mediator for consumer buying intentions.

Yavas (2001) states that attractive price influences online consumer. Competitive prices in online markets attract customers and consumers who are more price concerned. Consumers who are more price-conscious tend to spend more time comparing prices on online markets in order to find the best deal. Donthu and Garcia (1999) studied online consumer behaviour and they revealed that internet consumers tend to be more innovative and impulsive. They also have a higher desire to search for varieties of products and as a result have a positive attitude towards online purchasing (Cited by Liu et al., 2013). Blomqvist et al. (2015) stated experience changes consumer attitudes towards online grocery shopping. They explained if someone has bought

grocery online is more likely to buy more. Because consumer in the online grocery sector can compare the price with the different supermarket to choose the cheapest product.

Liu et al. (2013) found that online shopping brings happiness and relaxation to many consumers. They found that some customers experience more enjoyment because there is no pressure from salespeople to buy the products. Some customers like the fact that they are able to find out about availability and order at the same time. Foss and Bower (1986) mentioned that consumers plan relates to a goal-sub goal process to search and order a product. They also demonstrate that the goal is normally organised in a hierarchy of sub-goals. They pointed out the logical explanation that there is a hierarchical relationship between products search intention and products purchasing intentions. Therefore, searching for a product online and intentions to buy online imply in a subcomponent of one goal.

The previous experience of online shopping consumers has a moderating effect (Liang and Huang, 1998). Klein (1998) also supports the view that experience has a significant value when doing online shopping. However, in the Theory of Planned Behaviour, Ajzen (1985) did not mention anything about pre-experience. On the other hand, Shim and Drake (1990) suggested that strong intentions to buy online led from experience from non-store shopping. This statement is also supported by Liang and Huang (1998). Shoppers who have experience in using technology have enough knowledge on how to do online shopping. Weber and Roehl (1999) explained that there might be a direct relationship between previous online shopping experience and online shopping intentions. There is a link between past online shopping experience history and what is searched for online. Computer search engines track what a consumer searches for and shows them related items. These items directly influence the consumers' intentions about what products they want to buy. Therefore, the hypotheses can be developed here that:

H2: Positive attitudes towards online grocery shopping are presumed to be positively related to purchase decision making among ethnic consumers.

H3: There is a positive correlation between consumer attitude to a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase for the ethnic consumer.

Mathew (2015) conducted research in India (this helps to assess Asian consumer online buying behaviour) and discovered some of the changing trends in how Indian consumers do online shopping. There are many reasons why the online shopping market is growing in India. Some of the reasons are listed below:

1. **Easy to find:** Online products are easier to find compared to going to street shops. Search tap services are available which help online consumers to find products easily.
2. **Cheaper product:** Online products tend to be cheaper because of low maintenance costs.
3. **Save time and energy:** Online shopping is much quicker and easier as consumers don't have to go to a physical shop.
4. **Freedom of choice:** Consumers can choose their product from a larger selection of choices.
5. **Freedom of flexibility:** Consumers have alternative options to choose from. If they do not like the products on one website, they can easily look at another.
6. **High satisfaction percentage:** Advancements in technology has led to increased satisfaction amongst consumers.
7. **Buyer protection:** Nowadays online service providers provide assurances to buyers which can help to motivate them to make a purchase. One example of the assurances that companies provide is a money-back guarantee. PayPal, for instance, has this assurance.
8. **Rare products:** Products that may not easily be found in stores can often be found online.
9. **Privacy:** In some instances, customers do not want to show people what they are buying which is easily possible on the internet.
10. **E-business:** E-businesses have become commonplace in India because all the consumer need is an internet connection and a product or service to sell.

(Mathew, 2015).

Mathew (2015) also highlighted some negative sides to online services that restrict consumers.

These are:

1. **Delay:** When a customer does not receive the product, they have bought on the agreed-upon date it can be of great inconvenience. In some cases, the products are needed urgently, and customers could have bought the item from the shop in a quicker time frame.
2. **Inferior product:** the products listed on the website and the store sometimes are different. Visibility of the products is often less on the website when compared to going to the store.

3. **Shipping charge:** Another issue consumer face when buying products online is the delivery charges. Some products are sent by sellers with free shipping, but others are often not.
4. **Delivery problem:** Sometimes products arrive damaged or cannot be sourced for the customer. Sometimes customers can order the multiples of the same product but only receive one.
5. **Shopaholic:** Customers sometimes get addicted to buying too many items and due to the ease of buying items, are hard to stop. As a result, they often buy products that they don't need. Some people start to believe that because they are buying online, they are always saving money which isn't always true.
6. **Scam:** As much as online shopping has grown, the amount of fraud has also increased. As a result of the increase in fraudulent activities, consumers tend to only buy from trusted websites.
7. **Some items are better to buy from real store:** Clothes, shoes, and some fashion items are debatably better to buy from stores because of sizing issues and colour choices.
8. **Return problem:** Sometimes products do not satisfy the consumer. This leads to consumers wanting to send back items. Unfortunately for consumers this often means paying a return fee. Additionally, some sellers make it a requirement to get the products back in the original packaging and often have a very short time to return products.
9. **Warranty issues:** Some products bought online do not cover international warranty. Additionally, some untrustworthy companies make it very hard or even impossible for consumers to fulfil the terms of their warranty.
10. **Miscellaneous trouble:** these include credit card fraud and spyware.

(Mathew, 2015).

Katawetawaraks and Wang (2011) published research on online shoppers' behaviour and highlighted the main reasons that consumers do online shopping. They claim that there is a marketing communication system in place to help a consumer make an online or offline purchasing decision. A customer often is subconsciously persuaded to buy products when they see a promotional offer of a product and products advertisement.

Katawetawaraks and Wang (2011) also added that the consumers' perspectives have an influence on which brand they choose for their products and services. Products that can easily be bought online include software, books, clothing. Some other products are difficult to decide on when shopping online. In those cases, websites play an important role. Retailers of online

services providers pay a lot of attention to the websites that feature and focus their products. If the website is slow or is not safe for customers to browse, or payment systems are not clear, then customers feel uncomfortable to visit those sites and therefore don't make any purchases. Laudon and Traver (2009) indicated that, consumer skills and experience about online shopping is an important factor in making a purchase decision.

3.3.2 Consumer culture and online shopping

Researchers in different research has used culture as a major influencer of consumer buying decision and an important criterion for consumer market segments (Chaudhry and Crick, 2004; Chattaraman and Lennon 2008; Hamlett et al., 2008; Vida et al., 2008; Ayyub, 2015). Because of the economic importance of ethnic groups, cultural entities are important among marketers. The basis on the cultural difference some other aspects includes brands, product design, website design are important factors for consumer cultural adaptation (Appiah, 2004; Ranaweera, 2005; Chen and Barnes, 2007; Constantinides et al., 2010).

Researchers have controversial arguments about online shopping and cultural effects. Johnston and Johal (1999) are the opposing groups (internet is immune to cultural influence but there is no classification scheme) whereas Chan and Tai (2001) are in the supportive group (culture influences online shopping behaviour). Constantinides et al. (2010) indicated that online consumer buying behaviour is affected by website design, cultural atmosphere and emotions. On consumer web experience there are some element stated browsing, searching, findings a product, selecting preferred product. They classified consumer online experience in three categories. These are:

1. **Content category:** Marketing mix factors are important in this category. Making a website nice and attractive is an important tool to attract consumers.
2. **Psychological category:** This is building trust among consumers. Building up trust and privacy can lead to better business for an online retailer. There are some ways showed to build trust and privacy such as: minimizing uncertainty, fraud protection, money guaranteed, data protection policy.
3. **Functional category:** In terms of functionality the web selection needs to be easier for consumers. Some key feature of the web is that it is important to make it easier to browse the products and services.

Website colour, image movement or animations make a difference in consumer web selection preference.

3.4 CONSUMER TRUST AND SATISFACTION IN ONLINE PURCHASING

Zaltman and Moorman (1998) define trust as the belief that one party can rely on the other parties' word or promise. It is also described as the building up of a relationship between two parties. Gefen et al. (2003) defined trust as:

- A set of distinct beliefs consisting of integrity, benevolence, and ability.
- Creating a belief for everyone that mutual trust creates.
- “*willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another*” (Mayer et al., 1995, p. 712).
- “*feelings of confidence and security in the caring response of the other party*” (Rempel et al., 1985, p. 96); and
- A combination of these factors.

Campbell and Walker (2010) and Chen and Barnes (2007) detailed in their research that increasing trust in online environments increases purchasing behaviour. They stated that high levels of consumer trust increase online purchasing intentions and helps to retain online customers. If there is a lack of trust in the businesses selling products, consumers will be far more likely to stop purchasing products online. In economic transactions, different levels of uncertainty arise. According to Pavlou (2003), uncertainty is behavioural and environmental. Pavlou describes behavioural uncertainty as to the lack of seller performance and environmental uncertainty has to do with the medium of exchange or extraneous within the parties.

Shankar et al. (2002) stated that online trust is very important between parties such as customers and other stakeholders including employees, distributors, and suppliers. Therefore:

“Understanding how online trust is created and maintained can lead to improved websites, sales revenues, profitability, and ultimately shareholder value” (Shankar et al., 2002, p. 326).

Urban et al. (2000) demonstrated e-business strategy is about doing business through an electronic medium to redesign, reposition, reshape, and to revise business models for the competitive market to give advantages in the digital market environment. There are two types of trust:

1. Offline trust
2. Online trust

Offline trust is built up by businesses when they are dealing with business offline activities such as direct sales, channel sales, and different communication and transactions. Online trust

is built up through the use of the business' website(s). Consumer trust in online shopping has been defined in many kinds of research. Some of the definitions have summarized in table 3.3.

Table 3:3 Definition Trust

Study	Definition of trust
Barber and Gambetta (1992)	Trust is about building up a positive relationship between business and consumer.
Bianchi and Andrews (2012)	Trust is a positive attitude between business and consumer that allows for a transaction to happen.
Campbell and Walker (2010)	Trust reduces the perceived risk when purchasing online and increases the possibility of repeat purchases.
Chen and Barnes (2007)	Consumers' online trust is built up when they believe the business, they are dealing with has high amounts of integrity, benevolence, and ability.
Gefen et al. (2003)	Trust in an online vendor is the willingness to make oneself vulnerable to actions taken by the trusted party based on the feeling of confidence and assurance.
Mayer et al. (1995)	Trust is the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the action of another party.
Pavlou (2003)	Trust is the subjective assessment of one party that another party will perform a particular transaction according to her confidence and assurance.
Rempel et al. (1985)	Trust is a function of properties of the self with the specific partner and with a specific goal.
Salo and Karjaluoto (2007)	Trust in online environments is defined as the degree of trust consumers feel during online transactions. Online trust is often a psychological acceptance of business. They define trust within the boundaries of external factors (products, service, culture) and internal factors.
Shankar et al. (2002)	Trust in online stores is built up mainly by the effective use of technology.

3.4.1 A constituent element of trust

McKnight and Chervany (1996) examine six elements of trust that affect the online shopping user's behaviour (cited by Salo and Karjaluoto, 2007). These are:

1. Trusting beliefs
2. Trusting intention
3. Trusting behaviour
4. System trust
5. Dispositional trust and
6. Situational decision to trust

McKnight and Chervany (1996) evaluate an increase in trust in a brand happens based on three main categories. Firstly: based on expectancies and beliefs. Secondly: the behaviour of the parties and thirdly, based on affective or cognitive aspects.

1. **Trusting belief:** Salo and Karjaluoto (2007) suggest that ‘trusting belief’ is when a person believes that his/her online service provider is dependable. Trusting belief consists of four elements. These are:
 - Benevolence:** When businesses are ethical in that they aren’t just trying to exploit consumers. Ethical practices by businesses build up trust because consumers have the belief that they aren’t just being exploited
 - Honesty:** Trust can be built up by companies offering assurances and guarantees in products. For instance, if a company offers a warranty on a product it is clear that they believe that their product is of good quality and will last a good amount of time.
 - Competence:** When the consumer believes that the business, they are buying from is reliable and provides a good service and product.
 - Predictability:** If the consumer has had a positive experience with a product or business the business becomes predictable in that it will probably provide a good service again.
2. **Trusting intention:** it is dependent on whether one party is going to trust another. Five components are described by McKnight and Chervany (1996). They include potential negative consequences, feelings of security, dependence, lack of reliance on control, and situation-specific contexts.
3. **Trusting behaviour:** Barber and Gambetta (1992) explain that even after knowing the risks involved with buying some products consumers often still want to trust businesses.
4. **System trust:** System trust is based on structural assurances from businesses and built-up trust by establishing normal procedures when dealing with a business (situational normality) (Salo and Karjaluoto, 2007).
5. **Dispositional trust:** Some people tend to be more trusting than other people are. This can be due to previous life experiences. There are two types of dispositional trust. Trusting in people and trusting in businesses. (Salo and Karjaluoto, 2007).
6. **Situational decision to trust:** This is when consumers decide to trust a business in a specific scenario with specific factors.

Trust builds up through a variety of different factors (figure 3.7). Research has highlighted that word of mouth greatly affects people’s trust in businesses (Wen, 2009; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012). Brand reputation, quality of information, and mostly perceived risk are also important factors in creating a trusted online environment (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Pikkarainen et al., 2004).

Figure 3:7 Factors that influence online trust

Liu et al. (2013) interviewed online customers and found that customers' trust builds up when they see positive reviews from other customers. Better customer reviews on a website lead to a higher reputation amongst customers. As a result, people tend to spend more. This positive review model for increasing sales is far more effective than word of mouth (Liu et al., 2013). Chen and Barnes (2007) classified three characteristics of offline shopping and online shopping. First, there is extensive use of technology in online shopping, but offline shopping doesn't require much of it. Second, the consumer faces uncertainty, the temporal, impersonal character of the online transaction environment. On the other hand, traditional shopping or offline shopping has direct payment system cash/card method. These give some consumer to feel relaxed about their transaction. Third, online shopping is open, unpredictable and has technological infrastructure. Miyazaki and Fernandez (2001) criticised the risk perceived by consumers about online shopping is too high (cited by Browaeys and Price, 2015). Wang et al (2006) found that from a consumer perspective, there is a risk involved in making an online purchase. He also found that consumers demand a high level of privacy when making a transaction. Yuliasri et al. (2011) highlight a few factors that influence consumer online buying behaviour (Cited by Liu et al., 2013). These are the usefulness of online internet shopping, the ease of use, compatibility, privacy, security, self-efficacy, normative beliefs, attitudes, and buying intentions.

Liu et al., (2013) indicated the key factors towards online shoppers' attitudes are on risk perception as well as security perception. They also stated consumer demotivated to buy a

product if they perceive a high-security risk of the website. For instance, viruses, crackers and hackers try to steal private information from the user's computer. The users try to protect their computer by using anti-virus applications. Thus, trust and financial risk perception considered to be a barrier to online shopping.

It is argued that shoppers will weigh their level of trust against their level of perceived risk during an online grocery purchase decision; therefore, to measure trust alone is not sufficient because its influence is relative to, and determine in some part, by that of perceived risk (Bianchi and Andrew, 2012). A consumer who trusts the online shopping retailer will perceive less risk during online grocery shopping. Blomqvist et al. (2015) proved trust happen not only between online shop and shoppers but also between shoppers and the computer system. They also demonstrated greater the level of trust gained from shoppers to the seller to online seller the more likely they will come to the internet shop and have a positive intention to buy. Therefore, the next hypothesis to test trust variables in terms of online grocery shopping intentions.

H4: Ethnic consumers' trust significantly predicts online grocery shopping intentions.

Shankar et al. (2002) clarify:

“In the context of online trust, because of the divergence of interests of some of the stakeholders, the different stakeholder perspectives cannot be easily aligned for economic efficiency of the firm. Building and maintaining Web sites and electronic networks with high levels of trust with different stakeholders may call for a delicate balancing of the interests of these stakeholders” (p.330).

Online trust is built up from a partnership between consumer and business. This relationship changes over time and becomes stronger if the consumer keeps trusting the business. Trust can be built up in both an offline and an online environment.

3.4.2 Trust in online brand

A consumer's trust in online brands influences them to purchase online (Lau and Lee, 1999). Website reputation is one of the factors in whether a consumer trusts an online brand. Two examples of highly trusted online websites are Amazon.co.uk and Ebay.co.uk. Smith (2017) reported that there are 250 million eBay classified user across the globe. PayPal is the best example of an online transaction provider that consumers tend to trust.

Doney et al. (1997) stated that an increase in trust in an online brand is created largely through positive word of mouth. Increasing consumer trust is important for businesses to build up customer loyalty. Increased customer loyalty will likely mean returning customers and a more

profitable business. Garbarino and Johnson (1999) outline that consumer satisfaction only happens occasionally, and that some consumers only purchase online for enjoyment. They did also add that purchase trust is important in building up a relationship with the customer base.

Similarly, Ranaweera and Prabhu (2003) suggest that satisfaction and trust in online brands are related positively. Increased satisfaction and trust increase the loyalty level of consumers. Highly loyal customers are more likely to spread a positive message about the product/business. This will likely increase business. Research has suggested that the price and promotions are antecedents of brand switching behaviour (Bawa and Shoemaker, 1987). Consumers are brand loyal when attitudes and behaviour are favourable (Lyon Ha, 1998).

The researcher took into account more than just attitudes and intentions. The researcher has emphasised the importance of building up ‘trust’ as well as ‘satisfaction’ with online services (Ranaweera et al., 2005; Barber and Gambetta, 1992; Shankar et al., 2002; Gefen et al., 2003; Salo and Karjaluoto, 2007; Wen, 2009; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012). Trust can sometimes bring satisfaction. Online shopping does not include face to face interaction and as such relies on trust. Trust build-up by a situational construct for online behaviour determined by both system dependence and uncertainty about the transaction system. Ranaweera et al. (2005) in their research model highlighted:

“satisfaction as opposed to trust as the focal construct for the following reason. First, the antecedents and outcomes of satisfaction (in the chain of links; website quality → website satisfaction → website loyalty) are supported by solid body of research. The effect of uncertainty associated with online consumer behaviour and the consumer unique reaction to this uncertainty through a set of user characteristics” (p. 55).

On the other hand, Shankar et al. (2002) demonstrated,

“the lack of clear distinctions between the underlying dimensions and antecedents of online trust. Online trust and its relationship with its antecedents and consequences can be viewed from the perspectives of multiple stakeholders such as customers, employees, suppliers, distributors, partners, stockholders and regulators” (p. 328).

Consumers often look at where the product they wish to buy has originated from. They often also look at the products through the lens of their cultural identity when buying a product (Maheswaran, 1994). Images of nationality include:

- National products compared with international products.
- The national image of generic products.
- The national image of the manufacturing company.
- The image created in the mind by the brand name.

The national image of a country's products and the role that stereotypes play is associated with one another (Maheswaran, 1994). Products that are available in the countries of origin of ethnic minorities are often big sellers. Omar et al. (2004) demonstrated ethnic consumer preferred to go to the shop where they believe to find products that fulfil their cultural satisfaction. They believed that quality, taste, and originality of a product can be found on their national products. Therefore, the satisfaction of a product depends on the quality and the products itself. Several studies have highlighted that, trust and satisfaction are the most important antecedents of consumer repurchase intentions in online shopping (Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003; Omar et al., 2004; Wen, 2009; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012). The relationship between trust and satisfaction is well established in these studies. In the context of online grocery shopping, consumer order fruit, vegetables, meat and chicken, trusting that the retailer will provide quality products on stated time. Therefore, it is assumed that consumer who experiences satisfying outcomes from their online grocery shopping will develop a higher level of trust in online grocery shopping. Thus, the hypothesis can be developed:

H5: There is a positive significant relationship between ethnic consumer cultural satisfaction and online grocery shopping.

Online trust depends on website characteristics, user characteristics and some other online options. Building up online trust and the consequences are presented in figure 3.8.

Figure 3:8 Consequences of online trust

Source: Shankar et al. (2002, p.337)

3.4.3 The relation between cross-cultural environments and online trust

Trust in companies varies from culture to culture (Hofstede et al., 1990). Some individuals belonging to collectivist cultures that have a high emphasis on risk avoidance. Wu et al. (2010) underline that while studying online consumer behaviour, a cross-cultural study is important. Cultural influence motivates individuals to act according to his or her beliefs and attitudes.

Liu et al. (2004) emphasise the importance of understanding cross-cultural management for global online purchasing. The research was conducted in Brazil to understand how local culture is reflected on online sites and found that websites who valued local cultural beliefs had received positive outcomes on their business growth (Singh et al., 2006).

To better understand cross-cultural management, Hofstede developed a dimensional approach (Browaeys and Price, 2015). They stated management is affected by different cultural groupings. Hofstede's five-dimensional approaches are:

- 1) **Power distance:** attitudes to the stud entity, the distance between individuals in a hierarchy.
- 2) **Uncertainty avoidance:** the degree of tolerance for uncertainty or instability (e.g., trust and satisfaction).

- 3) **Individuals versus group orientation:** independence and interdependence, loyalty towards oneself and a group.
- 4) **Masculine versus feminine orientation:** the importance of work goals compared with personal goals.
- 5) **Short term versus long term orientation:** fostering virtues related to the past and present or virtues related to the future.

In cross-cultural management, marketers have little knowledge of how to effectively market to multicultural people. Fulfilling customers' needs are the main aims of businesses to make money (Browaeys and Price, 2015). However, they are failing to effectively market to a large portion of the marketplace.

Fujimoto et al. (2007) stated:

“In terms of the cross-cultural online communication context, because the low context of online communication matching the cultural perspective of individualists, they are expected to be more emotionally expressive online, which in turn, is likely to lead to negative emotional responses by collectivist counterparts” (p.15).

3.5 TECHNOLOGY IN ONLINE SHOPPING

Technology is a powerful tool in influencing and changing consumer behaviour. Claveria (2019) demonstrated how technology has an effect on consumer buying behaviour. Claveria highlighted 4 technologies that are already shaping consumer behaviour. These are:

1. The smart device offers consumers convenience and peace of mind: smartphones help a consumer to stay at home and see the world in the device. According to Claveria (2019), 75% of smart device users think that they can perform their daily routine life with safety and comfort. Because of the superfast 4G network consumers are doing more online shopping through a mobile device, and there is no age limit (CIWM, 2017).
2. Wearable devices shape consumer lifestyles and save businesses money. Smart wearable devices help a consumer to track their daily routine life, including physical exercise. Nowadays companies are providing a smart wearable device for their employees to track the progress of given tasks. Online product delivery can now be tracked to inform a consumer about the exact delivery time.
3. Fulfilment solutions drive seamless customer experience: companies are now focusing on a consumer-oriented delivery system. Consumers prefer to receive free delivery and one-day shipping with a tracking system. Claveria (2019) stated that online groceries are not only focusing on increasing the amount of online consumer but are focusing more to improve their experience.

Ad blockers allow a consumer to avoid unwanted ads: add-free online browsing can be a relaxation for the online consumer. According to Claveria (2019), 26% of desktop users use adblockers. Claveria's study also confirmed that 80% of the consumers who are aware of adblockers have used it. Companies are now using different types of marketing techniques to try and increase their potential advertising reach. The internet is an incredibly powerful tool in advertising due to the reach it has. The global audience can be reached with advertisements through all forms of websites. This form of advertising is unique compared to other advertising media for this reason (Spilker-Attig and Brettel, 2010).

Bagga and Bhatt (2013) suggest that marketers are shifting from traditional marketing methods and are now using the internet as the primary medium to advertise products. Internet marketing encompasses four factors.

- I. **Communication strategy:** All companies have an online communication strategy in order to effectively market online. This strategy might involve using social media to increase consumer awareness in their products. Or it could involve using a specific website to advertise on that they know likely consumers of their product use.
"People opt for online shopping due to a variety of utilitarian and hedonic needs out of which discounts and special deals is one of the most important which makes advertising and sales promotions online an integral part of any company's internet marketing strategy" (Liu and Xiao, 2008, p.131).
- II. **Distribution strategy:** This research has discovered that online shopping is far more convenient for consumers than going to a store. As such companies are looking to strengthen their distribution channels by eliminating the middlemen, thereby creating a win-win situation by cutting down middlemen margins and speedy doorstep delivery to its consumer. This is to try and make the online shopping experience even more convenient for consumers.
- III. **Website designing:** Designing a user-friendly website is essential for companies to ensure that people will buy their products online. Websites need to be informative and attractive as well as being different enough from competitors. They also need to be easy to navigate for those consumers who have little technical skill.
- IV. **Payment option and security:** Consumers often have concerns about online privacy and security. As a result, businesses need to be flexible and reassuring to customers and need to build up their trust. Cash on delivery tends to be a preferable choice for some consumers due to convenience and safety. However, websites do not provide this option (Bagga and Bhatt, 2013). Ranaweera et al. (2005) suggest that satisfying customer

needs is the most important step for building up customer loyalty. Therefore, businesses that have convenient and smooth processes in place are more likely to gain repeat customers. Loyalty to businesses online tends to be stronger than offline. Therefore, it is essential for businesses to create early positive impressions on consumers by creating a user-friendly website.

For better marketing strategy a good professional website is very important. Guerrier and Wilson (2011) demonstrated diversity on the website is important that fulfil consumer satisfaction. They suggested the website should focus on multilingual language option for the consumer who is unable to carry on with the English language. Singh et al. (2003) highlighted that Chinese websites have a higher frequency of high context orientation whereas US websites show low context orientation because Chinese people have high context culture comparing to Western people. Fujimoto et al. (2007) demonstrated maintaining cultural diversity is important by the emergence of new technology. For example, websites in different countries design their platform basis on culture-specific content. They mentioned, in Singapore internet freedom is tighter for a knowledge-based economy; alternatively, political and religious community website makes use of the internet to access and publish non-government endorsed views. Similarly, in Singaporean society's conservatism about gay issues reflects itself in a smaller number of websites dealing with alternative sexuality, demonstrating Singaporean culturally specific values. Fujimoto et al. study also suggest, if any western country wants to set-up business in Asian countries should follow the value and mindset of the country for better business performance. Because cultural value dissimilarity expected to have a negative effect on the multi-cultural environment. Therefore, a hypothesis can be developed here that,

H6: Websites that focus on ethnic cultural beliefs are proposed to have a positive impact on the likelihood of an ethnic consumer engaging in online shopping.

3.6 ONLINE GROCERIES SELECTION

With the development of technology, Online Grocery Shopping (OGS) has become popular all over the UK. There are studies on online shoppers that suggest that men tend to do more online shopping than women (Wood, 2011; Harris et al., 2017). However, Freeman (2009) found that women tend to do more online shopping. In the case of groceries, the evidence proves beyond a reasonable doubt that the majority of buyers are female, tend to be younger, and have higher than average income. Anesbury et al. (2016) researched online grocery purchasing and found that selecting whatever grocery brand one desires is very quick and easy. They also found that

consumers are concerned over how long shopping takes, regardless of whether this is online or in a store. The study also found that online shopping avoids travel and parking, physical store navigation, and contending with other shoppers.

Anesbury et al. (2016) published research about the learning process for new online shoppers. They found that most new online shoppers who make even just one purchase will become familiar with the process of online shopping. Additionally, any subsequent purchases will continue to familiarise the new online shopper with the online shopping system. When purchasing online, consumers often have a pre-set brand name that they are looking for. This helps them to minimise product selection and brand selection time. The study, however, finds that some consumers find it difficult to adjust to online shopping. For these consumers, it might take a few shops for them to become comfortable with the process and they may need the help of a friend to help them get started. There are many reasons why a new online shopper may struggle with adjusting to online shopping. One of these reasons is that online products are listed vertically whereas in a store it is usually shelved.

Supermarket shopping requires customers to find the product they are looking for. However, online shopping requires consumers to scroll down pages or type what they want into a search bar to find different kinds of products and brands. This can be difficult for some consumers. Breugelmans et al. (2006) found that whatever online shoppers view on the first page is far more likely to be bought than on any other page. They also found that customers with vast experience of online shopping know how to sort through the products by prices, brands, and capacity very quickly to find the best deals.

Anesbury et al. (2016) also researched how online shoppers interact with online tools and techniques. They found that new online shoppers have very little knowledge about online tools and techniques (such as products display, default settings). Hansen (2008) demonstrated,

“Online buying behaviour should not just be regarded as a matter of ‘subject-channel interaction’ but that also social normative influence could be of high importance to a consumer when considering an online grocery buying” (pp.8-9).

Hansen (2008) also found that consumers are more concerned about damaged items, cold, and frozen items when buying online. This is probably down to the fact that it's far harder to return items or get a refund if they are not up to a good enough standard. When shopping in a store, the customer can also avoid products with damaged packaging, which reduces risk. Liao and Cheung (2001) also found that some customers enjoy visiting shops and bargaining with sellers

before buying products which are not possible online. The researcher has pointed out some important attributes of online grocery shopping, which have been summarised in table 3.4:

Table 3:4 Attributes of online grocery shopping

Prefer to shop online	Prefer to shop in-store	Research
Avoiding the negative aspect of supermarket shopping Opportunity to find a good deal To avoid crowd	Security and privacy of online transaction Unable to judge the quality of the product	Roberts et al., 2003
Reduction of physical efforts Inconvenience	Waiting for delivery, delivery charges	Verhoef and Langerak (2001)
Reducing the time pressure	Inability to use coupons	Harris et al., 2017
Avoiding impulse buying and invasive salespeople	Lack of social contacts	Ramus and Nielsen, 2005

Kempiak and Fox (2002) revealed some facts about online grocery shopping. They stated that online grocery shopping depends on “sensory perception of a product”. While purchasing a product online, a consumer cannot touch or smell, or cannot justify the quality. Kempiak and Fox (2002) made some suggestion about online grocery shopping:

- Technological improvement is very necessary for the best possible graphic display.
- Product delivery time needs to be more accurate.
- An online security system must improve to influence and encourage more consumer to buy online.
- Privacy of a consumer is essential.

The above suggestions are supported by Harris et al. (2017). They have stated that online groceries are not universally supported as a better alternative of store shopping because of factors related to the reliability, cost of the online delivery service and slow delivery. A report came from Mintel (2016) stating more than 33% of the UK consumers have tried to do online grocery shopping but had to abandon it because of the problems associated with it. Harris et al., (2017) pointed out that some consumers had to stop doing online grocery shopping as it does not meet the required expectations. Some shoppers have a pre-set motive (disadvantages, barriers or concern about the options available) about purchasing groceries. This motive leads them to buy online or in-store.

3.6.1 Online grocery shopping in the UK

The CIWM report (2017) highlighted that in the UK there is a £169 billion grocery market, and it has a steady growth. It is forecast that by 2022 the UK grocery market value will grow 15%, giving it a value of £213 billion (IGD, 2018). A Mintel survey discovered that in the UK 30%

of the online grocery shoppers have increased the amount of food shopping and 48% of all shoppers are now doing online grocery shopping (Mintel, 2016). But BBC (2019) reported that the UK online grocery shopping has fallen because of the delayed delivery, delivery charges, and due to order problems. Amazon has launched the Amazon fresh service for its prime members with free one-day delivery or next-day delivery. Ocado has started its delivery services in 2002 in alliance with Waitrose and recently they have gained an alliance with Morrison. Sainsbury's, Tesco, Lidl, and Aldi have offered a wide range of delivery services. IGD (2018) reported that by 2023 the UK food and grocery markets are expected to grow 14.8% by £28.2 billion. Another report came from IGD in 2019 stating the UK is the fastest-growing purchase channel both in terms of value and growth (IGD, 2019). The average value of online food sales has doubled between 2010 and 2016 (£141.9 million in 2016). By 2020 the UK is forecasted to become the second-largest online grocery market worldwide after China (Statista, 2019). The forecast of the UK online grocery shopping and in-store grocery shopping is showed in table 3.5.

Table 3:5 Forecast of the UK Grocery shopping

	2018 value (£bn)	2023 value (£bn)	Change in value (%) 2018-23
Hypermarkets	16.4	16.7	+1.4
Supermarkets	89.1	95.9	+7.7
Convenience	40.1	47.2	+17.6
Discounters	23.1	31.5	+36.7
Online	11.4	17.3	+52.4
Other retailers	10.2	9.9	-3.5
Total	190.3	218.5	+14.8

(Source: IGD, 2018)

Consumer approaches to online grocery shopping are different from conventional shopping. Contemporary consumers are completing online grocery shopping through smartphones and tablets. There are many technological options available to purchase online, but smartphones have taken more aspects of the online grocery shopping experience. Statista (2019) reported that in 2016, 62% of online grocery shoppers purchased through the smartphone.

3.6.2 The reason behind demotivating for online groceries

Huang and Oppewal (2006) conducted an investigation to try and find out the reasons why consumers are demotivated or hesitant to do online grocery shopping. They discovered that delivery charges were the primary reason and grocery shopping is slower than it should be.

Several other studies have also suggested that delivery charges hinder online shopping (Miyazaki and Fernandez, 2001; Hamlett et al, 2008; Ayyub, 2015).

In the UK the most common online groceries market suppliers are Tesco, Asda, Sainsbury, and Waitrose. The largest online grocery supplier in the world is Tesco. Huang and Oppewal (2006) stated about Tesco warehouse model:

“To expand its product range Tesco recently started using a combination of the warehouse model, where deliveries are collected from a central warehouse, and the pick-and-pack model, whereby pickers collect orders from the shelves and the deliveries pass through the individual store’s accounts” (Huang and Oppewal, 2006, p.336).

Tesco often provides free delivery to customers and in some cases, they allocate a delivery slot which helps a consumer to receive the delivery at a convenient time. Huang and Oppewal (2006) developed a model to find out consumer’s shopping preferences. The model focused on four factors which affect consumer online shopping preferences (figure 3.9). These are:

1. The Cost factors
2. The Convenience factors
3. How much enjoyment the product is perceived to bring
4. Any perceived risks.

Figure 3:9 Consumer shopping preferences

Source: Huang and Oppewal (2006, p.337)

3.6.2.1 Cost factors

The cost of a product is a significant consideration to take into account when buying products both online and in stores. Most products have fixed costs. Bell et al. (1998) highlight the fact that travel costs are always a consideration when going to stores unless you live in walking distance. In many cases, online and offline prices are the same, which can lead customers to buy from the store to avoid delivery charges and waiting times. However, travel costs for shopping at stores can include but are not limited to parking charges, congestion charges, unintentional fines, and fuel costs. As a result, some consumers buy online instead, as the overall cost for them may be lower when taking into account all the potential costs. The

individual consumers' cost analysis and convenience analysis are often closely related. For instance, the stress of having to interact with other people as well as road traffic and rainy or hot weather discomfort combined with similar costs online and offline may tip the balance in choosing to shop online (or they may not). Even with the same costs and convenience factors in play, different people will choose differently.

3.6.2.2 Convenience factors

Convenience is also important when taking into account whether to shop online or in a store. Aylott and Mitchell (1998) highlighted a number of inconveniences that affect consumers. One potential inconvenience for consumers is the time that must be taken when buying products and another is the stress around buying products. Online shopping is available anytime from anywhere if an internet connection is available. However, the first time a consumer tries online shopping it will be very inconvenient to get used to online shopping. Additionally, websites usually require you to sign up in order to buy anything as well as enter payment details. This is all inconvenient for first-time buyers and can be confusing. Inexperienced online consumers are likely to have significant problems with finding products early on as they learn to navigate websites. Furthermore, every website is different so it can be difficult for new consumers to get to grips with multiple websites. Verhoef and Langerak (2001) also noted that waiting for deliveries is an inconvenience. In the long term, however, online shopping should be easier and less time-consuming. Supporting evidence is provided by Verhoef and Langerak (2001) and Hansen (2008) who suggest that online shopping significantly minimizes the physical effort required for shopping. As a result, it's unsurprising that consumers who have busy lives tend to online shop (Harris et al, 2017).

3.6.2.3 Enjoyment factors

Alba et al. (1997) point out in their study that some consumers enjoy shopping. However, grocery shopping has traditionally been considered as a burden by many scholars (Genuens et al., 2003; cited by Anesbury et al., 2016). However, some investigations have found that shopping is considered to be enjoyable. For instance, a study by Matthew (2015) found that many consumers enjoy online shopping. A consumer who is under more time pressure prefers to shop online rather than one who has spare time,

3.6.2.4 Risk factors

There is a purchase risk for every single order a consumer completes, whether online or in the store. However, the risk can be increased by a number of factors. Shopping online can be a higher risk especially for newer online shoppers due to payment scams (Harris et al., 2017).

Additionally, there is a higher risk of receiving the wrong product or damaged products. Some perishable grocery items are also a higher purchase risk product. For instance, fish, meat, vegetables, and fruit are items that consumers often like to see/touch/smell themselves before purchasing due to the fact that these products can be incredibly variable in quality and can spoil very quickly. Purchasing greater volumes of products also increases risk.

Harris et al. (2017) stated security of transaction and privacy, perceived complexity, unavailability to judge the products quality, postage and packing, sometimes some good offer to receive from the store, and lack of social contract are the main factor for online grocery shopping. Bianchi and Andrews (2012) indicated this risk (perceived risk) is identified as an inhibitor to online shopping, regardless of advance in technology and the increasing skill and competence of consumers on the internet. Mortimer et al. (2016) demonstrated during the online shopping process for food and groceries, some customers may experience some negative affect such as disappointment, displeasure, anxiety, sadness, frustration or anger over the transaction, which increase their perception of risk resulted reduces their intentions to repurchase from the online grocery retailer. Hence, from an ethnic consumer's perspectives, a hypothesis can be developed here that:

H7: Perceived risk assumed to have a negative impact on ethnic consumer online grocery purchase decision making.

Harris et al. (2017) highlighted the approach-avoidance behaviour theory to discuss online and store grocery shopping. They have discussed how an action occurs in terms of buying decision. The approach-avoidance behaviour theory works as a stimulus for an approach behaviour. This theory was first developed by Gray in 1970. Corr (2013) stated that,

“Approach–avoidance theories aim to describe the major systems that motivate behaviours in reaction to classes of appetitive (rewarding) and aversive (punishing) stimuli, and to explain consistent patterns of individual differences in these behaviours (p.285)”.

Harris et al. (2017) added that the approach-avoidance behaviour theory can be used to measure a shopper typology. Consumers' choice between online and store grocery shopping depends on accepting or rejecting the advantages or disadvantages. Buying online is considered to be an approach to online grocery shopping. Alternatively, because of the negative aspect's consumers avoid buying online groceries. Some advantages and disadvantages have been listed in table 3.6:

Table 3:6 Advantage and disadvantage of online grocery shopping

Advantages	Disadvantages
Convenient It is quick Shop when you want Availability of information Modern technology Trial ease Availability to choose new products	Service concern Delayed delivery Deliveries may not arrive Some product might be missing from the order Some products are hard to find Internet shopping is too slow Fraudulent activities In some cases, it is complicated

3.7 ETHNIC CONSUMER

3.7.1 Ethnic consumer-defined

Kotler et al. (2016) define ethnic consumers as consumers who have different beliefs and attitudes from the majority of consumers and who have also migrated from different countries.

Ethnic consumers are also ethnic minorities as ethnic consumers are a smaller group than the non-ethnic people. Ethnic minorities are a subcultural group within the dominant culture. They have a distinct cultural background, and they are distinguished from dominant culture through externally visible characteristics (physical and cultural). Ethnic identity is defined as the shared identity of a group of people based on a common historical background, ancestry, and knowledge of identifying symbolic elements such as nationality, religious affiliation and language (Jafari et al., 2014).

The ethnic minorities in the UK are primarily made up of younger people. This is due to the reason that ethnic minorities tend to migrate to the UK to find work. According to Burton (1996), a strong ethnic migratory workforce is essential to ensure the growth of the economy. However, the majority of the ethnic consumer studies have been conducted in the USA (Muller et al., 1993; Cui, 2001). This might mean that different results may be found if studies were done in the UK. Ethnic consumers' purchase decisions vary between different age groups and education level (Burton, 1996; Kotler et al., 2016). Figure 3:10 suggests factors that young consumers take into account when making a purchase decision.

Figure 3:10 Important factors for young customers

Cui (2001) suggests that ethnic consumer purchasing depends on media advertising and social media usage. Cui (2001) also suggests that advertising with success to ethnic minorities often depends on advertising differently to people who have different occupations and social roles. Vida et al. (2008) suggest that homogeneity is the largest motivating factor for consumers. People like to fit in with others and buy accordingly.

Some marketing academics working in the USA brought attention to the concept of ‘acculturation’ with the ‘host’ culture. Studies show that the culture of immigrant groups influences the ‘host’ culture and vice versa. This creates a common fused culture (Wallendorf and Reilly, 1983 cited by Hamlett et al., 2008). There is a significant amount of research published to try and understand the acculturation process, such as Penaloza (1994) and Reardon et al. (1997) (cited by Hamlett et al. 2008). These studies implied that acculturation and ethnic identity are not mutually exclusive, and there is no definite endpoint to view the acculturation process from a transitional point of view.

3.7.2 Ethnicity categories in the UK

In the UK there is an increase in ethnic minorities. Black, Asian, and Minority Ethnic (BAME) are counted 35% in London. BAME used to refer to people in the UK who are not white (Cambridge Dictionary, 2020). The UK 2011 census calculated that around 8.1 million people are BAME (13%). A large number of BAME people live in London and the second largest in the West Midlands (Office for National Statistics, 2013). Ethnicity category is presented in table 3.7:

Table 3:7 Ethnicity category in the UK

White	English, Irish, Scottish, Welsh
	Northern Irish
	Gypsy or Irish Traveller
	Polish
Mixed/multiple ethnic groups	White and Black Caribbean
	White and Black African
Asian	Indian/British Indian
	Pakistani/British Pakistani
	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi
	Chinese/British Chinese
	Other Asian
Black/African/Caribbean/Black British	African/African British
	Caribbean/Caribbean British
	Black/Black British
	Other African
Other ethnic groups	Arab/Arab British
	Any other

(Source: Office for National Statistics, 2013)

According to the 2011 census in the UK, BAME population clusters are as highlighted below:

- Indian/British Indian: An estimated 1,412,958 people in the UK are Indian or British Indian ethnic minority, 122,039 of which live in Leicester, which has the UK's largest Indian population by area.
- Pakistani/British Pakistani: The UK had a Pakistani population of 1,123,511 Pakistanis, of which 164,441 live in the city of Birmingham.
- Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi: 447,201 people in the UK have a Bangladeshi ethnic background. The largest Bangladeshi community is in East London, with 128,000 Bangladeshi residents.
- Black African/Black British African: 989,628 black Africans are residents in the UK, the largest group of which live within South East London, which has 135,210 Black African residents.
- Black Caribbean: 594,825 black Caribbean people are resident in the UK. The largest black Caribbean population centre is also in South East London, which has 135,210 black Caribbean residents.

(Office for National Statistics, 2013)

In Britain, ethnic group categories were first introduced in the 1991 Census (Bulmer, 1996 cited by Willis, 2016). In this category, there was no recognition of the Irish people. There were two categories based on skin colour: White and Black. Black people have some additional sub-categories of Caribbean, African, or other. Indian, Pakistani, Bangladeshi and Chinese

nationalities were also included in the ethnic category. There was an 'any other group' category for all other people. Willis (2016) stated that in 1997 the Commission for Racial Equality (CRE) recommended to include Irish as an ethnic minority group and to include the category in the official forms.

This study focuses on studying BAME population (mainly Asian and Black African). According to the definition from Kotler et al. (2016), the BAME population has different beliefs and attitudes compared to White people. BAME people have migrated to the UK from different countries and their beliefs and attitudes are different from the White majority. Additionally, Wade (2007) wrote an article about 'English and Irish' people published in 'The New York Times'. This article stated Britain and Ireland have lots of similarities in genetics and culture. Wade (2007) wrote:

"Britain and Ireland have been inhabited for thousands of years by a single people that have remained in the majority, with only minor additions from later invaders like Celts, Romans, Angles, Saxons, Vikings and Normans" (p.1).

Therefore, Irish and White people have been excluded from this study.

3.7.3 Characteristics of an ethnic consumer

Some characteristics that define ethnic consumers are laid out below:

- Most purchasing is based on family decisions. A collective decision process tends to come up for any kind of decisions.
- They tend to be easy to successfully advertise to. For instance, if the advertisement contains minority actors many ethnic people tend to be greatly influenced.
- Ethnic people hold to set beliefs that tend to pass from generation to generation.
- Ethnic people come from diverse areas and can be from differing generations, ages, languages, locations, and countries of origin.
- Ethnic consumers prioritise their (country's original) language when on websites. This is because some ethnic people are not familiar with the language of the country that they are living in.
- Ethnic consumers tend to abide far more strictly by their perceived cultural values and tend to be far more secretive than non-ethnic people if they go against their cultural values.
- Ethnic people tend to show high levels of brand loyalty when buying products.
- Ethnic consumers tend to be more drawn in than non-ethnic people by promotional offers.

- Ethnic consumers tend to always accept what their religious authorities say. As a result, if a product is against their religion, they will usually not buy it.

(Burton, 1996; Jafari et al., 2014).

Wu (2003) suggests that consumer purchase decisions are strongly influenced by cultural, social, personal, and psychological factors. Armstrong and Kotler (2015) stated that marketers cannot fully control these factors but need to try and consider them if they want to market effectively. Characteristics of ethnic consumers and mainstream consumers are listed in table 3.8.

Table 3:8 Characteristics of ethnic consumer and non-ethnic consumer in terms of online shopping

	Online shopping characteristics	
	Ethnic consumer	Non-Ethnic consumer
Internet acceptance	Internet resistant.	Internet-friendly.
Cultural value	High context cultures (indirectness, politeness, ambiguity, and group membership).	Low context cultures (oral agreements, situational cues, and nonverbal behaviours).
Sales option	Performance has a greater impact on sales.	The price is the main factor in whether a sale takes place.
Brand loyalty	High level of brand loyalty.	Low level of brand loyalty.
Literacy	Less educated.	More educated.
Advertising	Advertising has a greater impact on sale.	The sale depends on the quality and accessibility of products.
Time management	Time is not that important.	Proper time management.
Technology	New to modern technology.	More advanced in the use of modern technology.
Cultural motivation	More ethnocentric.	Less ethnocentric.

Adapted from: (Wu, 2003; Fujimoto et al, 2007; Featherstone, 2007; Hamlet et al, 2008)

3.7.4 Importance of researching ethnic consumer

The ethnic consumer market can no longer be satisfied with a single market. The power and size of the ethnic market have increased and researching and formulating rules for ethnic consumers is very important. Ethnic consumers' society, culture, and behaviour are constantly changing. Phinney (1996) mentioned, "*Ethnic identity is a dynamic construct that changes over time and context and varies across individuals*" (p, 145).

As a result, it is very difficult to separate ethnic consumers for a single market. It is better to research ethnic minorities. For instance, how they behave, how they interact with other people, if they accept technological innovation, how they view society as a whole and do they understand anything about marketing concepts (Nwankwo and Lindridge,1998). Measuring ethnic cultural values is a primary step in investigating ethnic minority markets. Furthermore, it is relevant to explore ethnic subculture in Britain. Khairulla et al. (1996) define the term acculturation as when ethnic-cultural attitudes become diluted and mixed with the culture that they are living in. Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) showed that a person who was born and

raised in the UK is extremely likely to be acculturated with British culture whereas an ethnic migrant is far less likely to be as acculturated. They outline four schemes with differing acculturation levels. These are shown in figure 3.11:

Figure 3:11 Individuals different acculturation

(Source: Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998)

Sills and Desai (1996) and Marcado et al. (2001) highlight several problems when researching ethnic minorities. These are:

1. **Obtaining reliable universal data:** In the UK, a number of immigrants are undocumented. Many more have not registered to vote. The Commission for Racial Equality (CRE) has reported that the situation has improved. However, a higher percentage of ethnic people are not registered to vote when compared with non-ethnic people. When researching ethnic consumers, problems will likely arise because of these issues because people who are in the UK illegally are less likely to want to answer questions honestly when compared to those who are in the UK legally. They are also less likely to answer surveys in general.
2. **Interviewing:** Another problem with researching ethnic minorities is getting the right interviewers to conduct appropriate surveys. The Centre for Disease Control and

Prevention (CDCP) in the USA was researching public services through the use of focus group discussions. They found that single race panels and multicultural panels reacted differently to the same evidence and the same people being surveyed (Rabin, 1994). The research suggested that inventive ideas were most fruitful for targeted versus group audiences. Harris research of employment in Britain among West Indian males found similar result (Watson, 1992; cited by Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). While researching half of the sample taken from the White population and the rest from ethnic minorities results found that White nationals try to secure their job rather than taking any benefit facility while ethnic minorities tend to go to benefit facilities rather than seeking a job.

3. **Language:** The PSI in their fourth national survey found that Asians tend to have more language difficulties than Africans. This made this particular study harder. Similarly, Maxwell (2012) states that Asians are far less likely to integrate with the dominant culture because of the language barrier. Having respondents that don't sufficiently understand the language is a barrier for researchers as it will be much harder to ask understandable questions.
4. **Gender matching:** A problem with researching ethnic minorities is the fact that conservative attitudes amongst some religions and cults mean that women are sometimes not allowed to be interviewed by male interviewers. This can mean that women are just not interviewed at all. Or at the very least, fewer women will be interviewed than men. This, of course, can alter the evidence that is collected in surveys.
5. **Ethnic matching:** Sills and Desai (1996) stated that every ethnic minority group holds to a set of beliefs. If a research question goes against their views or their culture or religious activity, they refuse to answer or might answer 'do not know'. To further complicate matters different subcultures within ethnic minorities have differing views and differing cultures. So, one offensive questions to one subculture might not be offensive to another subcultural group.
6. **Statistical comparison:** If cultural data is not available locally it is very difficult to study ethnic people. Individuals' demographic information, educational qualification, and social groupings may be different, as well as the relative amounts spent on promotion and advertising in different areas (Marcado, 2001).

3.7.5 Ethnic consumer buying behaviour

Browaeyns and Price (2015) explained that

“sub cultural affinity classes can be an ideal target for standardized products because they have a sense of belonging to a common age, gender or income group across different countries. they may also share a common channel of communication, particularly the web and satellite television” (p.234).

Understanding a specific culture and the people who are part of that culture is important in being able to communicate with and fulfil the demands of that specific culture. Kaynak and Jallat (2005) presented that changing geographic and political situations cause consumers behaviour to gradually change (cited by Browaeyns and Price, 2015). Young consumers are increasing in number, which creates another challenge for businesses. In cultural and economic environments, there is uniformity in consumer taste and preference. International market strategy makers now consider it to be of great importance to consider subcultural lifestyles when marketing (Kaynak, 2012).

McKechnie (1992) studied consumer buying behaviour and highlighted studying consumer buying behaviour is an important part of marketing research. This study also showed the importance of studying different interlinked stages of the buying process, which are also described in section 3.1.1. Kotler et al. (2016) mentioned that when there is a high degree of involvement with the product, consumers pass through a cognitive, affective, and behavioural stage. On the other hand, Baker (1983) added six concepts of consumer buying behaviour. These are:

1. Selective perception
2. Hierarchy of needs
3. Hierarchy of effects
4. Post-purchase dissonance
5. Buy tasks and buy phases
6. Characteristics of goods

McKechnie (1992) study figured out consumer demographic characteristics and brand are important for making a buying decision. Joy et al. (1991) showed the relationship between consumer buying behaviour and ethnicity. Their study highlighted the importance of ethnic consumer financial services and engaging with it. Confidence, trust, and customer loyalty were marked as an important factor of ethnic consumer buying behaviour. Their studies mentioned another point that consumers are more service-oriented rather than oriented on all the technological dimensions.

Dey et al. (2019) linked up a study with ethnic consumer acculturation and multicultural market. Their study showed to what extent ethnic consumers retain their ancestor's culture or adjust with the host countries' culture. They used the Uni-directional acculturation concept where ethnic culture is gradually replaced by the host culture. Regarding the Bi-directional acculturation model, the study pointed out that the acculturation process of ethnic minorities has a different pattern, such as Muslims in Western societies slowly adapting to Western cultural food habits. The Muslim mindset believes that vegetarian food (e.g., veg roll, sandwich, onion pasties) is Halal only if they are shown the Halal sign or sticker from the shop. In this case, food purchasing plays an important role in ethnic consumer buying behaviour.

Jamal (2005) described that ethnic consumers and mainstream consumers are different with regards to food purchasing behaviour. The ethnic consumer normally holds their cultural values in their private life, but this is different when engaging with public gatherings. The study also pointed out that ethnic consumers generally prefer to do shopping from a familiar shop.

Pleasant (2015) discussed the Ethnic Consumer Purchase Intent Model (ECPIM). This model offers the opportunity for the researcher to capture the influence of cultural differences and similarities among consumers. Schiffman and Kanuk (2006) agree that culture has a strong impact on the determinants of product purchases. They also added that culture is the summation of beliefs of a particular group in the society whose values and customs direct them to choose their shopping style. Hofstede et al. (1990) demonstrated values and beliefs are formed and shaped significantly by culture. Schiffman and Kanuk (2006) added the fact that the impact of culture is so natural and automatic that its influence on behaviour is usually taken for granted. The ECPIM model discussed the difference between cultural and subcultural groups and their decision-making process. This model focusses on the individual consumer as well as their family contribution to a buying process. Pleasant (2015) stated marketers should identify and categorise ethnic consumer cultures and subcultures in order to make a marketing decision.

3.8 CONCEPT OF ETHNICITY

Stillwell and Ham (2010) define ethnicity as:

“selected cultural and sometimes physical characteristics used to classify people into groups or categories considered to be significantly different from others. In some cases, ethnicity involves merely a loose group identity with little or no cultural traditions in common. On the other hand, some ethnic groups are coherent subcultures with a common place of origin, language, religion, ancestry and cultural tradition” (p.2).

Ethnicity and its meaning have been discussed in many disciplines. This includes the fields of sociology, psychology, anthropology as well as in marketing literature. Ethnicity is defined by a selection of statements. These are:

- A long-shared history, the memory of which is kept alive.
- A common geographic origin.
- A cultural tradition that includes family and social customs, sometimes religiously based.
- A common language.
- Common literature either written or oral.
- A common religion.
- Being a minority and being racially conspicuous.

(Guilherme and John, 2015).

Ethnicity plays an important role in consumer purchase decisions (Burton, 1996; Chaudhury and Crick, 2004; Lopez, 2005). Consumer research conducted in different ethnic subcultures highlights how the strength of ethnic identification significantly impacts the consumption of varied products such as ethnic foods, movies, music, and cultural performances (Chattaraman et al., 2008). Ethnicity indicators depend on whether subjective or objective factors are used. Subjective ethnicity is when consumers believe themselves to be from an ethnic background. It is a reflection of an individual's own psychological identity. Objective ethnicity is based on factors such as how individuals from a particular ethnicity are likely to follow a particular religion, the language that a particular ethnicity tends to speak, and cultural traditions of that particular ethnic group (Burton, 1996). However, Deshpande et al. (1986) stated in their research:

“Any combination of objective-subjective perspectives may not be sufficient to assess ethnicity, for there is no measure of intensity of affiliation with the ethnic group” (p.215).

Jafari et al. (2014) indicated in their article ‘Rethinking religion in the context of ethnicity and well-being’ that religiosity has a very large impact on what choices people make and what lifestyle they choose to lead. Being very religious implies that the individual has a strong connection with their culture and their ethnic background. Percentage of the different religious group in the UK are described in table 3.9.

Table 3:9 Population in the UK in terms of religion

Religion	Number	%
1 No Religion	23,725,080	36.34
2 Christian (all denominations)	33,111,246	50.72
3 Buddhist	263,398	0.40
4 Hindu	1,021,449	1.56
5 Jewish	336,965	0.52
6 Muslim	3,372,966	5.17
7 Sikh	404,891	0.62
8 Any Other Religion	1,028,513	1.58
Missing	2,023,914	3.10
Total	65,288,422	100%

(Source: Office for National Statistics, 2018)

3.8.1 Ethnic identity

Ethnic identity as defined by Phinney (1992):

“Ethnic identity is a person’s knowledge of his or her membership in a social group and the value and emotional significance attached to that membership” (p.144).

Ethnicity and ethnic identity may be differentiated from an identity which is based on cultural rules which individuals think they are bound to follow. Morally ethnic identity is when an individual follows the same rules and acts in a similar way to all the other people who are part of the same ethnicity tie. This means it is often possible to observe an individual’s ethnicity from their morals, their aesthetics, and the technical and legal rules they follow. Additionally, someone from a particular ethnicity may possess certain items that are often used in the culture they are from. From this viewpoint, we might say that an individual’s identity is set by influences from their culture and ethnicity.

Appiah (2004) stated that the strength of ethnically black consumers’ ethnic identity may have a significant effect on their evaluations of websites. Deshpande et al., (1986) indicated that

“Research on Black consumers has focused on mediating effects on consumer’s race or ethnicity, the use of ethnic identification as a means of classification may provide greater discriminating power than more traditionally used measures of ethnicity” (p. 217).

Identity concepts occur in a number of disciplines including sociology, psychology, social anthropology, and political science. Research on ethnic people and ethnicity as a whole has highlighted some problems in Europe for some ethnic groups, usually based on countries’ political situations. On occasions, clashes of ‘identity’ can occur between different ethnic groups, especially around political issues such as immigration (Rex, 1991).

Immigrants who have a strong ethnic identity tend to have strong traditional beliefs in relation to their traditional culture. These culturally influenced beliefs are reflected in everything they do and think and can affect several factors (customs, language, dress, foods, religion, products use, and media use). Individuals with weak ethnic identities tend to abide by traditional cultural values far less. People with a strong ethnic identity tend to live in a way that reflects their indigenous culture's values and attitudes. However, immigrants with a weak ethnic identity tend to have a set of beliefs diluted by the culture that they live in. The research of Appiah study has shown that the stronger the ethnic identity, the more likely an ethnic group is to exercise their traditional values (Appiah, 2004).

Rex (1991) suggests that the political and psychological problem of identity was formulated in France with his study mainly focusing on Muslims of Maghrebian descent. The concept of identity in psychology is important. All human beings have an identity of some kind that always influences their decisions (Rex, 1991).

“identity is formed through the incorporation into the personality of specific objects of identification during childhood and the subsequent mastering of tasks in later life. Thus, at any point, the individual's identity, already a social product, is seen as confronting a further world of social objects, in relation to which it learns to master a range of tasks in accordance with patterns of culture which are learned” (Rex, 1991, p.7).

Therefore, investigating different ethnic identities helps businesses to an effective market strategy towards the ethnic market.

3.8.2 Products ethnicity

Pharr (2005) and Park et al. (2016) define product ethnicity as the stereotypical connection between certain products and the country of origin the product comes from.

Research into the products ethnicity is important because it helps informs marketers about how consumers perceive certain products. Examples of products that have a perceived product ethnicity are curries, Pasta, and Vodka. Consumers tend to associate curry with India, Pasta with Italy, and Vodka with Russia. Research has proven that consumers associate certain products with certain countries (Roth and Romeo, 1992).

The perception of product ethnicity comes from intrinsic and extrinsic cues (Ahmed and D'Astous, 2008; Bagga and Bhatt, 2013). Hong and Wyer (1990) stated in their research that consumer emotion and symbolic interactionism relate to the country the products they are buying from. Furthermore, Beverland and Farrelly (2010) suggest that consumers that buy products that are associated with a particular country are satisfied because it fulfils their urge to discover new cultures and the experiences they have to offer. Cultural satisfaction leads to

consumer authenticity which will, in turn, lead to a more positive association with the products. Therefore, consumers like authentic cultural products as it helps them to connect with the countries they are from. If consumers start to associate positive connotations with a certain product, they are likely to buy the product again.

“congruent product ethnicity, relative to incongruent products ethnicity, positively relates to perceived authenticity” (Park et al., 2016, p. 460).

3.8.3 Ethnic groups and minority groups

Weber (1961) defines ethnic groups as:

“human groups that entertain a subjective belief in their common descent – because of similarities of physical type or a custom or both, or because of memories of colonization or migration – in such a way that this belief is important for the continuation of the no kinship communal relationships” (p. 306).

On the other hand, Essed (1991) uses an umbrella term to define ethnic groups:

“indeed, the substitution of ‘ethnicity’ for ‘race’ as a basis of categorization is accompanied by increasing unwillingness among the dominant group to accept responsibility for the problem of racism” (p.28).

Social scientists define ethnicity in broad strokes. Gordons (1978) suggests that ethnic groups are defined by race, religion, and national origin. Glazer (1983) defines ethnic groups as collectives of people that have common values and interests, have a similar genetic background, and share common history and experiences. Scholars, including Henry Cabot and Werner Sollors (1996), define ethnic groups as groups of people with similar national origins. However, some scholars define ethnic groups by shared physical characteristics rather than shared national origins. To define ethnic identity, ancestry is important (Feagin and Feagin, 2010).

The strength of ethnic identification significantly impacts the consumption of several ethnic and ethnic-inspired apparel, traditional foods, ethnic soft drinks, and ethnic entertainment such as movies, music, and cultural performances (Kim and Arthur, 2003; Xu et al., 2004).

Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) define ethnic minorities as a

“population group that are small in number and, by definition, less than the majority mainstream population” (p. 201).

Whereas Barzilai (2010) defines a minority group as a group of people who are separated from the social majority. The social majority hold the majority of social power. Feagin and Feagin, (2010) stated that minority groups have five characteristics. These are:

1. They tend to suffer from discrimination and subordination.

2. They have physical and/or cultural traits that set them apart and which are sometimes disapproved by the dominant group.
3. They hold to a shared sense of collective identity and common burdens.
4. There are some socially acceptable rules regarding who belongs and who does not have minority status.
5. Individuals from minority groups tend to marry others from the same group.

Different researchers have defined ethnicity and ethnic groups in different styles. Details are shown in table 3.10.

Table 3:10 Ethnicity defined by researchers

Researcher name	Ethnicity definition
Gordons (1978)	“defined ethnic group basis on race, religion and national origin”
Glazer (1983)	“defined ethnic groups where people have common values and interest, the groups are descent, real and mythical, and sharing a common history and experience”
Deshpande et al., (1986)	“Any combination of objective-subjective perspectives may not be sufficient to assess ethnicity, for there is no measure of the intensity of affiliation with the ethnic group”
Essed (1991)	“indeed, the substitution of ‘ethnicity’ for ‘race’ as a basis of categorization is accompanied by increasing unwillingness among the dominant group to accept responsibility for the problem of racism”
Henry Cabot and Werner Sollors (1996)	“Defined ethnic group in the term of national origin”
Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998)	“population group that is small in number and, by definition, less than the majority mainstream population”
Stillwell and Ham (2010)	“some ethnic groups are coherent subcultures with a common place of origin, language, religion, ancestry and cultural tradition”
Guilherme and John (2015)	“Defined, ethnicity is based on shared history, common geographic origin, social customs, common language, common religion, being a minority and being racially conspicuous”
Kotler et al. (2016)	“ethnic consumers are the people who belongs to different beliefs and attitudes from the majority and who are migrated from different countries”

3.9 ETHNIC MARKETING

Cui (2001) defines ethnic marketing as:

“Ethnic marketing is conceived as marketing that treats ethnic minority consumers (or the ethnic community they are a part of) as distinctive markets separate from the macro market and seeks to reach these markets using differentiated marketing mix strategies” (p, 87).

Similarly, Guilherme and John (2015) stated that ethnic marketing is a marketing approach that focuses on the needs and wants of a particular group of consumers by segmenting and targeting that market. Modern marketing strategies often utilise market segmentation to better market to

groups of people rather than advertising the same way to all consumers. Segmenting the market based on ethnicity is one such way of separating the general population into different groups. Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) stated that before the 1990s, ethnic marketing was focused on the market potential of subcultural groups, essentially a few different approaches but mostly uninformed advertising. However, nowadays traditional market segmentation has changed due to increasing diversity and complexities in the marketing system.

Ethnic marketing utilises a new approach that differs from the traditional marketing processes by having a marketing approach of 'thousands of fragments' (4P'S model). This means that there are thousands of marketing approaches each tailored to a different group of people. Guilherme and John (2015) interviewed marketing experts and listed the following ethnic marketing definitions (table 3.11).

Table 3:11 Ethnic marketing definition

Interviewee name	Definition
Christian Grönroos	<i>“Ethnic marketing refers to deliberate consideration by firms of target groups of people that have a cultural context other than that of the mainstream context”.</i>
Rohit Deshpandé	<i>“It’s understanding the similarities and differences of marketing to groups of consumers defined by their ethnicity as compared to marketing to the general population. I see it as the shape of a T. There are commonalities in the way that we market to ethnic groups as well as to the majority of the population. That goes across the T, the horizontal. The vertical is where there are differences. I think that extant research is mainly focused on the differences. This is because that’s how you tend to publish work. It is to say: here’s what we think about everybody, but here is a group of people that behave somewhat differently. Then the theoretical part is the possible explanation for why those differences exist. I think that’s the general domain of ethnic marketing”.</i>
Michel Laroche	<i>“It should encompass marketing activities targeted to specific groups, whether single or in comparison with other groups, that involve the marketing activities directed toward using a specific group of characteristics to develop successful marketing strategies”.</i>
Ikuo Takahashi	<i>“It’s a kind of segmentation marketing, based on ethnicity”.</i>
Kim Fam	<i>“It’s targeting to a small group, an ethnic group of people. For example, in Malaysia, especially in the East Malaysia, there are various ethnic groups, such as the Ibans, Kadazans, Bajaus, Muruts and so on. These are groups of people and when you start marketing to them, you don’t do it as to any ordinary general consumers. They have their own specific values, customs, religious beliefs and such, so you have to take into consideration these characteristics in order to reach them, so they can associate with what you are trying to communicate to them, with their belief”.</i>
Kamal Ghose	<i>“It’s anything that is focused on some ethnic segments, because of the nature of the demand of the segment. It is different to generic marketing. It’s more focused towards the ethnic community, taking their background and their culture into account. It’s both about how ethnic entrepreneurs target their own communities and about how anybody markets to particular segments defined by ethnicity”.</i>
Lisa Penalosa	<i>“On the surface it sounds like a very simple question . . . but it does tend to be quite complicated. I guess, for me, it’s a convention of tailoring marketing campaigns for goods and services – so there’s certainly an aspect of it that’s designed to generate business – and that convention is targeting a group of people that are designated by what we now recognise as ethnicity. Which begs another definition but, for me, I think of it more in cultural terms, and I mean that as much sociologically as geographically in that sense. So, we’re talking about a group of people that typically is identified in terms of – some kind of geography, language, often a belief system, sometimes a form of religion, sometimes not, as well as physical characteristics like colour, race, as well as coming back to the sociological social class. So, there’s a kind of a composite”.</i>

Source: Guilherme and John (2015, pp. 26-27)

Schein (2010) described ethnic marketing under the revealing lens of culture which inputs all its symbolic charges printed over human conduct, customers, consumers, clients, employees, entrepreneurs, governments agents, and intermediaries. Ethnic marketing finds out the hidden predominant values and beliefs supported by an in-depth underlying world located at the heart of our cultural roots (figure 3.12).

Figure 3:12 Cultural Level

Source: Schein (2010)

3.9.1 The needs for ethnic marketing

Guilherme and John (2015) suggest that there are four fundamental issues (table 3.12) that need to be explained in order to understand how the market evolves over-time. These factors are as follows: how businesses relate to the market, where they operate, how consumers behave in the real world, and how marketing theory contributes to organisational performance and social welfare.

Table 3:12 The need for ethnic marketing

Ethnic market function and evolution by	Business relation to the ethnic markets
Production, distribution, and promotion. Segmentation of the market. Intercultural accommodation model. Aggregation/disaggregation function.	Profitable management activities Serving products according to customer’s demand Generating customer loyalty Ethnic sensitive service-products and strategies Creating opportunities for ethnic sensitive supplier
The behaviour of ethnic minority consumer in the real world	Contribution of marketing theory towards organisational performance and social welfare
Consumer socialisation dimension Information and appraisal difficulties Looking for a set of alternatives from the same criteria	Positive economic effects A greater preoccupation on perceived problems

3.9.2 The development of ethnic marketing

Ethnic marketing is an effective approach to categorise the dominant ethnic group and all other ethnic consumers. The categorisation provides opportunities for a market vendor to make an effective marketing strategy. These types of marketing approaches include domestic marketing,

global marketing, or what is sometimes called multicultural marketing. Nowadays, developing and developed nations tend to have refined ethnic marketing strategies. These countries include Australia, Canada, USA, UAE, Saudi Arabia, the UK, and Europe (e.g., Germany, Turkey and Hungary) (Guilherme and John, 2015).

Appiah (2004) suggests that marketers have come to recognise that segmenting the market along demographic lines, such as ethnicity is a better way to sell their products. This realisation may have come from the fact that the number of ethnic minorities is increasing in the UK. Media plans have begun to advertise targeting black and white targeted people. Grouping consumer segmentation is relatively successfully to reach Black people. Table 3.13 demonstrates market segmentation based on geographic, demographic, psychographic, and behavioural factors.

“it may prove even more beneficial to dissect Black audiences even further to reveal differences among subgroups. By focusing mainly on a biological attribute such as race, past research has neglected the potential psychological mechanisms that may more effectively mediate responses to racially targeted media” (Appiah, 2004, p. 313).

Table 3:13 Market segmentation

Market Segmentation			
Geographic	Demographic	Psychographic	Behavioural
Countries	Age	Lifestyle	User status
Nations	Gender		User rates
States	Family	Social class	Benefits sought
Regions	Education		Occasions
Cities	Income	Personality	Loyalty
Neighbourhoods			Attitudes

Being able to separate cultures and subcultural groups from each other is important when developing a marketing strategy both domestically and internationally. Segmenting the market along the lines of commonly shared values, lifestyle, and common life experiences are useful to help separate demographic groups. There is huge market potential in reaching ethnic consumers. Therefore, developing an effective marketing strategy towards ethnic consumers will help businesses to make more money.

3.9.2.1 Factors to develop an ethnic marketing mix

Marketing mix can be defined as *“the retailing mix, that provides a standard vocabulary for the marketing community”* (Kalyanam and McIntyre, 2002, p.5).

The marketing mix is defined as a set of marketing tools that businesses use to try and reach their target market (Kotler et al., 2016). It is also known as the four Ps (Product, Price, Promotion, and Place) and is the foundation of any economic market. Nowadays marketers focus on seven Ps (additional: Process, People, and Physical environment). They also occasionally focus on eight Ps (including Performance) (Kotler et al., 2016). Figure 3.13 describes the different marketing mix.

Figure 3:13 Marketing mix

Source: Kotler et al. (2016)

According to Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) promotion is the most important marketing factor when addressing the ethnic market. Jamal et al. (2012) investigated responses to sales promotion amongst ethnic consumers. They found that some supermarkets offer promotions to ethnic consumers. Stevenson (1991) suggested that in the past ethnic minorities were presented in a stereotypical and unflattering manner when being advertised to (cited by Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). An example of this is stated below:

“Ford Motors (the deliberate erasure of black faces from a version of the company’s advertisement); a Persil TV commercial in which a black and white-spotted dog was seen shaking off its black spots in a bid to demonstrate the effectiveness of the detergent; and the crass ignorance of multiculturalism revealed in the Vauxhall advertisement featuring babies supposedly reflecting the wider British society but, ironically, not a single one of them was black” (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998, p. 210).

Due to the massive market potential ethnic consumers have, marketers need to study ethnic culture to ensure that they can market as effectively as possible. Brumbaugh and Rosa (2009)

highlight that ethnic consumers tend to behave differently to promotional strategies when compared to mainstream consumers. Jamal et al. (2012) repeated that promotion can give different types of worth to marketers. These include money worth, happy family worth, the entertainment worth, negative worth, quality worth, usage worth, net worth, social worth, nutritional worth, negative worth, and educational worth (figure 3.14). Therefore, a hypothesis could be developed here:

H8: Ethnic consumer culture is expected to have a positive correlation with the promotional offer.

According to Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) an effective marketing promotion strategy needs to address the following:

- **Stereotypes:** It is important to consider how the views of different people influence how they respond to advertising. Some adverts reflect society's values and beliefs and that need to be done politely and neutrally to try and not offend anyone.
- **Condescending:** It could be done by avoiding any predictable message indicating any cultural group or target market. The message of advertisement should not be insulting to any group of people whether they are majority or minority.
- **Culture:** Religious and cultural beliefs can often create problems for marketers. It is very important to try and not offend groups of people when advertising. One example of this is when showing a Muslim festival, to make sure that the advert follows the dress code of both men and women for that particular festival. Recent advertising sometimes shows Muslims as terrorists in their advertisements and that creates a negative idea of Muslim people.
- **Intentional and unintentional racism:** Businesses need to be careful to try and not be perceived as racist. If they are perceived as racist, then they will lose many customers.
- **Celebrities:** Using celebrities or other dignitaries that are important in certain subcultures is a very effective way to market to those subcultures. This is because celebrities and other important dignitaries are trusted and respected by certain subcultures. Ethnic celebrities are effective spokespeople to help market campaigns in particular communities.
- **Permission:** Permission from minority group leaders may need to be sought regarding certain controversial products. The more controversial a product or issue, the more support and permission from the group first.

Figure 3:14 Ethnic consumer responses to sales promotions

Source: Jamal et al. (2012, p.5)

Kalyanam and McIntyre (2002) used a term called e-marketing mix which discussed a retailer (e.g., Amazon.com), a manufacturer of consumer electronic products (Hewlett Packard), a manufacturer of networking gear (Cisco Systems Inc.) and an industrial distributor (W.W. Grainger Inc.). They pointed out that, all the companies have business websites (URL) and they included in their website company advertising, product packaging, company letterhead, and the bottom line is a business card. Some companies provide personalised account facilities where customers can create and log in to their account to view transaction or to place a new order. However, customers first think about privacy and security before personalising any account.

3.10 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The aim here is to find the factors that influence online grocery purchasing behaviour and to discuss it through the use of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) will also be discussed in relation to consumer online purchasing decisions.

3.10.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The TAM was proposed by Davis (1986) in his doctoral thesis titled “A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems: theory and results” submitted to the Massachusetts Institute of Technology. Bhattacharjee (2001) first used the TAM to help analyse internet banking. The TAM has been used in this study to investigate consumer

acceptance of technology (why consumers accept or reject certain technology) (Davis, 1989). There have been a few modifications added to TAM overtime. The extended TAM for online shopping scrutinises the influence of PU, PEOU attitudes, and variable factors of online shopping behaviour (Bauerová and Klepek, 2018). The extended model of TAM shows attitudes are a very strong direct predictor of online shopping acceptance. Ajzen (1985) detailed that an individual's favourable or unfavourable behaviour measured by attitudes.

Abbasi et al. (2011) indicated that the usage of technology varies on different cultural context. They described that TAM has some weakness in-terms of multicultural groups. Their study stated that there is very little variation in the usage of technology in Western countries, including Japan. However, the lack of usage was found in people from non-Western countries. Fujimoto et al. (2007) explained that in the collectivist cultural context, especially people from South Asian backgrounds, are more resistant to internet uses. China uses a very strong strategy against internet fearing that unregulated access by its citizens to non-official news sites would jeopardize the country's stability (hacking, information privacy, rumour). Therefore, a hypothesis could be developed that:

H9: Ethnic consumers are expected to have difficulties in the ability to adapt with technology to do online shopping.

The TAM proposes that a person's reaction to technology depends on two beliefs (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000):

1. Perceived usefulness
2. Perceived ease of use

Pikkarainen et al. (2004) introduced an extended version of the TAM for use in online buying behaviour. It outlines six factors. These are:

1. Perceived usefulness
2. Perceived ease of use
3. Perceived enjoyment
4. Information on online services
5. Security and privacy
6. The quality of the internet connection

They used their model in a bank survey in Finland. Perceived usefulness and how much information was provided were the main reasons why people used online banking. Bauerová and Klepek (2018) made an elaboration of TAM based on Davis (1989) in terms of Online grocery shopping shown in diagram 3.15:

Figure 3:15 Elaboration of Technology Acceptance Model

Source: (Bauerová and Klepek, 2018; p.740)

Yiu et al. (2007) through further innovation added two further factors to the TAM. These factors are personal innovativeness and perceived risk. They claimed that perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived risk, and personal innovativeness have a direct relationship with choosing whether to do internet banking. They focused on the risk of using ATM's (Automated Teller Machine), the risk of phone banking, and difficulties with using traditional branches as causes for customers to use internet banking. However, the ability to use banking facilities anywhere at any time as well as easy and quick money transfers, bill payment, and time saved during the transaction are the most common reasons people use online banking services. This theory is applied to online grocery shopping as well as shown in figure 3.16.

3.10.1.1 Perceived Usefulness (PU)

Celik (2016) defines perceived usefulness as:

“PU is the degree to which individuals believe that using a technology will increase their task performance” (p.282).

Perceived usefulness has a strong relationship with the online environment (Davis et al., 1989). Online grocery shopping saves time. Lockett and Littler's (1997) proved that in the UK the most attractive factor for online services is the availability of said services at all times (Cited by Marakarkandy et al., 2017). PU helps to show an individual's evaluation of technological performance (i.e., behavioural or financial, the efficiency of the internet facilities, effectiveness, productivity), using the website for grocery shopping makes it easier to do shopping. Online grocery shopping requires the usage of technology. In the UK availability to use online services is higher than in any other country (Clark et al., 2015). However, for consumers with the background of an ethnic country, these availabilities are very limited because of internet availability and technological facilities.

3.10.1.2 Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)

Davis (1989) defined perceived ease of use as the degree that a person believes that internet shopping adoption and using technology will be free of effort without any obstacle (Davis et al., 1989). Celik (2016) stated that knowing about using technology helps to do better online grocery shopping.

Perceived ease of use is not as strong of a predictor compared to PU in relation to online shopping acceptance (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). Individual attitudes are affected by PEOU. As long as an individual uses any technology, its positive effects will influence users to use the technology more and the negative effects will motivate individuals not to use it again. Fujimoto et al. (2007) demonstrated,

“In terms of the cross-cultural online communication context, because the low-context of online communication matching the cultural perspectives of individualist, they are expected to be more emotionally expressive online, which in turn, is likely to lead to negative emotional responses by collectivist counterparts (p. 15)”.

Abbasi et al. (2011) stated internet usages amongst those of South-Asian background are less than Western countries. The Pew research centre (2020) reported that in India 32% of internet users use a smartphone and 32% do not. Another 35% have a mobile phone but they do not have a smartphone. The Office for National Statistics (2019) described that 19% of the Asian in the UK uses the internet for selling or buying goods whereas this usage is 26% and 25% amongst Black/Mixed and the White population respectively.

Dennis et al. (2009) criticise the TAM model, claiming that it did not focus enough on elements of e-consumer behaviour. These include social factors (Theory of Reasoned Action), situational factors, and consumer traits. Perea y Monsuwé et al. (2004) mentioned four factors:

1. **Consumer traits:** Consumer traits include consumers gender, age, education, and income. In shopping environments, education is the most important factor. People who have been educated to a higher level are likely to engage more with information that is presented and as such will likely have a greater capacity for decision making. Individuals who are less educated are generally worse at processing information and making good decisions (Dennis et al., 2009). Another trait discovered is that older consumers are less likely to search for alternative information compared to younger consumers (Moskovitch, 1982).
2. **Situational factors:** Online shopping behaviour often relies on perceptions of convenience. Kim et al. study suggest that convenience is the main attraction for e-

satisfaction (Kim et al., 2009). Individuals who have more experience with internet usage are more likely to research the products they are interested in buying and are more likely to make repeat purchase (Evans et al., 2001).

3. **Product characteristics:** Nowadays, products need to not only be tangible but also need to create a sense of excitement. Dennis et al. (2009) suggest that consumer interaction with online service providers brings enjoyment.
4. **Trust:** When a consumer starts to trust a company and/or a product then they make repeat purchases with less hesitation. This is because the company/product has proven themselves to be reliable (Salo and Karjaluoto, 2007).

3.10.2 Theory of Planned Behaviour

In 1985 Icek Ajzen first proposed his 'Theory of Planned Behaviour' in his article "From intention to actions: A Theory of Planned Behaviour" (TPB). Blomqvist et al. (2015) define the Theory of Planned Behaviour as a theory that explains the influences and mechanisms behind deliberately performed actions. It is an extension of the theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). Ajzen (1985) states that TPB is a very useful way to learn about human actions and suggests that individuals have enough financial resources to spend on different places. When purchasing online services or online shopping, consumers tend to try to look for alternatives to ensure that they receive the best value for the product they want to buy. Consumer intention to perform a certain behaviour is influenced by the normative beliefs held by the consumer (Hansen, 2008). Hansen (2008) added that Perceived Behavioural Control (PBC) is a determinant of behavioural intention. TPB is a well-suited theory to investigate ethnic consumer online grocery shopping behaviour for a number of reasons.

First, ethnic consumers may have some perceived obstacles and difficulties while doing online grocery shopping such as disappointment, displeasure, anxiety, sadness, frustration or anger over the transaction, language accessibility and finding the right products. PBC should be taken into consideration when studying consumer online shopping behaviour because online shopping requires searching for a product on a website. This can be done through skills, opportunities, resources, and experience.

Second, ethnic consumers may perceive both difficulties and risk when considering online grocery shopping such as the security of online payment and confidentiality, cultural and products quality. It is believed that consumers use their cognitive resources to develop beliefs towards related characteristics of online shopping. Consumers seek for normative guidance to overcome the perceived risk associated with OGS.

Ajzen (1985) defined TPB suggests three behaviours (figure 3.16). These are:

1. Attitudes
2. Subjective norms
3. Perceived behavioural control

Figure 3:16 Theory of Planned Behaviour

Source: Ajzen (1985)

3.10.2.1 Attitudes

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) suggest that attitudes can tell us about a person's actions or behaviour in relation to a product. However, the attitudes develop in a different format of a person. Attitudes develop from a cognitive belief that is stored in explicit memories. Blomqvist et al. (2015) highlight the two aspects that consumers have pre-conceived ideas about (products and services).

“Different brand attributes such as package design of the product, advertisements in print and digital form and what manufacturer it is, connects to the symbolic and social representations of the product or service, this refers to the external stimuli that the consumer is exposed to” (Blomqvist et al., 2015: p.14).

Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) suggest that a person's attitude shows whether this person is positive or negative about a specific thing. If a person shows positive attitudes it means that it is favourable to the people and negative means unfavourable. Some beliefs come from individual direct experience and some from other people. Some of the beliefs of an individual form an attitude. Hansen (2008) reported that personal values affect consumer attitudes towards online grocery shopping. Ethnic consumer online grocery shopping is bounded by their culture. What food consumers normally buy does not only include their nutritional demand, but that food represents their cultural values. Ethnic consumer online grocery shopping is based on traditional values which may not be changed overnight. Hence, ethnic consumer attitudes towards online grocery shopping are the most important predictor for online grocery buying intentions. Hansen's (2008) study added perceived difficulties effects on consumer online grocery shopping.

“The result suggests that online buying behaviour should not just be regarded as a matter of ‘subject-channel interaction’ but that also social normative influence could be high importance to a consumer when considering online grocery buying” (Hansen, 2008: p.135-136).

3.10.2.2 Subjective norms

Social norms are actions that are considered the normal behaviour of a select group of people. Subjective norms are based on normative beliefs. Normative beliefs determine whether a person should or should not perform behaviour. Normative beliefs could be descriptive (normal or common behaviour in a certain situation) or injunctive (beliefs of other references) norms. Subjective norms are the beliefs about what others will think about the behaviour of the individual. Several studies focused on the risk and trust issues of online shopping. The ethnic consumer generally believes that traditional shopping is risk-free compared to online grocery shopping (Maxwell, 2012). Kim and Arthur (2003) mentioned that perceived risk is higher in online shopping because the consumer cannot taste, touch, or smell the grocery products. Moreover, the security of online payment and confidentiality is categorised as perceived risk. Therefore, ethnic consumers build up their beliefs about online risk and trust not only directly from perceptions but also their normative beliefs.

3.10.2.3 Perceived behavioural control

Perceived behavioural control was added into the Theory of Reasoned Action model. Perceived behavioural control is studied to find the actual control of a person in a certain situation. Blomqvist et al. (2015) suggest that perceived behavioural control depends on some external or internal factors. Thus, the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) was developed to discuss how consumers behave during a certain period (Fishbein, 1980).

“the theory of reasoned action asserts that attitude toward buying and subjective norm are the antecedents of perform behaviour” (Lyong Ha, 1998: p.53).

There are two important propositions for TRA offered by Lutz (1991):

First: In order to judge purchase behaviour, it is also important to measure attitudes towards the performance of the acting behaviour (attitudes towards the performance). A person’s attitudes towards buying a luxury car might be favourable but the person may not buy the car. Online grocery shopping requires some resources (e.g., internet connection, computer or smartphone, online payment facilities). An ethnic consumer may have the intention to buy online groceries, but they cannot buy these if there is a lack of facilities.

Second: This is simply the attitude towards the behaviour. There is a behaviour called subjective norm, which influences personal behaviour. In some situations, people’s behaviour

cannot be controlled by themselves, but other factors influence their behavioural performance. Consumers' past experience helps them to have a better online grocery shopping experience.

Lyong Ha (1998) suggests that TRA is different from the traditional attitude's theory (mental and emotional entity by a person). He also added that consumer attitudes towards the behaviour, subjective norms and purchase behaviour are known as 'unit brand loyalty'. Berkowitz et al. (1978) said that unit brand loyalty is put into practice when a purchase occurs. Online transaction provider PayPal has created such a sense of loyalty to the customers that everyone feels free to do any transactions through it.

3.11 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Jabareen (2009) defines

“conceptual framework as a network, or “a plane,” of interlinked concepts that together provide a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon or phenomena” (p.3).

Conceptual frameworks are developed in order to help understand the research objectives. Conceptual frameworks elaborate on the outline of the study graphically and through the narrative form.

The aim of this study is to discover and analyse ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour by analysing online shopping behaviour. Many researchers suggest that social, cultural, personal, and psychological factors strongly affect the consumer online buying process (figure 3.3 and table 3.1). Consumers have to pass several psychological and physical steps in order to make a purchase decision (figure 3.4). There are some factors which affect a consumer to make the decision and to do repeat purchase. Trust and security of online shopping are the key indicators in deciding whether to make online purchases (figure 3.8). Perceived risk and perceived ease of use are highlighted through the Technology Acceptance Model (figure 3.15). This study has developed a conceptual framework from the factors found in the literature review in relation to ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. These factors are listed in figure 3.17 and proposed hypotheses linked shown.

Figure 3:17 Conceptual framework

List of hypotheses

H1a: There is a significant difference between the male and female in the factor influencing for online grocery shopping.

H1b: There is a significant difference between the age group of people and factors influencing for online grocery shopping.

H1c: Those with a higher level of education will have a higher online buying intention than those with a lower level of education.

H2: Positive attitudes towards online grocery shopping are presumed to be positively related to purchase decision making among ethnic consumers.

H3: There is a positive correlation between consumer attitude to a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase for the ethnic consumer.

H4: Ethnic consumers’ trust significantly predicts online grocery shopping intentions.

H5: There is a positive significant relationship between ethnic consumer cultural satisfaction and online grocery shopping.

H6: Websites that focus on ethnic cultural beliefs are proposed to have a positive impact on the likelihood of an ethnic consumer engaging in online shopping.

H7: Perceived risk assumed to have a negative impact on ethnic consumer online grocery purchase decision making.

H8: Ethnic consumer culture is expected to have a positive correlation with the promotional offer.

H9: Ethnic consumers are expected to have difficulties in the ability to adapt with technology to do online shopping.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter aims to provide information about how the research will be undertaken. There are different methods that can be utilised when conducting research. The best methods and strategies for conducting this particular research have been outlined in this chapter. All the techniques and tools used throughout the research are highlighted in this chapter.

4.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHIES

Bryman and Bell (2015) define:

“Research philosophy is a cluster of beliefs and dictates which for scientists is a particular discipline influence what should be studied, how research should be done, and how results should be interpreted” (Bryman and Bell, 2015, p.24).

Burrell and Morgan’s (1979) stated that there are four paradigms to understand the epistemological and ontological foundations of business research and they also suggested that each paradigm could be either subjective (organisation is considered to be a constructed product, where an individual gets to socialise and where they are directly involved with the activities) or objectivist (where individuals can see the real view of the structure of the organisation). Kuhn defined scientific paradigms as universally recognised scientific achievements that, for a time, provide model problems and solutions for a community of practitioners (Kuhn, 2012). Kuhn highlighted a few points that need to be addressed in order to conduct research:

- The background of the research.
- The way of asking the questions to the respondents and probing the answer relating to the area.
- The way of organising the research questions.
- The judgement of theoretical prediction within the discipline.
- The relation between scientific investigation and the result.
- Nature of doing the experiment and related methods.

To decide it is necessary to do an investigation deeply with all the relevant information. Once the information has been gathered it needs to be analysed for judgement for a good solution. Research helps to analyse all the information in the right way to make the right decision. In this research, the researcher has planned to follow the research onion from Saunders et al. (2012) (figure: 4.1). This onion creates a series of stages to understand different methods of data collection and demonstrate different steps of the methodological study.

Figure 4:1 Research Onion

Source: Saunders et al. (2012)

There are a variety of paradigms that exist in social sciences, including positivism, post-positivism, conflict paradigms, social Darwinism, symbolic interactionism and feminist paradigm. Each paradigm indicates a different way of social life about the way of social reality.

Saunders et al. (2012) classify research philosophy into four categories: positivism, pragmatism, interpretivism and realism. Positivism is an epistemological position which applies natural science to reality with scientific proof (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Positivism tells us about valid knowledge with scientific evidence. In positivism, research undertaken is a value freeway and researchers are independent to do work e.g., collecting data and building up a hypothesis to analyse the data. Researchers use the highly structured methodology in positivism philosophy to quantify something with statistical analysis (Saunders et al, 2012). Second, Bryman and Bell (2015) identify pragmatism as a cluster of believes and dictates which, for scientists in a particular discipline, influence what should be studied, how research should be done, and how results should be interpreted. Saunders et al. (2016) define pragmatism as an instrument or tool to solve research problems. It describes the nature of a concept, its meaning, beliefs, and knowledge about a field. It tells a researcher which research philosophy to use from ontology, epistemology, and axiology to solve a research problem. Interpretivist or pragmatist philosophy tells whether to work with epistemology, ontology, or axiology. In pragmatism, the research question is the most important determinate of research philosophy. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), pragmatism can be combined with interpretivist positions within

the scope of single research depending on the nature of the research questions. Unlike positivist and interpretivist philosophies, the pragmatist research philosophy can integrate more than one research approach and research strategy within the same study (Saunders et al., 2012). The third philosophical approach, interpretivism, that opposes the positivism of natural science (Saunders et al., 2012). In qualitative research, interpretivism is important because it integrates human interest into a study. Interpretivism is different from natural science because it only interpreted the world.

Finally, realism is related to scientific enquiry. It is related to the essence or existence of an object in the real world (Bryman and Bell, 2015). There are two types of realism exist described by Saunders et al. (2012). The debate between direct realism and critical realism is that direct realism believes we cannot judge the world on illusion. If we must decide on something, we have to observe an object closely from different angles. As a researcher, it is better to understand what is going on in the real world. Bhaskar (1989) said that we might understand the real world if we know the structure (cited by Saunders et al., 2012). Bhaskar also added that we can identify reality through practical and theoretical knowledge.

4.1.1 Ontology

Ontology is a philosophical term that informs research about what entities exist and how they are grouped together (Saunders et al., 2012). Within ontology, the researcher knows how reality is, how the world operates, and commitments held to a particular view. In business management research, there are two ontologies:

- Objectivism
- Subjectivism

Objectivism tells a researcher how social entities exist independently of social actors. Objectivism states about management systems and judges that all management systems have the same types of procedures. Its nature is to describe different aspects of the management. Subjectivism is about understanding the meanings that individuals attach to social phenomena. Subjective ontology suggests that reality is an outcome of the human mind and human actions.

“Subjectivism asserts that social phenomena are created from perceptions and consequence actions of social actors. As social interactions between actors are a continual process, social phenomena are in a constant state of revision. This means it is necessary to study the details of a situation in order to understand what is happening or even the reality occurring behind what is happening” (Saunders et al, 2012, p.142).

4.1.2 Epistemology

Bryman and Bell (2015) define:

“An epistemological issue concerns the question of what is (or should be) regarded as acceptable knowledge in a discipline. A particularly central issue in this context is the question of whether or not the social world can and should be studied according to the same principles, procedures, and ethos as the natural sciences” (p.15).

Epistemology concerns what constitutes as acceptable knowledge in a particular field of study. In epistemology, researchers rely on the object that they’re perceiving to be true. Researcher design research questions based on epistemological assumptions about reality (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Therefore, methodological assumptions provide a framework to investigate answers to philosophical questions to acquire and share new knowledge in the field. Epistemology provides the philosophical reasoning underpinning the gathering of relevant and reliable knowledge (Saunders et al., 2102). Comparison of four research philosophies described in figure 4.2:

Figure 4:2 Comparison of four research philosophies

	Positivism	Realism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
Ontology: the researcher's view of the nature of reality or being	External, objective and independent of social actors	Is objective. Exists independently of human thoughts and beliefs or knowledge of their existence (realist), but is interpreted through social conditioning (critical realist)	Socially constructed, subjective, may change, multiple	External, multiple, view chosen to best enable answering of research question
Epistemology: the researcher's view regarding what constitutes acceptable knowledge	Only observable phenomena can provide credible data, facts. Focus on causality and law like generalisations, reducing phenomena to simplest elements	Observable phenomena provide credible data, facts. Insufficient data means inaccuracies in sensations (direct realism). Alternatively, phenomena create sensations which are open to misinterpretation (critical realism). Focus on explaining within a context or contexts	Subjective meanings and social phenomena. Focus upon the details of situation, a reality behind these details, subjective meanings motivating actions	Either or both observable phenomena and subjective meanings can provide acceptable knowledge dependent upon the research question. Focus on practical applied research, integrating different perspectives to help interpret the data
Axiology: the researcher's view of the role of values in research	Research is undertaken in a value-free way, the researcher is independent of the data and maintains an objective stance	Research is value laden; the researcher is biased by world views, cultural experiences and upbringing. These will impact on the research	Research is value bound, the researcher is part of what is being researched, cannot be separated and so will be subjective	Values play a large role in interpreting results, the researcher adopting both objective and subjective points of view
Data collection techniques most often used	Highly structured, large samples, measurement, quantitative, but can use qualitative	Methods chosen must fit the subject matter, quantitative or qualitative	Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative	Mixed or multiple method designs, quantitative and qualitative

Source: Saunders et al (2012, p.140)

Selected philosophy for this research

This study is based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour of groceries. Online shoppers buying intentions studied in order to have a better understanding of how each ethnic online shopper behave toward online grocery shopping. McKechnie (1992) found that a shopper's behaviour has social-physiological origins so each person may have different social influences as per the cultural difference. Triandis (2004) highlighted Asian culture is different from western culture and Asian people have collectivist culture comparing to Western people. Therefore, the study requires an approach to study ethnic consumer buying behaviour in a specific context. The pragmatism research approach is centred around exploring human behaviour (how people behave in certain circumstances) whereas interpretivism focuses on

human interest in the research area. Interpretivist philosophy is sometimes called a critique of positivism in social sciences (Saunders et al., 2012). Interpretivist philosophy thinks that through language and other shared interests' reality can be focused (Myers, 2008). Interpretivism is sometimes linked with idealism. Interpretivism discusses socially construct phenomena, subjective meanings, and may use multiple methods. If researchers think epistemologically, idealism is to understand people's mindsets. The way human ideas, beliefs, and values are shaped is discussed in idealism. Epistemology describes subjective meanings and social phenomena in detail of a situation.

Pragmatism is a research philosophy based on the epistemology that there is no single way of learning but many different ways of understanding because there are multiple realities (Saunders et al., 2012). Pragmatism is a deconstructive paradigm that advocates the use of mixed research methods and "*sidesteps the contentious issues of truth and reality*" (Yvonne Feilzer 2009, p.8). Tashakkori & Teddlie (2003) stated that pragmatism, "*focuses on 'what worked' as the truth regarding the research questions under investigation*" (p.713). Ethnic consumer online buying behaviour in a specific field needs to investigate. The research question is very important to measure online buying behaviour. Therefore, this study will follow the pragmatism approach. Through this integration, the researcher hopes to gain a better understanding of the study from the views of people who lived the experiences and from scientific modelling and testing of facts and figures. Table 4.1 interpreted about the difference between pragmatism and interpretivism.

Table 4:1 Difference between pragmatism and interpretivism

Pragmatism		Interpretivism	
Deductive/inductive	Develop ideas by analysing data	Inductive	Takes a problem-solving approach
Objective or subjective	Data present subjective meaning	Subjective	Assume a situated embodied producer of knowledge
Value-free/biased	Logic of discovery	Biased	Assumes a search for multiple perspectives
Qualitative and/or quantitative	Elaborate concepts rooted in qualitative and quantitative data	Qualitative	Aims to study people's actions to solve emergent problems

Adapted from (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003; Yvonne Feilzer, 2009 and Saunders et al., 2012)

4.2 RESEARCH APPROACHES

The research approach is the method a researcher is going to select a theory, either inductive or deductive (Saunders et al., 2012).

4.2.1 Inductive Approach

An inductive approach is an approach a researcher generates theory from data. The main purpose of this approach is to find what is going on in the natural world. Inductive approaches mainly focus on exploring new phenomena and on trying to analyse phenomena that have been previously researched (Saunders et al, 2012). Maylor et al. (2017) indicated that *“Researcher often rely on induction when they are researching an area without theory to guide the development of hypotheses (and hence which data to collect)”* (p.152).

4.2.2 Deductive approach

Maylor et al. (2017) showed: *“The purpose of deduction is to provide a structured process for testing a general rule or theory using data about a specific instance”* (p.150).

Deductive research is mainly quantitative but sometimes can be qualitative. Maylor et al. (2017) highlighted that in deductive research, hypothesis testing is done by the following criteria:

1. Selecting a method such as an experiment, survey, or secondary source of data analysis.
2. Transformation of collecting data in a numerical form.
3. Statistical analysis tools to analyse the quantitative data.
4. Testing the hypothesis basis in order to accept or reject the scenario.
5. Find out how the result supports the theory or conceptual framework.
6. Presenting the result in number, diagram, or chart.

Saunders et al. (2012) suggested that the main characteristic of the deductive approach is a generalisation. They used a scientific sample size to statistically analyse human social behaviour. The difference between inductive and deductive approach are listed in table 4.2:

Table 4:2 Difference between the inductive and deductive approach

Inductive	Deductive
Gaining an understanding of the meaning	Scientific principles
Data mainly qualitative	Data mainly based on quantitative
Base on ethnography or interpretivism	Positivism philosophy
A researcher is a part of the research process	A researcher is independent of what is being researched
Research-based on meaning	Based on measure
Mainly interview, focus group discussion observation	Methods used are normally: experiments, minimising bias, but limiting the possibilities of discovery

Selected Approaches for this research

It is necessary to validate the results of the research. The deductive approach can help to quantify the data accurately and can clarify the research concept. Inductive approaches are mainly used to help understand phenomena, whereas the deductive approach does scientific validation of the data. Thus, this study is guided by the deductive approach. The deductive approach in this research may help the researcher to find the result with scientific validation.

4.3 RESEARCH STRATEGY

Research strategies are the third layer of Saunders's research onion. Saunders et al. (2012) defined research strategies through research design. Research design is a general plan where a researcher determines how they are going to answer research questions. Research questions may be descriptive, descriptive and explanatory, or purely an explanatory answer. Research design is a blueprint for the research.

Saunders et al. (2012) in their book 'Business Research Methods' highlighted seven types of business research strategies. These are:

- Experiment
- Survey
- Case study
- Action research
- Grounded theory
- Ethnography
- Archival research

Table 4.3 discusses the comparison of different research strategies and approaches

Table 4:3 Different research strategies and approaches

Research Strategy	Approaches	Data collection	Philosophies
Experiment	Inductive or deductive	Qualitative or quantitative	Positivist or interpretivist
Survey	Deductive	Quantitative	Positivist/Pragmatism
Case study	Inductive or deductive	Qualitative or quantitative	Positivist or interpretivist
Action research	Inductive	Qualitative	Epistemology, interpretivism
Grounded theory	Inductive	Qualitative	Interpretivism
Ethnography	Inductive	Qualitative	Interpretivism
Archival research	Inductive	Qualitative	Interpretivism

This research is based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. Ethnic consumers are a subgroup of consumers. The researcher has planned to select a specific community to collect data from. From the above description, the researcher can see that survey research can collect data from a group of people (BAME group). Experiments happen for a longer period and case studies are based on a selection of people from a group. In case studies, multiple sources of data are used. For this research, the individual answers to the questionnaire are an appropriate clarification for online grocery shopping behaviour and there need not be a verification process. The reason this research can use individual answers is that the research is based on different individuals' experiences.

Additionally, in grounded theory, data collection normally starts from a series of observations to find human behaviour in a specific field. Grounded theory develops a theory but does not test a theory. Instead, it develops a tactic knowledge. On the other hand, to find out insight into a context, ethnography is not the right choice. In this context, a survey is the most suitable strategy for this research because surveys help to collect and quantify data and to analyse using inferential and descriptive statistics (detailed in section 4.3.1).

4.3.1 Survey

To collect data from a particular group of people a survey method was used. Surveys are defined as conducting research from a specific group of people in a quantitative way and analysing the data using descriptive and inferential statistics (Saunders et al, 2012). There are several methods for survey research. These are:

- Phone
- Mail
- Internet
- Face to face

There is one popular method used in surveys (questionnaires). This study used the questionnaire method to collect data from respondents through face to face and internet. There is a mix of open-ended questions and close-ended questions used in the survey.

4.4 RESEARCH DESIGN

Bryman and Bell (2015) define research design as: *“A research design provides a framework for the collection and analysis of data. A choice of research design reflects decisions about the priority being given to a range of dimensions of the research process”* (p. 40).

They suggested that research design is important for expressing the causal connections between variables, in generalising larger groups of individuals, in selecting a group for research purpose, and to understand human social behaviour in specific social contexts.

According to Bryman and Bell (2015), there are five different types of research designs. These are:

1. Experimental design
2. Cross-sectional or social survey design
3. Longitudinal design
4. Case study design and
5. Comparative design

Blumberg (2008) mentioned that research designs provide answers for questions like:

- What kind of answers is the study looking for and which methods will be applied to find them?
- What techniques will be used to gather data?
- What kind of sampling will be used?
- How will time and cost constraints be dealt with?

On the other hand, Ghauri and Kjell (2005) stated:

“The research design is the overall plan for relating the conceptual research problem to relevant and practicable empirical research. In other words, the research design provides a plan or a framework for data collection and its analysis” (p.56).

According to Saunders et al. (2012), they classified research design in three main classes as shown in table 4.4.

Table 4:4 Classification of research design

Research design	Problem structure
Exploratory	Unstructured
Descriptive	Structured
Causal	Structured

Churchill and Iacobucci (2002) outline three main research designs in a diagram and defined in what context they can be applied. The diagram is shown in figure 4.3.

Figure 4:3 Types of Research Design

(Source: Churchill and Iacobucci, 2002)

4.4.1 Exploratory research design

Exploratory research is to explore or search through a problem or situation to provide insights and understanding (Malhotra, 2007). The main idea of exploratory research is to discover ideas and insights (Churchill and Iacobucci, 2002). Malhotra (2002) showed exploratory research can be used for the following purposes:

- Formulate a problem or define a problem more precisely
- Identify the alternative course of action
- Develop a hypothesis
- Isolate key variables and relationship for further examination
- Gain insights for developing an approach to the problem
- Establish priorities for further research

There are different types of exploratory studies, which include: literature search, experience surveys, interviews, observation, focus groups, and analysis of selected cases. Exploratory research is normally conducted when the field is new to the researcher and when the researcher doesn't have sufficient prior knowledge of the subject area.

4.4.2 Descriptive research design

Descriptive research is normally conducted for characteristics of a market function (Malhotra, 2007). Sierra and Hyman (2013) mentioned,

“Descriptive research, which predominantly is survey-based research. Descriptive research can describe the environment by identifying the characteristics of things or phenomena that are associated with one another” (p.39).

Churchill and Iacobucci (2002) stated that descriptive research normally highlights the relationship between two variables. This research is also known as statistical research. In general, a descriptive study is used to explain the characteristics of a specific group of people. Malhotra (2007) highlighted a few reasons to conduct a descriptive study. These are:

- To describe the characteristics of relevant groups, such as consumers, salespeople, organizations, or market areas.
- To estimate the percentage of units in a specified population exhibiting a certain behaviour.
- To determine the perceptions of product characteristics.
- To determine the degree to which marketing variables are associated.
- To make specific predictions.

Descriptive research requires some specific requirements of the who, what, when, where, why, and way of the research. Survey methods are used to conduct descriptive research. Malhotra (2007) outlined that a vast majority of marketing research studies involve descriptive research. Descriptive research is conducted by using the following major methods:

- Secondary data analysed in a quantitative as opposed to a qualitative manner.
- Surveys.
- Panels.
- Observational and other data.

4.4.3 Causal Research

Causal research is sometimes called explanatory research and it shows the relationship between cause and effect. Ghauri and Kjell (2005) stated that in casual research the problem is under scrutiny and structured. Causal research measures what aspect of a cause occurs and to what extent it is cause and effect. Causal research aims to investigate causal relationships and therefore always involves one or more independent variables (or hypothesised causes) and their relationships with one or more multiple dependent variables. Causal research can be tested using statistical and econometric methods. Blumberg et al. (2008) describe four types of asymmetrical relationships among other reciprocal and symmetrical as shown in figure 4.4.

Figure 4:4 Four types of an asymmetrical causal relationship

Relationship Type	Nature of Relationship	Examples
Stimulus-response	An event or change results in a response from some object.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A change in work rules leads to a higher level of worker output. • A change in government economic policy restricts corporate financial decisions. • A price increase results in fewer unit sales.
Property-disposition	An existing property causes a disposition.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age and attitudes about saving. • Gender attitudes toward social issues. • Social class and opinions about taxation.
Disposition-behavior	A disposition causes a specific behavior.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opinions about a brand and its purchase. • Job satisfaction and work output. • Moral values and tax cheating.
Property-behavior	An existing property causes a specific behavior.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stage of the family life cycle and purchases of furniture. • Social class and family savings patterns. • Age and sports participation.

Source: Blumberg (2008, p. 157)

The selected research design for this study

When researching the behaviour of certain groups of people, descriptive research is useful. Descriptive research builds up a hypothesis and gives a scientific explanation of a problem. Descriptive research answer what, when, where, and how questions. Considering this, it seems to the researcher that descriptive research is the best match for this research. This research is to find out the online shopping behaviour of ethnic people in a specific situation with a clear research question/problem statement and focused hypothesis. Thus, the descriptive research design was used in this study to describe ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Ethnic people are a certain group of people whose behaviours and experience through online services will try to be established in this research. A descriptive study will help to explain and validate research findings.

4.5 RESEARCH METHODS

Ghauri and Kjell (2005) demonstrated: *“Research methods refer to systematic, focused and orderly collection of data for the purpose of obtaining information from them, to solve/answer a particular research problem or question”* (p.109).

Research methods differ from the techniques of data collection. There are two methods of research used to conduct research. These are:

1. Quantitative research method
2. Qualitative research method

4.5.1 Quantitative Research method

Bryman and Bell (2007) define that quantitative research is research that quantifies something in the collection of data and its analysis.

“quantitative research is entailing the collection of numeral data and exhibiting a view of the relationship between theory and research as deductive, a prediction for a natural science approach (and of positivism in particular), and as having an objectivist conception of social reality” (Bryman and Bell, 2007, p.150).

The main steps in quantitative research are outlined by Bryman and Bell (2007) and shown in the diagram (figure 4.5). The first step starts with elaborating on theory and theory applies to the deductive approach. The hypothesis is deduced from the theory and is then tested. The next step is to choose a research design which is the implication of the external validity and findings, and then concepts are measured. Measuring a concept is called operationalisation. In the later stage, a researcher plans to do a set for his/her research sites considering the subject area and respondents. Then the process comes to the administration of the instruments of the research,

which is likely pre-testing the subject. If the research uses a survey method, the sample instrument is structured interviewing, self-administered questionnaires, etc. The collected information needs to be transformed into ‘data’ in the next stage and the process comes to analysis. In that stage, researchers interpret the results of the analysis from where a finding comes up. Once all stages have been developed, the researcher can complete a dissertation. For this research, the researcher used quantitative research methods. The nature of this research is to find out ethnic consumer online buying behaviour, which needs to be quantified and needs an assumption as a hypothesis to test. Quantitative research can use statistics to generalise a finding, test theories and hypothesis. Therefore, quantitative research methods have been applied in this study.

Figure 4:5 The process of quantitative research

Source: Bryman and Bell (2015, p.151)

4.5.1.1 Questionnaire design

Brace (2003) defines:

“In market research, the term questionnaire’ is used to refer both to questionnaires intended for self-completion by survey participants and to survey instruments intended to be administered by an interviewer, either in a face to face interview or by telephone. In other disciplines this is often referred to an interview schedule, with the term questionnaire reserved for the self-completion and interviewer-administered surveys is adhered to” (p.2).

How to design a questionnaire depends on whether the researcher is going to collect exploratory information (generation of hypothesis) or quantitative information (to test the hypothesis). Qualitative data does not require statistical procedures while quantitative data is processed statistically. Brace (2003) stated that data collection is mainly done in two categories.

These are:

1. Interviewer administered
2. Self-completion surveys

Self-completion surveys: a self-completion survey is a paper-based or electronic survey where an individual completes a set of questions. This type of survey can be done without bias and is easy to process for a researcher. The only difficulties are to select a representative sample from a large number of selections, and the response rates are low.

There are many types of survey questions. However, some common survey questions which are referred to many research books include:

- 1) Closed-ended questions
- 2) Open-ended questions
- 3) Rating scale questions
- 4) Likert-type scale questions
- 5) Semantic differential
- 6) Multiple-choice questions
- 7) Rank order questions
- 8) Dichotomous questions

The researcher in this research has planned to use self-completion surveys with a mix of closed-ended, open-ended, multiple-choice, and Likert scale questions. Malhotra (2007) outlined a process of questionnaire design which is shown in figure 4.6.

Figure 4:6 Questionnaire design process

Source: Malhotra (2007, p.300)

The first step to follow designing the questionnaire is focusing on what information is needed.

4.5.1.2 Questionnaire for this research

The questionnaire that was used in this research can be found in appendix 2.

4.5.1.3 Justification of the research question

In order to research ethnic consumers, it was necessary to create a questionnaire and have respondents answer. The completion of the questionnaire allows context to be established for the investigation. Selecting appropriate respondents and by asking appropriate questions the goal of the research was met. There are some points below regarding the importance of the research:

Questionnaire format: The questionnaires designed for this research have the same format for all respondents. Designing one format for all respondents helps to better analyse the opportunity for the researcher. If the same questions are asked differently to the different respondents, it will be difficult to analyse. Brace (2008) indicated, "*Large scale surveys where*

there is anything more than a few dozen respondents, it is impossible to handle and interpret data without a standardized question format” (p.4).

Likert scale questions: Likert scale questions aim to find the degree of respondent’s agreement or disagreement about a specific question. Most of the marketing research mainly use Likert scale questions to know the level of customer satisfaction and attitudes. Likert scale questions help the researcher to continue with consistency in values and cohesiveness to gather information. Another good side of the Likert scale is that respondents can easily understand and answer this questionnaire format.

Demographic questions: demographic questions are sensitive in nature. Some questions are very personal (e.g., age, income, religion) that respondents may not be willing to answer or want to hide from people. Demographic questions in this research aim to categorise the respondents, supposing people’s purchasing behaviour varies with different age ranges and the attitudes and behavioural change occur (attitudes and behaviour changes based on age range). Same as income and purchasing power are related (high income leads to more purchase).

Online shopping and customer satisfaction questions: this research is mainly based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. Questions are designed to understand the satisfaction of a consumer in relation to online shopping. There are questions asked about attitudes, intentions, culture, online groceries, consumer trust in online services, satisfaction, technology and web selection.

Details of the justification of the questions are showed in table 4.5:

Table 4:5 Justification of the research questions

Research Questions	Justification of the questions
Demographic	
1 What is your gender?	This question was asked to help categorise the respondents by gender.
2 What is your educational qualification?	Establishing the educational qualifications of respondents will help the researcher to find out if online shopping is affected by the level of education of ethnic consumers.
3 What is your occupation?	Respondents were asked about their occupation in order to establish whether the jobs they have affected their online shopping behaviour.
4 Which age group do you belong to?	Other similar studies indicate that age is the largest contributing factor in the amount of online shopping an ethnic consumer carries out. Therefore, this study has investigated whether these other studies have merit.
5 How long have you been living in the UK?	This question has been asked to find out whether respondents are likely to have become acculturated to a British way of life. (Ethnic consumers who have lived in the UK longer are presumed to be more likely to live according to British culture rather than the culture of their country of origin.)
6 Which ethnic group do you belong to?	It is important to ascertain the ethnic background of consumers. This is because different ethnic cultures have different beliefs from one another and from British culture. These differences might affect their shopping behaviour.
Online shopping	
7 To understand your activity about online shopping please answer the following. Please tick one number to indicate the frequency of usage of the internet.	
I browse the internet	To see the difference between browsing the internet and online shopping.
I do online shopping	To know the percentage of online shoppers amongst ethnic consumers.
Language barrier stops me from doing online shopping	It is important to establish whether ethnic consumers are not purchasing online due to religious or cultural beliefs. It is also important to ascertain if a lack of linguistic knowledge stops ethnic consumers from purchasing online.
8 To establish online users' experience with online purchasing please tick one number below.	
Quality of online products	It is important to find out the quality of products as it helps consumers to make purchase decisions.
Value of online products	It is important to ascertain the value of products to help consumers make purchase decisions.
Reliability of online services	It is important to know the reliability of online services as it helps consumers to make purchasing decisions.
Consumers attitudes and Intensions	
9 The following statements reflect the attitudes and intentions of consumers towards online shopping, please tick one number to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements.	
The speed of delivery services in online shopping is accurately reported.	If products are delivered in an appropriate time frame, customers are more likely to feel comfortable buying online products again.
I feel safe and secure when doing online shopping	To prevent fraudulent activity, customers tend to be hesitant when providing personal information.

Online shopping is easy and reliable	Customers are unlikely to use online shopping if it isn't convenient and reliable. They are far more likely to stick with what they know (shopping in stores).
I can save my time and energy on online shopping	It is important for customers to find online shopping easy. Otherwise, they are likely to save their time and energy and will just shop in stores.
I manage to buy the cheapest products online compared to a street shop	This question is important because many consumers will buy wherever it is cheaper.
Returning a product bought online is easy and simple	How easily a customer can return a product is an indicator to buy online. If returning is easy, customers feel free to buy without hesitation.
For online products, the warranty is the same as store shopping	The level of warranty that can be secured online compared to store shopping is often a factor that consumers consider.
I can access online shopping 24 hours a day	Normally online shopping is accessible for 24 hours a day. It is essential to know whether a customer is getting accessing problems when buying because of internet problems or any other issues.
I get my money back if any item is missing or damaged when online shopping	Getting a refund of the full amount is often an expectation for online consumers.
Online Groceries and Consumer Culture	
10 The following statements are based on online grocery purchasing and consumers' cultural orientation, to what extent do you agree or disagree? Please indicate by ticking one number below.	
I buy most of my groceries online	To know whether customers do online groceries purchasing or not
Buying online groceries is easy and hassle-free	How easy is it for customers to buy groceries online and as a result are, they likely to keep shopping online?
I never faced any difficulties with online groceries products	Difficulties for any reason restrict customers from buying online. Therefore, it is important to know the possible difficulties that are faced by customers.
Delivery charges on online groceries affect my purchase decision	Sometimes customers change their minds when buying online because of delivery charges. It is essential to know the percentage of consumers that change their purchasing decisions based on delivery charges.
Online groceries products are as fresh as when they are bought in person from a supermarket	When buying from supermarkets it is easy to tell the freshness of products being bought. However, when buying online it is impossible to tell how fresh the product you are buying is. This is because a random person will select the products to send to the customer.
Product substitution does not impact my decision to buy groceries online	Online grocery shopping has a procedure that when the product ordered is not available, the store will replace the product with a similar product. Often this leads to consumers receiving products they didn't want. This can be seen as a large inconvenience. Therefore, this question is asked to see if the substitution of products affects whether people buy groceries online.
I exercise my culture of origin	This question is important to know how culturally orientated individual ethnic consumers are and as a result how likely they are to buy online.
It is essential for me to purchase a product that is related to my culture of origin	This question is important to better understand how culturally orientated individual ethnic consumers are and as a result how likely they are to buy online, as ethnic cultures often do not have products that are suited for them online.
I accept promotional offers by companies	To know how influenced ethnic customers, tend to be by promotional offers from companies.

I found contradictions between the British lifestyle and my cultural beliefs.	To know the controversy between ethnic cultural beliefs and British culture.
Marketing strategies that are specifically aimed at ethnic consumers will improve my online shopping.	It is important to see if specific ethnic marketing strategies create more online shopping activity amongst ethnic consumers.
I think advertising aimed at a target market should be advertised by a representative of that target market	To find the cultural relationship between ethnic consumers and advertising.
Consumer Trust, Satisfaction, Web Selection and Technology use	
11 The following statements reflect consumer trust and satisfaction in online shopping as well as the web selection process in doing online shopping. Please tick one number to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree.	
I only trust branded websites for online shopping	To know which websites customers, trust when purchasing goods.
The unfamiliarity of a website restricts me from purchasing online	To know which websites customers, trust when purchasing goods.
I prefer to provide personal information on websites	How personal information affects consumer purchase decisions online.
Customer reviews and feedback influence my online shopping	To see whether customers follow the reviews and feedback provided by previous consumers.
Trust is built up by repeat purchases among consumer	To see the relationship between purchase decisions and trust.
Cultural beliefs on websites motivate me to increase my trust in online shopping	To see whether consumers focus on their ethnic culture or messages on online services to make a purchase decision.
I do not bother about the security issues of the website	How security issues impact purchase decisions.
The services I received from the online websites are satisfactory	To know whether online websites fulfil consumers' needs and desires in terms of their products and services.
The satisfaction of a products increases based on where it was made (origin of the products)	To see where consumers find satisfaction. Do they find satisfaction when the product comes from their home country?
Customer satisfaction helps to increase loyalty level	To see how the loyalty level increases amongst customers over time as customers are consistently happy with the products and services they have bought.
I feel satisfied if the products are the same as they were described	To know the issues that affect satisfaction amongst consumers.
I feel very comfortable ordering online products	To see find out what customers feel about online ordering.
I do online purchases where the website shows a green padlock	To investigate how much consumers are influenced by security concerns.
Language accessibility helps to browse a website and easy to find products related to my culture	This is important to see how consumers are affected by accessibility on individual online websites.
Detailed information on products that I am interested in buying affects my selection of online shopping	How a customer decision gets affected by the information provided on the website.
Online websites allow consumers to access a larger number of products than supermarkets	To see the market strengths of online services from customer perspectives.
Higher internet speeds tend to encourage an increase in online shopping	To find how internet speed affects online shopping behaviour.
Familiarity with using new technology helps consumers to make online purchases	To investigate how those familiar with other technologies can quickly adapt to online shopping.
I do most of my purchasing through mobile app system	To find out how a customer accepts new technology. For instance, using mobile apps.
I struggle to pay using the online payment system	To investigate how payment facilities, affect online purchasing.

Gathering information about a product is necessary before you buy online	To find out whether customers collect enough information to buy online.
12 Do you identify any negative issues from your online shopping experience?	This is an open question for customers to state their experience with online shopping. This is to ensure that customers can report all their experiences with online shopping.
Questions for Non-users of online shopping	
13 Please tell us why you are not using online shopping-	This question is for consumers who don't use online shopping.

4.5.1.4 Questionnaire Content

Table 4.6 shows the structure of the questionnaire as well as the different constructs. Moreover, the type of scale, anchors, questionnaire number, and the individual objective of each question are summarised in this table.

Table 4:6 Measures Used to Capture Constructs

Constructs	Scale & Type	Anchors	Question Number & Coding	Statements	Question's Objective (Items)
General information					
Demographic		N/A	Q1	What is your gender?	To identify the gender of the respondents to categorise information.
		Multiple choice	Q2	What is your educational qualification?	To categorise respondents according to their education level.
			Q3	What is your occupation?	To identify occupation and online shopping relations.
			Q4	Which age group do you belong to?	To identify the relation between age and online shopping.
			Q5	How long have you been living in the UK?	To find a cultural relationship with the year of stay.
			Q6	Which ethnic group do you belong to?	To categorise respondents with different ethnic nationalities.
Part 1: Users of Online Shopping					
Section 1: Online Shopping					
Online shopping	Q7-Q8		To understand your activity about shopping online, please answer the following. Please tick one number to indicate the frequency of internet uses.		To identify whether respondents are engaged with online shopping and to what extent they apply it.
	1-5 Likert scale	Always to Never	7-1	I browse the internet	To know whether a respondent browses the internet or not.
			7-2	I do online shopping	To identify whether the respondents are related to online shopping.
			7-3	Language barriers stop me from doing online shopping	To evaluate the relationship between the language barrier and online shopping relationship frequency.
	Very good to very poor	8-1	Quality of online products	To find out how a respondent categorises product quality.	
		8-2	Value of online products	To know how a respondent value online product.	
8-3		Reliability of online services	To identify the reliability of online products associated with the online shopping experience.		
Section 2: Consumer Attitudes and Intentions					
Q9		9 The following statements reflect attitudes and intension of a consumer towards online shopping, please tick one number to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements.			To find out whether consumer attitudes and intentions play a role in online shopping behaviour.
Attitudes (2/1)	Strongly agree to	9-1	Speed of delivery services in online shopping is accurate		To find out whether delivery services effects online shopping behaviour.
		9-2	I feel safe and secure do online shopping		To know in what extend customers rely on to provide personal information online.
		9-3	Online shopping is easy and reliable		To determine reliability and online shopping behaviour.

	1-5 Likert Scale	strongly disagree	9-4	I can save my time and energy on online shopping	To demonstrate a shopper's preference for online shopping.
			9-5	I manage to buy the cheapest products online compared to a street shop	To identify how easily a shopper accepts online shopping.
Intensions (2/2)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	9-6	Returning a product bought online is easy and simple	To know the way of behaving with online shopping (product return).
			9-7	In online products, the warranty is the same as store shopping	To ascertain whether products online and in-store are in the same conditions.
			9-8	I can access online shopping 24 hours a day	To state online shopping availability to a consumer.
			9-9	I get my money back if any item is missing or damaged when online shopping	To articulate whether consumers are treated the same online as they are in the shop.
Section 3: Online Groceries and Consumer Culture					
Q10			The following statements are based on online grocery purchasing and consumer cultural orientation, in what extend do you agree or disagree? Please indicate by ticking one number below.		To find out consumer culture and online grocery purchasing relationship.
Online Groceries (3/1)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	10-1	I buy most of my groceries online	To know respondent preference about groceries purchasing.
			10-2	Buying online groceries is easy and hassle-free	To find out how people think about online groceries shopping.
			10-3	I never faced any difficulties with online groceries products	To find any issue related to online groceries shopping.
			10-4	Delivery charges on online groceries affect my purchase decision	To know if consumer behaviours change because of delivery charges.
			10-5	Online groceries products are as fresh as from a supermarket shop	To identify online groceries' quality.
			10-6	Products substitution does not impact my decision to buy groceries online	To know whether products interchanging affects shopping decision.
Consumer Culture (3/2)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	10-7	I exercise my culture of origin	To know the cultural practice of a consumer.
			10-8	It is essential for me to purchase a product that is related to my culture of origin	To identify ethnicity and purchase decision.
			10-9	I accept promotional offers by companies' beliefs experience	To know how an ethnic consumer, show their interest in the promotional offer.
			10-10	I found contradictions between the British lifestyle and my culture	To determine whether an ethnic consumer lifestyle being changed and faces a problem because of culture.
			10-11	An ethnic marketing strategy will improve my online shopping	To know the needs of ethnic marketing strategy.
			10-12	I think advertising based on a target market should be advertised by the representatives of the target market	To know the strategy formulation policy thoughts of ethnic consumers.
Section 4: Consumer Trust, Satisfaction, Web Selection, and Technology use					
Q11			The following statements reflect consumer trust and satisfaction with online shopping and the web selection process to do online shopping. Please tick one number to indicate to what extent you agree or disagree.		To know consumer trust, satisfaction, web selection and technology use towards online shopping.
Consumer Trust (4/1)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	11-1	I only trust branded websites for online shopping	To identify consumer action on online shopping.
			11-2	The unfamiliarity of a website restricts me from purchasing online	To determine the negative effects on online shopping.
			11-3	I prefer to provide personal information on websites	To identify how a respondent thinks to provide personal information on online sites.
			11-4	Customers reviews and feedback affect my online shopping	To know whether a respondent's behaviour or action changes due to reviews and feedback.
			11-5	Trust is built up by repeat purchases among consumer	To identify the repeat customers.

			11-6	Cultural beliefs on website motivate to increase my trust in online shopping	To know how an ethnic consumer is motivated by their cultural beliefs.
Satisfaction (4/2)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	11-7	I do not bother about the security issues of the website	To know the action or thought about a security issue of a website.
			11-8	The services I received from online shops are satisfactory	To know the rate of satisfaction of a customer.
			11-9	The satisfaction of a products arises based on where it came from (origin of the products)	To identify if the consumers are oriented to buy the country-of-origin products.
			11-10	Customer satisfaction helps to increase loyalty level	To know the relationship between satisfaction and loyalty level.
			11-11	I feel satisfied if the products are the same as they are described	To know consumers way of satisfaction.
			11-12	I feel very easy and comfortable ordering online products	To identify how easily can purchase made online.
Web Selection (4/3)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	11-13	I do online purchase where a website shows a green padlock	To identify the indicators of website selection.
			11-2	Language accessibility helps to browse a website and easy to find products related to my culture	To determine the types and characteristic of the website.
			11-3	Detailed information of a product affects my selection of online shopping	To identify the information required about a product on the website.
			11-4	Online I can access a larger number of products than in a supermarket	To know the range of the products on website and consumer behaviour.
			11-5	The speed of the website selected for shopping boosts the online shopping behaviour	To find out consumer attitudes on the internet and website speed.
Technology use (4/2)	1-5 Likert Scale	Strongly agree to strongly disagree	11-6	Familiarity with using new technology helps with having a better online experience	To identify consumers action towards a known website.
			11-7	I do most of my purchasing through a mobile app system	To find out how new systems are used by consumers (e.g., mobile app).
			11-8	I struggle to pay using an online payment system	To know the payment option facilities accepted by a consumer.
			11-9	Gathering information about a product is necessary before you buy online	To identify whether consumers are looking for adequate information before taking action.
Open-ended question			Q12	Do you identify any negative issues from your online shopping experience?	To know customers thought about the positive and negative sides of online shopping.
Part 2: Non-Users of Online Shopping					
Open-ended question			Q13	Please state why you are not using online shopping:	To identify the reason behind not using online shopping.

4.5.1.5 Pilot Questionnaire and questionnaire amendment

Questionnaire piloting: questionnaire piloting is testing the questions in a small sample of the respondents to eliminate potential problems (Malhotra, 2007). Normal procedure is to test a questionnaire as much as possible before taking the final survey. By piloting a questionnaire, a researcher can identify the gaps (questions content, wording, sequence, form and layout, question difficulty, and instruction).

Piloting a questionnaire is possible by interviewing known people and asking for feedback. Respondents behaviours and attitudes being justified by interviewing a respondent personally. The researcher here followed the steps of piloting to find the best questionnaire that respondents can answer promptly. There are different amendments based on the suggestion of the respondents and the director of studies. After one pilot, another version was created, and another pilot survey was taken to find the mistakes and limitations. Two important variables (income and religion) have been eliminated from the research:

Income: a person's financial stability could be based on income. High income leads to a person spending more compared to low-income groups. Income is a tricky question ask because some people feel as though their income is an expression of their personal worth. Respondents might be embarrassed to share their income, even though research questionnaires are anonymous. Sometimes, the confirmed income does not match with respondents' other financial circumstances and respondents have a fear that someone might find out their income. There are some statements from respondents below about the question of their income:

“Our income is personal information that we are entitled to be discreet and private about.”

“There is just no need to disclose what we earn to anyone.”

“income is completely a private matter and it is better not to ask.”

Therefore, this study has removed the income-related question from the questionnaire. However, the study has taken into consideration from the secondary sources and journal (Kotler, 2016; Wu, 2003; Dyer et al., 2006; Servon and Kaestner, 2008) to justify and add income in this research. Different statements (e.g., occupation and income are related) from this questionnaire also helped the researcher to gain knowledge about income and expenditure. Additionally, this study also used income sources from the Office for National Statistics.

Religion: religion has a significant effect on consumer buying behaviour. During different religious festivals, consumer buying behaviour changes. This study also discussed religion as well as income, and respondents also have disagreements about answering questions related to religion. Because of global religious conflicts, some respondents suggested not to add religion-

related questions in the questionnaire. Therefore, this study has removed this question from the questionnaire. However, this study used secondary sources (Gordon, 1978; Guilherme and John, 2015; Jafari et al., 2014) and data from the Office for National Statistics for the analysis. Additionally, ethnic minority consumer religion can be identified easily depending on the nationality they came from.

This study has a series of questionnaire amendments as showed in table 4.7.

Table 4:7 Questionnaire amendment history

Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 1 Version.1)	
Q5. What is your income level?	Some respondents were not comfortable to answer this question. One respondent suggested income level should not be asked because it is a completely personal matter (detailed in section 4.5.1.5). This question was removed from the questionnaire.
Q9. How important is it to you to purchase products related to your cultural origin?	The question was asked in the first part of the questionnaire. One respondent commented to move it to the second part because the first part is mainly basic questions. So, it has transferred to the second part.
Q15. Are there any negative aspects of online shopping?	The question was close ended with a 'yes' or 'no' answer. If the answer was 'yes' there was no option to write what they are. Q15. Added a box to write your own words if the answer is yes.
Q23. Is there any contradiction between your lifestyle and online shopping?	There was a respondent who could not understand the question. Question 23 was re-written for better understanding
Q28. Please state a few points about browsing online (e.g., advantage and disadvantages of browsing online)?	There was a suggestion from a respondent to put a box stating the advantages and disadvantages of browsing online. This Q28 was modified with required boxes.
Q29. What is your general thought about online shopping (please write in few words)? Q30. What do you think about ethnic minorities' online shopping (please write in n few words, e.g., positive and negative aspects of online shopping)?	A few respondents said this question was already answered. So, it is unnecessary to repeat the question. This Q29 and Q30 was removed from the questionnaire.
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 2 Version.2)	
New questions developed by removing some irrelevant questions	According to the developed hypothesis, some new questions added, and some question re-written on consumer attitudes and intention.
Researcher details have moved to the end of the questionnaire	Researcher ID details have moved from the introductory part to the end of the questionnaire. Respondents will get to know about the ID once they complete the questionnaire
Q4. What is your education?	There was a suggestion from the director of studies about criteria of education level. Therefore, the education level has been modified.
Q5. Which religious group do you belong to?	The suggestions from the respondents and the Director of studies are that to find out about online shopping behaviour this question is irrelevant (detailed in section 4.5.1.5). So, question 5 has been removed from the questionnaire.
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 2 Version.3)	
There are two parts developed in the questionnaire	For the users and non-users of online shopping, two parts were created. The first part belongs to users of online shopping and the second part is for non-users of online shopping. In part 1 there are 4 sections for users of online shopping.
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 3 Version.4)	

The variables have been removed	There were six variables stated in the questionnaire in every part of the questions. The questionnaire has now been designed removing the variable indicators because it is not necessary for the respondents. There is a copy made for the researcher only indicating which questions are related to what variables.
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 3 Version.5)	
New questions developed	There was a question about the negative aspects of online shopping. Some respondents mentioned the substitution of products when shopping online. Therefore, a question was written about product substitution. The layout of the questionnaire was made with some boxes
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 3 Version.6)	
Q9 Was removed from section 1 and put at the end of section 4 Q7 One statement style has changed	Some respondents suggested describing their online shopping experience at the end of the questionnaire. Therefore, Q9 has transferred from section 1 to the end of questionnaire section 4. In Q7 there was a statement about language and online shopping. Some respondents suggested changing the wording of the statement relating the scale. Therefore, the wording of the question was changed.
Questionnaire Amendments (Pilot 4 Version.7)	
Some grammatical mistakes have been corrected	There were grammatical mistakes found in the fourth pilot interview.
Q4 Age group has been amended	The question was structured asking which age group you belong to. Some respondents suggested the questionnaire should not be taken by respondents under 18 years of age. So, the structure of the questionnaire was amended.

4.5.1.6 Questionnaire distribution

Questionnaires were distributed among respondents who are living in the UK. Respondents were targeted based on ethnicity. Mainly people of Asian and African origin counted towards the population of this study. Questionnaires filled in by any other ethnic origin were eliminated from the study. Questionnaires were distributed in two ways: self-administered and an online questionnaire. Online questionnaires were distributed among respondents who were not reachable after several attempts.

To distribute the online questionnaires a survey monkey was used. A survey link was created using survey monkey (<https://www.surveymonkey.co.uk/r/XBQGX9R>). Links were distributed through Facebook, messenger, and via email. The link did not allow respondents to complete the questionnaire a second time. In some cases, a follow up was made to get a response from the respondents. Emails were sent twice and even three times to the people who did not complete the questionnaire or left it incomplete.

Self-administered questions were collected from 1st of May to the 18th of June 2018 and online questionnaire were collected from 7th of June to 18th of June 2018. To collect the questionnaires some public places were selected, e.g., community meeting spaces, libraries, shopping centres, restaurants, parks and residential homes. Online questionnaires received after 18th of June were

eliminated from the study. At some points, the researcher acted as a bilingual person because some respondents could not read or understand English. The respondents who could not read also read through the questionnaire by the researcher and completed according to the answer from the respondent. Multilingual help collected questionnaire is 10'. Details of the questionnaire collection and areas are presented in table 4.8.

Table 4:8 Questionnaire collection

Date (2018)	Place of collection	Number of questionnaires	Methods of collection
1 st May to 15 th June	UWS, Paisley campus	42	Self-administered
6 th May and 8 th of May	Brighton	21	Self-administered
8 th May to 16 th of June	Tower Hamlets, London	134	Self-administered
17 th May to 21 st of May	Camden Town, London	66	Self-administered
24 th of May	UWS London campus	18	Self-administered
25-27 th of May	Newham, London	57	Self-administered
7 th June to 18 th of June	UK residents	53	Online
Total self-administered collected questionnaires		338	Accepted 314, Rejected 24
Total online collected questionnaires		53	Accepted 51, and Rejected 2
Total accepted questionnaires		365	

Some questionnaires were rejected for not completing all sections and some had completed both parts of the questionnaire. Those who completed both parts of the questionnaire has eliminated from the study because it is not clear whether the respondents are users of online shopping or non-users of online shopping. A few questionnaires were completed by those of British and Scottish origin. Some questionnaires were completed without the respondent reading the questions and completed only on one Likert scale (e.g., all the answers either agree or disagree). These questionnaires were rejected. Questionnaires received after 18th of June 2018 are not included in this list either.

The response rate to this research seems low compared to the time spent on the questionnaire. It indicates how stressful this questionnaire collection from the ethnic minority population was for the researcher. However, the percentage of questionnaires completed by the respondents are very good. There were 92.9% correctly completed questionnaires in this research. The researcher collected online questionnaires when it was found that targeted responses did not come through the self-administered survey.

4.5.1.7 Fieldwork experience

To collect the questionnaires the researcher went through a lot of effort. Below are detailed several experiences the researcher had while doing the fieldwork:

1. The researcher handed out the questionnaire among respondents. Some respondents thought this was an advertising campaign. Hence, it was very hard to clarify to some

respondents that this was only for academic purpose. Some respondents did not show any interest to listen to the questions.

2. At some points, respondents took a long time to complete the questionnaire. While completing, respondents would take a phone call or sometimes started chatting with another friend or asked and discussed the questionnaire.
3. Some respondents showed some racist attitudes while asking them to complete the questionnaire. It was hard to categorise ethnic minority respondents and mainstream respondents. There was a good positive response to this research though.
4. The data collection period was during the holy month of Ramadan (the fasting month for Muslims) which made it difficult for the researcher to engage with many people on a daily basis. The weather was hot, and tiredness was involved.
5. It was estimated that there would be plenty of data from community meetings, wedding parties and religious occasions. There were fewer responses from these parties. People appeared to be focusing more on their personal agenda rather than helping to complete the questionnaire. Some respondents were very keen to complete the questionnaire, but they had language difficulties or were unable to read the questionnaire. In these cases, the researcher acted as an interpreter person to complete the questionnaire.
6. There were special thanks at the end of completing the questionnaire. In some cases, a tea or coffee session was held to discuss the topic as well as some personal conversation.

4.6 SAMPLE SELECTION

Sample selection is a procedure to collect social data in a definite procedure (Bryman and Bell 2015; Ghauri and Kjell, 2005 and Blumberg et al, 2007). Ghauri and Kjell (2005) explained that when a research problem is defined, alongside suitable methods to collect data and all the instruments developed it is crucial to select sample size. To conduct research, it is not possible to collect data from larger numbers of populations. Selecting a sample following the appropriate method helps a researcher to save time and cost. To conduct a research selecting sample size is very important.

A research result might vary if the proper sample size is not selected from the right place. Ghauri and Kjell (2005) mentioned a few steps to draw a sample size for any research. These include defining the population, identifying the sample frame, selecting a sample frame, selecting a sampling procedure, determining the sample size, selecting the units and collecting data from the sampled units. Blumberg et al (2007) added that by selecting a sample size researcher draw a conclusion about the entire population (a population is the total collection of

elements about which researcher wish to make some inference). According to Blumberg et al. (2007), there are a few reasons to do sampling. These are lower cost, greater accuracy of results, greater speed of data collection, availability of population elements. Sample procedures can be divided into two ways and examples are shown in table 4.9.

1. Probability sampling
2. Non-probability sampling

Table 4:9 Types of Sampling

Probability sampling	Non-probability sampling
Simple random sampling	Convenience sampling
Systematic sampling	Judgmental sampling
Stratified sampling	Quota sampling
Cluster sampling	Snowball sampling

Probability sampling: when a researcher feels that the sample represents the whole community that is being studied and can justify it, it is called probability sampling. In probability sampling, all population have a non-zero chance to get selected (Bryman and Bell 2015; Ghauri and Kjell, 2005 and Blumberg et al, 2007).

Non-probability sampling: non-probability sampling takes the opposite direction of probability sampling. Malhotra (2007) described that non-probability sampling relies on the judgment of the researcher rather than the chance to select sample elements. This type of sampling is called a good estimate of population characteristics.

Considering the nature of the study convenience sampling uses in this study. Convenience sampling is a non-probability sampling technique where samples are selected from the population only because they are conveniently available to the researcher (Harding, 2019). Convenience sampling helps to find the respondents easily on the specific field (Saunders et al., 2012). The researcher used some specific locations and randomly chosen respondents to get information from them that include the library, educational institution, market, wedding hall and religious places. But it is known that non-probability sampling approach that the findings from the study cannot be confidently generalised to the population. Because convenience sampling based on closed contacts (e.g., surveying friends, family, relatives, colleague). These why the study has taken respondents very carefully so that different characteristics of a population can be found rather than getting the population of the same type. During the questionnaire collection consumer demographic information highly prioritise to receive multi-cultural people of the ethnic consumer.

4.7 SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size is important for any kind of research. Selecting a sample size depends on a few things. Most importantly it depends on time and cost, response rate, and the kind of analysis. One general belief is that a larger sample size minimises the common errors of the research. Ryan (2013) stated,

“Determining sample size does require overcoming certain obstacles. In particular, whether our objective is to determine a sample size so as to have a desired degree of power for a hypothesis test, to have a confidence interval with a specified width, or to estimate a parameter with a maximum error of estimation for a specified probability, it is necessary to specify values of the parameters that are involved in the distribution of the estimate of the parameter for which the hypothesis test, confidence interval, or point estimate is being constructed. Since the other parameters will also generally be unknown, some type of estimate must be provided for them.” (p.127).

The larger sample size is more accurate compared to the smaller sample size. The researcher has given a scale of the sample size. For example, Comrey (1973) stated that a sample size of 50 is called a very poor sample size. Similarly, a 100 is poor, 200 is fair, and it is good if it's 300. For this research, the researcher is focusing on different areas and ethnic minority people. The researcher is focusing on people who migrated from different countries, or their ethnicity is based in foreign countries. By the nature of quantitative research, the sample size of 365 people includes male and female participants from different ethnicities. According to Comrey (1973) sampling guide, this study was conducted with good sample size.

4.8 DATA COLLECTION

Data collection is a process of gathering and measuring information. In market research, data is generally collected by the researcher. There are two types of data collection:

1. Primary data collection
2. Secondary data collection

4.8.1 Primary Data collection

Primary data is mainly collected by the researcher. Primary data does not exist, and it is the work of the researcher (Saunders et al. 2012). Primary data is important for all types of research, but primary data collection is very expensive as the researcher has to conduct a large number of data collection. Primary data collection takes time and is normally expensive compared to secondary data collection. There are different methods to collect primary data. Most common primary data collection techniques are:

- 1) Questionnaire method
- 2) Interview method

- 3) Focus group discussion method
- 4) Projective techniques
- 5) Delphi techniques

4.8.2 Secondary Data collection

Saunders et al. (2012) defined that secondary data collection is the way of getting information from different sources (e.g., books, journal articles, internet sources). Secondary data collection for this research includes external and internal sources. The researcher in this study used as external sources mostly books, journal articles and website publication. Secondary data helps a researcher to save time and cost, as well as to understand in-depth the background of the study. Secondary data has more accuracy because it has already been validated by previous researchers and has the same reliability. However, there are some limitations of secondary data. These include:

- Irrelevant data
- Lack of availability
- Wrong information
- Valid sources
- Insufficiency of data

If secondary data is used from a valid source the research outcomes gain validity. Collecting and using secondary sources mainly depends on valid grounds from where the data was collected. Some researchers use inaccurate information or irrelevant information which might mislead the objectives of the research.

The researcher in this research used both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected by the researcher from field surveys and as secondary data different journal articles, books and internet sources were used. The study analysed the primary data through descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study were justified through secondary studies and literature. The understanding of the study and study rational has been developed through secondary data. Figure 4.7 describes about the types of secondary data.

Figure 4:7 Types of secondary data

(Source: Ghauri and Kjell, 2005, p.100)

4.9 DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis is to find the meaning of the data. Data is analysed through a process and from the output a conclusion is formed. Data analysis and transforming the data in this research followed Saunders et al.'s (2012) research book. This study has used quantitative data analysis. For quantitative data analysis statistical software SPSS version, 25 was used in this research. The researcher has followed a few steps to do quantitative data analysis. These steps are shown in diagram 4.8.

Figure 4:8 Steps of quantitative data analysis

4.9.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics in this study is to summarise the collected data in a meaningful way. The collected data needs interpretation. To do the interpretation the data will be shown as a graphical presentation and frequency distribution. There will be focuses on mean, median, and

mode to measure central tendency, standard deviation, and variance to measure dispersion. Crosstabulation of the different variables is also presented in descriptive research.

4.9.2 Inferential statistics

In inferential statistics, researchers show a prediction of the presented data. This part tells the researcher how to generalise the presented data. Inferential statistics talk about correlation, regression analysis, data validity and reliability.

4.9.2.1 Correlation

Saunders et al (2016) indicated that correlation is used to describe the relationship of two variables. The relationship comes as a positive or negative strength. Pearson correlation coefficient r range from -1 to +1, where -1 indicates a perfect negative correlation, +1 indicates perfect positive and 0 indicates no correlation. Cohen (2013) stated the correlation coefficient range which is shown in table 4.10:

Table 4:10 Range of correlation coefficient

Strength of Association	Coefficient, r	
	Positive	Negative
Small	.1 to .29	-0.1 to -0.29
Medium	.3 to .49	-0.3 to -0.49
Large	.5 to 1.0	-0.5 to -1.0

(Source: Cohen, 2013)

4.9.2.2 Multiple Regression

Regression analysis was carried out in order to show how multiple independent variables relate to dependent variables. Regression analysis is a prediction or forecast of the variables. The research has shown how much change happens when one dependable is varied and another variable is fixed. The regression model gives more insights into the details of a relationship between a number of variables when compared to a standard correlation.

4.9.2.3 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical tool that is used to analyse the differences between group means of two or more samples (Pallant, 2016). ANOVA compares the variance between groups. This study conducted a one-way analysis of variance. One-way analysis of variance is used when there are two or more group means needing to be compared on a continuous variable. The value F represents the variance between the groups. A large F ratio indicates that there is more variability between the groups than within the groups (Pallant, 2016).

4.9.2.4 Independent sample T-Test

For independent samples, a T-test shows whether there is a statistically significant difference in the mean scores for the two groups (Pallant, 2016). This test is used when two sets of

information come from the same group of the population. An independent sample T-test is a very powerful technique which is normally used for a variety of research problems. This research used an independent sample T-test alongside other statistical tests.

4.9.2.5 Data validity

This research is valid as the research represents the phenomena that it is supposed to measure. Data can be valid to a certain degree and variables that are accurate are judged to be more valid (Malhotra, 2007). The researcher in this research will check criterion validity. Criterion validity indicates whether a scale is performing as expected in relation to the other variables (Malhotra, 2007). Criterion validity measures variables that include demographic and psychographic characteristics, attitudinal, and behavioural measures. The researcher will compare the data of all the respondents to check the validity in this research.

4.9.2.6 Data reliability

Here the researcher discusses internal consistency to highlight the reliability of the data. Internal consistency is used to measure how the item is measuring the same construct. There are many methods to measure internal consistency, but this research has used the most popular method: Cronbach's Alpha. Cronbach's Alpha is based on a few items such as the number of questions on a questionnaire and average inter-item correlation. Cronbach's Alpha is commonly used when there are multiple Likert scale questions in a study. If there is a small number of items (less than 7) in the scale, then the Cronbach's alpha could be smaller. When the Cronbach's alpha is smaller it might show a correlation between items. It is suggested that inter-item correlations range from .2 to .4 (Lehman et al., 2013). Cronbach alpha score ranges from (0) to (1). If the score comes in at (0) it means the result is unreliable and (1) means the result is completely reliable. If the Cronbach alpha score is less than .6 it is considered poor and above .8 is considered a very good score. According to Cohen (2013) the Cronbach's Alpha range is presented in table 4.11:

Table 4:11 Cronbach's Alpha range

Cronbach's Alpha α	Internal consistency
$0.9 \leq \alpha$	Excellent
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Good
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor
$\alpha < 0.5$	Unacceptable

4.10 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

For research that uses primary sources, confidentiality is very important. Some demographic information has been ascertained from some individual ethnic consumers in order to conduct the research. They have been assured that all information will be secured and will not be published to any third parties. The information was collected only for research purpose. During the data collection, respondents' consent was established. Considerations for work periods and other anonymous circumstances have been understood.

There was an information sheet stating the purpose and aim of the study, why the respondents should answer the research questions, and what their benefits will be if they complete the questionnaire. There was a procedure at the beginning of the questionnaire to ensure that the respondents understood the purpose of the research and that they should feel free to answer all the questions based on their own experiences.

The consent sheet and questionnaire are included in the appendix 1 & 2 of this research.

CHAPTER 5: DATA ANALYSIS

This chapter is about presenting the data that has been collected by the researcher as well as describing trends and patterns that can be seen. The data is presented in graphs to help highlight statistics that are of relevance to this investigation. Pertinent information, for example, can be displayed using percentages and frequencies in graphical format. As a result, the statistics can be easily analysed to check for variables, correlations, and regression analyses. From this analysis of the data hypotheses can be made. The hypotheses can then be analysed to see whether the data supports the hypotheses or whether the data contradicts the hypotheses. Both inferential and descriptive statistics have been used to analyse the data. The descriptor has been derived from the literature review and theoretical framework. SPSS version 25 software has also been used to analyse the data.

5.1 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

5.1.1 Gender, Education, and Occupation

The frequency distribution shows that in this survey of the 365 respondents 56.99% were male and 43.01% were female (table 5.1 and figure: 5.1). So, the response rate contains more male responses than female responses. However, a census in 2011 showed that there are more females in the UK than there are males. So, in that regard, the data is a little biased. There were 35.3% (table 5.6) Bangladeshi respondents, which are more than one-third of the total respondents. The second-largest group of respondents was Pakistani and Indian respondents. The educational level (table 5.2) of the respondents shows interesting trends. A comparison showed a response rate from college-level respondents of 24%, whilst university level respondents had a slightly smaller share of response at 21.6%. The Office for national statistics (2016) published a result in the UK educational qualification that shows that 27% of England and Wales's population has a higher educational qualification. It can be safely assumed therefore, that most of the respondents had the ability to answer the questions and understood the research context.

Table 5:1 Gender of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	208	57	57	57
	Female	157	43	43	100
	Total	365	100	100	

In terms of the occupations of the respondents (table 5.3), data was collected mostly from students (making up 23.6% of those surveyed). This indicates that many of the responses have

come from younger people. Young people are the group in society that have the highest skills relating to technology and as such are far more effective at carrying out activity online. Partly due to this fact, young people are for more likely to use online facilities when comparing them to any other age group.

Table 5:2 Education of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	School Level	53	14.5	14.5	14.5
	College Level	91	24.9	24.9	39.5
	University Level	79	21.6	21.6	61.1
	Masters	66	18.1	18.1	79.2
	Doctorate	41	11.2	11.2	90.4
	Others	35	9.6	9.6	100
	Total	365	100	100	

Table 5:3 Occupation of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Student	86	23.6	23.6	23.6
Public Service	42	11.5	11.5	35.1
Self-employed	73	20.0	20.0	55.1
Retired	35	9.6	9.6	64.7
Businesses	54	14.8	14.8	79.5
Other	75	20.5	20.5	100.0
Total	365	100.0	100.0	

5.1.2 Age

The researcher has focused on distributing the data according to the differing age groups in society. From the collected data, 30.4% of respondents are from the 26-35 age range and 22.5% are from 36-45 age range (table 5.4). A census taken in 2011 reported that in the UK, 16% of the population were in the category of the ageing population (66+) in the UK. Yet, this research only collected responses from 6.6% of the ageing population. However, the collected data is still relevant because a 2011 census also reported that there are more young ethnic working individuals in the UK compared to young British people. There number of the aged ethnic population is smaller compared to the British aged population. The bell curve data (appendix 3) result indicates that it is skewed to the left a bit but is distributed normally among ethnic respondents, especially when considering the relatively small sample size. This study has collected most of the data from the population of the ethnic student (table, 5.3). The overall findings of this research will be generalized with caution.

Table 5:4 Age of the respondents

	Frequency	Number	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18-25	48	13.2	13.2
	26-35	111	30.4	30.4
	36-45	82	22.5	22.5
	46-55	66	18.1	18.1
	56-65	34	9.3	9.3
	66+	24	6.6	6.6
Total	Total	365	100.0	100.0

5.1.3 Living status in the UK

The survey asked respondents to explain their living status (table 5.5). Living status can determine different people's cultural adaptability with British culture. Britain is more advanced in the online sector than any other country (Clark et al., 2015). Eventually, people adapt to the social system of the country they move to. Most of the respondents in the survey have been living in the UK for 6-10 years. The second-largest group of responses are from those who have resided in the UK since birth and the third largest group of responses are from people from the 26 years and above range. This does mean that the respondents are familiar with the online activities and British culture.

Table 5:5 Living status of the respondents in the UK

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Since birth	64	17.5	17.6	17.6
	0-5 years	34	9.3	9.3	26.9
	6-10 years	80	21.9	22.0	48.9
	11-15 years	49	13.4	13.5	62.4
	16-20 years	38	10.4	10.4	72.8
	21-25 years	40	11.0	11.0	83.8
	26 years and above	59	16.2	16.2	100.0
	Total	364	99.7	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.3		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.4 The ethnicity of the respondents

The research is mainly based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. Responses have been collected from people of both Asian and African countries (BAME population) (table 5.6 and figure 5.1). Thirty-five-point-three percent of the responses have been recorded from Bangladeshi's/British Bangladeshis. A 2011 census showed that most of the ethnic population that is living in the UK are from Indian descent whilst the second largest population of ethnic minorities are from Pakistan. However, the researcher has collected data mainly from the Tower Hamlets area in London. This area has a higher percentage of the ethnic population from Bangladeshi origin. Ofcom (2013) reported that 74% of the Bangladeshi ethnic group in Great

Britain lives in London. As a result, the survey has a far higher response level from those of Bangladeshi origin compared to Indian and Pakistani people.

Table 5:6 Ethnicity of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	129	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Indian/British Indian	48	13.2	13.2	48.5
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	49	13.4	13.4	61.9
	Chinese/British Chinese	24	6.6	6.6	68.5
	Other Asian	46	12.6	12.6	81.1
	African/Black African	44	12.1	12.1	93.2
	Other	25	6.8	6.8	100.0
	Total	365	100.0	100.0	

Figure 5:1 Ethnicity of the respondents

5.1.5 Online grocery shopping

When asked about purchasing groceries online, the majority did not buy groceries online (table 5.7). Out of 365 respondents 15.6% agreed they buy groceries online and 13.4% neither agree nor disagree with the statement. More than 2/3 of the respondents do not buy groceries online (67%).

Table 5:7 Prefer to buy groceries online

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	131	35.9	42.8	42.8
	Disagree	74	20.3	24.2	67.0
	Neutral	41	11.2	13.4	80.4
	Agree	43	11.8	14.1	94.4
	Strongly Agree	17	4.7	5.6	100.0
	Total	306	83.8	100.0	
Missing	System	59	16.2		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.6 Conveniences of online groceries

In terms of the convenience of buying groceries online, some respondents explained that they think that buying groceries is easy and hassle-free (35.2%). Table 5.8 shows that 30.6% of respondents stated that they do not know whether buying groceries online is easy or not.

Table 5:8 Buying grocery online is easy and hassle-free

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	38	10.4	12.5	12.5
	Disagree	66	18.1	21.7	34.2
	Neutral	93	25.5	30.6	64.8
	Agree	79	21.6	26.0	90.8
	Strongly Agree	28	7.7	9.2	100.0
	Total	304	83.3	100.0	
Missing	System	61	16.7		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.7 Practising own culture

When establishing the motivation around whether ethnic peoples buy groceries online, it is important to consider the weight respondents put in their cultural background or preferred culture. This is because there may be a link between the culture practised by an individual and the online shopping behaviour that they employ. Cultural activity described here is defined by attending British cultural events, buying British cultural products online, whether or not an individual attends traditional religious events of their country of origin, or whether they no longer attend. Forty-seven percent of the respondents (33.1% agree and 13.9% strongly agree) confirmed they practice their traditional ethnic culture of their country of origin (Table 5.9).

Table 5:9 Practising traditional cultural value is important to ethnic consumer

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	22	6.0	7.3	7.3
	Disagree	49	13.4	16.2	23.5
	Neutral	89	24.4	29.5	53.0
	Agree	100	27.4	33.1	86.1
	Strongly Agree	42	11.5	13.9	100.0
	Total	302	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	63	17.3		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.8 Accepting promotional offer

A researcher in a different study highlighted that ethnic people tend to be highly motivated to accept promotional offers, which is backed up in the primary research of this study (Maxwell, 2012). Twenty-one-point five percent of the respondents strongly agree that they almost always accept promotional offers from companies whilst 34.1% of the respondents agree that they tend to accept promotional offers. Around 20% of the respondent's stated that they are not interested in accepting promotional offers. It is therefore evident that almost 50% of respondents in this study accept promotional offers when they are offered by companies. Descriptive statistics of the promotional offer have been presented in table 5.10.

Table 5:10 Ethnic consumers are motivated to accept the promotional offer

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	22	6.0	7.3	7.3
	Disagree	39	10.7	12.9	20.2
	Neutral	73	20.0	24.2	44.4
	Agree	103	28.2	34.1	78.5
	Strongly Agree	65	17.8	21.5	100.0
	Total	302	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	63	17.3		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.9 Conflict between cultures

Some respondents believe that there is a conflict between the British lifestyle and their culture of origin. Thirty-nine percent of respondents (table 5.11) feel a contradiction with the British lifestyle, whereas 28.2% of respondents do not feel any contradiction with British lifestyle.

Table 5:11 Ethnic consumer find contradiction between British lifestyle and own culture

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	37	10.1	12.1	12.1
	Disagree	49	13.4	16.1	28.2
	Neutral	100	27.4	32.8	61.0
	Agree	84	23.0	27.5	88.5
	Strongly Agree	35	9.6	11.5	100.0
	Total	305	83.6	100.0	
Missing	System	60	16.4		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.10 Marketing strategy

There are many ethnic consumers in the UK and their online buying behaviour may differ (Maxwell, 2012). Twenty-eight-point-four percent of the respondents agree that there need to be better marketing strategies for ethnic consumers (table 5.12). Fourteen percent of respondents strongly agree with this point.

Table 5:12 Business should introduce better marketing strategy for ethnic consumer

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	23	6.3	7.6	7.6
	Disagree	50	13.7	16.5	24.1
	Neutral	93	25.5	30.7	54.8
	Agree	86	23.6	28.4	83.2
	Strongly Agree	51	14.0	16.8	100.0
	Total	303	83.0	100.0	
Missing	System	62	17.0		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.11 Providing personal information

Providing personal information on selected websites is an important step for consumers. Most of the respondents do not prefer to provide personal information on websites. Only around a quarter of respondents agree to providing personal information on websites (table 5.13).

Table 5:13 Providing personal information on the website is safe and secure

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	56	15.3	18.5	18.5
	Disagree	79	21.6	26.2	44.7
	Neutral	85	23.3	28.1	72.8
	Agree	66	18.1	21.9	94.7
	Strongly Agree	16	4.4	5.3	100.0
	Total	302	82.7	100.0	
Missing	System	63	17.3		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.12 Customer reviews and feedback

Customer reviews and feedback help consumers to see the previous experience of other consumers with a product. This can be an invaluable tool in deciding whether they make a purchase and if so, which product they choose. The majority of ethnic consumers indicated that their buying decision is affected by reviews and feedback from other customers. More than half of the respondents stated that other customers' feedback is a major factor when deciding what products, they buy online (table 5.14).

Table 5:14 Checking customers reviews, and feedback is important to buy online groceries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	13	3.6	4.3	4.3
	Disagree	26	7.1	8.6	13.0
	Neutral	69	18.9	22.9	35.9
	Agree	107	29.3	35.5	71.4
	Strongly Agree	85	23.3	28.2	99.7
	Total	301	82.5	100.0	
Missing	System	64	17.5		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.13 Language accessibility and culture on website

Language accessibility helps ethnic consumers to browse and find the products that relates to their culture. More than 50% of the ethnic consumer (74.4%) indicated they find its easy when websites have language accessibility. It helps to find a product and its description. Very few numbers of the respondents were disagreed and 18.2% of the respondents neither agree nor disagree (table 5.15).

Table 5:15 Language accessibility helps to browse online groceries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	2	.5	.7	.7
	Disagree	20	5.5	6.7	7.4
	Neutral	54	14.8	18.2	25.6
	Agree	127	34.8	42.8	68.4
	Strongly Agree	94	25.8	31.6	100.0
	Total	297	82.5	100.0	
Missing	System	68	18.6		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.14 Using an app system

Nowadays the majority of online service providers have an app system that can be downloaded. Using mobile applications helps consumers to place orders incredibly easily and efficiently. This app only has to be logged in to with the consumers' personal ID once, which saves the hassle from frequently having to log in. More than one-third of the respondents confirmed that

they use app systems and it's easy to place an order online whereas a quarter stated that they do not (table 5.16).

Table 5:16 Using mobile app system is easy

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	46	12.6	15.2	15.2
	Disagree	71	19.5	23.4	38.6
	Neutral	64	17.5	21.1	59.7
	Agree	83	22.7	27.4	87.1
	Strongly Agree	39	10.7	12.9	100.0
	Total	303	83.0	100.0	
Missing	System	62	17.0		
Total		365	100.0		

5.1.15 Online payment system

Online payment facilities are the most crucial part for a consumer when using online services. Researchers have demonstrated that customers often get demotivated because of lack of trust in online payment systems (Campbell and Walker, 2010; Chen and Barnes, 2007). Some customers are stopped from making payments because of online verification systems of the service provider, which means that they are often driven away from shopping online. Even some banks stop consumers from paying large amounts of money to online service providers, mostly to avoid fraud and theft. When respondents were asked about the paying barrier on online services, most respondents stated that they do not face any complexity when paying for online services. On the other hand, 21.8% (16.8% agree and 5% strongly agree) of respondents confirmed that they often face complexity when making online payments (table 5.17).

Table 5:17 There is complexity associated with the online payment system

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	98	26.8	32.3	32.3
	Disagree	90	24.7	29.7	62.0
	Neutral	49	13.4	16.2	78.2
	Agree	51	14.0	16.8	95.0
	Strongly Agree	15	4.1	5.0	100.0
	Total	303	83.0	100.0	
Missing	System	62	17.0		
Total		365	100.0		

5.2 CORRELATION AND CROSSTABULATION

Saunders et al (2016) defined that correlation is used to describe the relationship of two variables and Malhotra (2007) stated that crosstabulation is used to describe when there are two or more variables and the links between the variables need to be found. Correlation and crosstabulation of the variables showed in this section.

5.2.1 Online shopping, browsing the internet, and language barrier by gender

There is a relation between browsing the internet and doing online shopping. Table 5.18 shows that the correlation r is .488, which means there is a moderately positive correlation (correlation result is -1 to +1, table 4.10) between browsing the internet and doing online shopping. Therefore, online shopping and browsing internet are related but not too strong.

There is also a question to be asked about the language barrier when doing online shopping. Majority of the respondents indicated that the language barrier does not make a difference in whether they do online shopping (65.48%, table 5.19). This is because majority of the respondents in this study are student and educated. On the other hand, 34.52% of the respondents stated that language barrier in somewhat affect their online shopping behaviour. The percentages of whether or not respondents felt they were affected by the language barrier are occasionally (17.10%), many times (10.33%) and very often (4.84%) (table 5.19).

Table 5:18 Correlation between online shopping, internet browsing and language

		Correlations		
		Doing online shopping	Browsing Internet	Language barrier stop to do online shopping
Doing online shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.488**	-.117*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.039
	N	360	359	310
Browsing Internet	Pearson Correlation	.488**	1	-.318**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	359	364	309
Language barrier stop to do online shopping	Pearson Correlation	-.117*	-.318**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.039	.000	
	N	310	309	310

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 5:19 Gender of the respondents * Language barrier stop to do online shopping Crosstabulation

Count		Language barrier stop to do online shopping				
		Never	Occasionally	Fairly many times	Very often	Always
Gender of the respondents	Male	113	34	18	9	3
	Female	90	19	14	6	4
Total		203 (65.48%)	53 (17.1%)	32 (10.32%)	15 (4.84%)	7 (2.26%)

Table 5.20 shows the correlation of online shopping by gender. The result indicates there is a large positive correlation of browsing the internet and online shopping by gender (r is .759 for male and .688 for female). However, the result shows that the correlation is a little bit higher for the male respondents than female respondents. This is because the study has a higher response rate of male respondents than female respondents. On the other hand, figure 5.2

indicate browsing the internet and gender relation. The crosstabulation bar chart shows that 78 male respondents (21.43%) always browse the internet comparing to 51 female respondents (14.01%). Male and female respondents are the same in percentage of those who don't browse the internet (2.47%). However, the cluster bar chart suggests that there are younger people doing online shopping (figure 5.3). This is because 43% of people from Asian ethnic groups and 45% from other ethnic groups are aged 20-39 years old (Office for National Statistics, 2018). Foxall (2017) stated young are more technology friendly. From the crosstabulation it is clear that different age range populations have respondents on different scales (table 5.21). Furthermore, as detailed above this study has more student respondent and they are mainly young.

Table 5:20 Correlation by gender

Gender of the respondents		Correlations			
		Online shopping	Browsing Internet	Age of the respondents	
Male	Online shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.759**	-.373**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
		N	208	207	208
	Browsing Internet	Pearson Correlation	.759**	1	-.411**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
		N	207	207	207
	Age of the respondents	Pearson Correlation	-.373**	-.411**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
		N	208	207	208
Female	Online shopping	Pearson Correlation	1	.688**	-.322**
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
		N	157	157	157
	Browsing Internet	Pearson Correlation	.688**	1	-.299**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
		N	157	157	157
	Age of the respondents	Pearson Correlation	-.322**	-.299**	1
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
		N	157	157	157

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5:2 Percentage of gender and browsing internet

Figure 5:3 Bar chart between browsing internet and age of the respondents

Table 5:21 Age of the respondents and online grocery shopping

Age of the respondents	Never	Occasionally	Fairly many times	Very often	Always
18-25	2	16	12	14	4
26-35	6	29	27	22	27
36-45	11	24	17	18	12
46-55	15	23	13	6	8
56-65	13	12	4	3	0
66+	8	5	3	4	2
Total	55	109	76	67	53

5.3 INFERENCE STATISTICS

5.3.1 Reliability statistics

Reliability is essential in ensuring the consistency of the research. Pallant (2016) uses the reliability scale to indicate how free the data is from random error. Reliability depends on sample size. There are two types of reliability test:

1. Test-retest reliability
2. Internal consistency

In this research, internal consistency has been checked. Internal consistency is used to show the items in one scale measure the same attributes as the other scale. To measure internal consistency, the most used method is the ‘Cronbach’s coefficient alpha’ method. If there is a small number of items (fewer than 7) in the scale Cronbach’s alpha could be smaller. When

the Cronbach's alpha is smaller it might show a correlation between items. It is suggested that inter-item correlations range from .2 to .4 (Lehman et al., 2013). The Cronbach alpha score ranges from (0) to (1). If the score comes in at (0) it means the result is unreliable and (1) means the result is completely reliable. Cronbach alpha scores less than .6 are considered poor and above .8 are considered very good.

Table 5:22 Reliability Statistics

Variables name	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Online Shopping	.542	.563	6
Consumer Attitudes	.689	.692	4
Consumer Intentions	.574	.560	5
Online Grocery	.711	.711	6
Consumer Culture	.698	.697	5
Trust	.409	.449	7
Satisfaction	.584	.609	5
Web selection	.431	.584	5
Technology use	.358	.369	4
Total	.747	.760	47 (9)

For this research, the researcher calculated that the average Cronbach alpha for all variables together is .747 (table 5.22) which suggests that there is a great deal of consistency between the variables in this research. However, individually some variables have a lower score. The variable from 'technology use' Cronbach alpha score is .358 which is much lower than .7 and there are 4 items in that scale. The fact that there are 4 variables means that the reliability is expected to be a little lower. If the number of items increases, the expected result might increase to a higher score. Web selection, trust, and satisfaction also have a lower score than .7 because there are fewer items in the scale. Having an item score of less than .3 means that the results differ from what the researcher tried to measure. There are no variables with a score less than .3 in this research. When checking the correlation between inter items it is essential to check that all values are positive. If there are any negative items, it means that the item is not counting the same things. From the inter-item correlation matrix 'online payment system' in table 5.23 is negatively correlated. If this item is deleted the Cronbach alpha will be higher (table 5.24).

Table 5:23 Inter-Item Correlation Matrix

	Familiarity to use a new technology	Using mobile app system	Online payment system	Gathering information about a product
Familiarity to use a new technology	1.000	.183	-.013	.244
Using mobile app system	.183	1.000	.080	.217
Online payment system	-.013	.080	1.000	.054
Gathering information about a product	.244	.217	.054	1.000

Table 5:24 Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Deleted	Scale Variance if Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Deleted
Familiarity to use a new technology	9.0199	5.196	.208	.079	.280
Using mobile app system	9.7583	4.224	.248	.070	.220
Online payment system	10.4305	5.309	.063	.009	.442
Gathering information about a product	9.0364	4.846	.268	.092	.214

5.3.2 Normality test

Normality tests are used to check whether the data is distributed normally or not. In statistics, normality is described as when a bell-shaped curve comes from the data (Pallant, 2016). A normality test is a graphical presentation of the normality. Two main tests are used for calculating normality (Sprinthall, 2014). These are:

1. Kolmogorov-Smirnov
2. Shapiro-Wilk

The **Kolmogorov-Smirnov** test is used to compare a sample with reference to probability distribution or to compare two samples.

On the other hand, the **Shapiro-Wilk test** rejects the hypothesis of normality if p value is less than or equal to 0.05. The normal confidence level for the test is 95%. Pallant (2016) stated that a normality test can be checked by skewness and kurtosis values. If Kolmogorov-Smirnov sig. value is more than .05 this is called normality. However, for larger samples the sig. value is .000 which is quite common. For this research, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov value is mostly .000 which is approximately normal (table 5.25). From the Normal Q-Q plot it is indicated that most of the value should be on the straight line. For this study, most of the values are on the straight line. In that case, it is generally assumed that the data is approximately normal.

On the other hand, data normality can be checked by **skewness and kurtosis** value. Pallant (2016) defined “the **skewness** value provides an indication of the symmetry of the distribution and **kurtosis** provides information about the ‘peakedness’ of the distribution” (p,57).

Groeneveld and Meeden (1984) showed that the skewness and kurtosis z value are between ‘-1.96 to +1.96’. The z value is calculated by dividing ‘statistic’ value and ‘std. error’ value (statistic/std. error=z value). For this study, z value for skewness and kurtosis are mostly between the range of ‘-1.96 to +1.96’ (table 5.26). So, the result should show that the data is mostly normally distributed. Details of the graphical presentation highlighted in figure 5.4.

Table 5:25 Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Online shopping	.081	303	.000	.987	303	.008
Consumer attitudes	.118	303	.000	.969	303	.000
Intension	.076	303	.000	.987	303	.009
Online grocery	.072	303	.001	.983	303	.001
Consumer culture	.099	303	.000	.982	303	.001
Trust	.105	303	.000	.945	303	.000
Satisfaction	.088	303	.000	.983	303	.001
Web selection	.117	303	.000	.721	303	.000
Technology use	.114	303	.000	.981	303	.000

Table 5:26 Skewness and Kurtosis value

	Skewness			Kurtosis		
	statistic	Std. error	Z Value	statistic	Std. error	Z Value
Online shopping	0.151	0.14	1.07857143	-0.277	0.279	-0.9928315
Consumer attitudes	-0.477	0.14	-3.4071429	0.102	0.279	0.3655914
Intension	0.069	0.14	0.49285714	-0.395	0.279	-1.4157706
Online grocery	-0.022	0.14	-0.1571429	0.512	0.279	1.83512545
Consumer culture	-0.289	0.14	-2.0642857	0.323	0.279	1.15770609
Trust	0.755	0.14	5.39285714	5.012	0.279	17.9641577
Satisfaction	-0.26	0.14	-1.8571429	-0.026	0.279	-0.09319
Web selection	4.912	0.14	35.0857143	57.389	0.279	205.695341
Technology use	0.19	0.14	1.35714286	0.063	0.279	0.22580645

Skewness and Normal Q-Q plot: if one tail in a normality distribution graph is longer than another it is known as skewness. A normal distribution graph is sometimes called symmetric distribution.

Left skewed distribution: when a distribution leans left it is called a left skewed distribution. This distribution is also called a negatively skewed distribution because it has long tail in the negative direction on the number line. In this study distribution, the mean is left of the peak.

Right skewed distribution: when a distribution has a right long tail, it is called right skewed distribution. This distribution is also called positively skewed distribution because it has long tail in the positive direction on the number line. Here, mean is to the right of the peak.

Normal Q-Q plot: Normal Q-Q plot is a graphical line (scatterplot) which helps to understand data normality. There are two sets of values in Normal Q-Q plot. Observed values and expected normal values. If both values form roughly straight line the data is normally distributed.

Figure 5:4 Graphical presentation of normality distribution

When checking normality for online shopping is seems approximately normally distributed. Mean for online shopping is 3.22 and standard deviation is .533. Normal Q-Q plot indicates a straight line.

Consumer attitudes is little bit left skewed or negative skewness where mean is 3.78 and standard deviation is .655. Normal Q-Q plot is about to fall in a straight line.

When checking on consumer intentions towards online shopping it is a little left skewed. From 303 respondents mean is 3.47 and standard deviation is .665. Normal Q-Q plot indicates a straight line.

In terms of online groceries, the graphs show it is normally distributed. Online grocery mean is 2.82 and standard deviation .733. Normal Q-Q plot indicates a straight line for the scatterplot.

Consumer culture is slightly left skewed, the mean is 3.26 and standard deviation is .733. Normal Q-Q plot shows all the dots go upward in a straight line.

Consumer trust in online shopping is right skewed, the mean is 3.24 and standard deviation is .536. Normal Q-Q plot shows all the dots go upward in a straight line.

Consumer satisfaction in online shopping is slightly left skewed, the mean is 3.76 and standard deviation is .536. Normal Q-Q plot shows all the dots go upward in a straight line.

Consumer web selection in online shopping is right skewed which mean is 3.24 and standard deviation is .536. Normal Q-Q plot shows all the dots is upward in a straight line.

Technology use of online shopping is approximately symmetric, the mean is 3.19 and standard deviation is .671. Normal Q-Q plot shows all the dots go upward in a straight line.

5.3.3 Regression analysis

Regression analysis is a statistical tool which shows the relationship between variables (Sprinthall, 2014, Pallant, 2016). The relations happen between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables. Regression analysis helps to understand how a dependent variable change when one independent variable varies. In research normally two types of regression used. These are:

1. **Simple regression** (when there is a visible relationship between one independent variable and one dependent variable). The simple regression equation is $y=a+bx$
2. **Multiple regression** (when there is a relationship between one independent variable and several dependent variables.) The multiple regression equation is

$$Y=a+b_1x_1+b_2x_2+b_3x_3+\dots+b_nx_n+\varepsilon$$

Where:

- y =dependent variable
- a =the Y-intercept when all x value is zero
- b =the coefficients assigned to each of the independent variables during regression
- x =different independent variable
- ε =error term

This study aims to analyse and test the hypothesis and decide whether it should be accepted or rejected. There are four models created for this study.

$$\text{Model 1: OLS}=\alpha + \beta_1(ATT) + \beta_2(INTS) + \beta_3(CONC) + C$$

$$\text{Model 2: OLS}=\alpha + \beta_1(TST) + \beta_2(SAT) + \beta_3(WEB) + \beta_4(TECH) + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Model 3: OLS}=\alpha + \beta_1(ONLG) + \varepsilon$$

$$\text{Model 4: OLS}=\alpha + \beta_1(DEMO) + \varepsilon$$

Where:

OLS=online shopping

ATT= Consumer attitudes

INTS=Consumer intension

CONC=Consumer culture

TST=Consumer trust in online

SAT=Consumer satisfaction

WEB=Web selection

TECH=Technology use

ONLG=Online grocery shopping

DEMO=Demographic information

5.3.3.1 Multiple regression analysis

For this study, the researcher has used multiple regression analysis. Details of the results and the interpretations of the results are presented in this chapter.

5.3.3.2 Correlation and Multicollinearity

The first step for multiple regression analysis is to check for multiple correlations between variables. The correlation table insinuates that there are some links between the independent variable and the dependent variables (the preferable relationship is .3 or above). Table 5.27 shows that consumer attitudes and intention have a correlation with online shopping above .3 which are .554 and .507 respectively. So, assumptions can be made that positive attitudes and intention lead a consumer to buy online.

Table 5.30 shows the coefficient of the variables. The column Tolerance and VIF indicates multicollinearity. Pallant (2016) states that tolerance is an indicator of how much of the variability affects a specific independent variable. Tolerance is calculated by 1-R squared value. If the Tolerance value is less than .10 it means that the chance of multiple correlations is very high. But in this research, all the variables have a Tolerance above .10, which means there is no multicollinearity.

Variance Inflating Factor (VIF) indicates how much variability there is. If the VIF value is above 10 it indicates multicollinearity. For this study, all values are less than 10 which means there is no multicollinearity (table 5.30).

Table 5:27 Correlations between online shopping, attitudes, intentions and culture

		Online shopping	Consumer attitudes	Intentions	Consumer culture
Pearson Correlation	Online shopping	1.000	.553	.503	.003
	Consumer attitudes	.553	1.000	.605	.089
	Intentions	.503	.605	1.000	.008
	Consumer culture	.003	.089	.008	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	Online shopping	.	.000	.000	.482
	Consumer attitudes	.000	.	.000	.060
	Intentions	.000	.000	.	.442
	Consumer culture	.482	.060	.442	.
N	Online shopping	305	305	305	305
	Consumer attitudes	305	305	305	305
	Intentions	305	305	305	305
	Consumer culture	305	305	305	305

5.3.3.3 Outliers, normality, linearity, homoscedasticity, and independence of residuals

By checking the normality probability plot or P-P Plot of standardised residuals and checking the scatterplot of the assumption of Outliers, the normality, linearity and independence of residuals could be found. Pallant (2016) described that the residual scatterplot allows to check the following:

- **Normality:** the residuals value should be normally distributed about the predicted dependent variable score.
- **Linearity:** it should have a straight-line relationship with the predicted dependent variable score.
- **Homoscedasticity:** residual variance of the predicted dependent variable scores should be the same for all predicted scores.

Pallant (2016) stated that normal P-P plots should stay in a straight diagonal line from bottom left to the top right. If the plot is a straight diagonal line it means that there is no deviation from normality. This study figure 5.5 shows a straight line which indicates a normal P-P plot. So, in this study, the data is distributed normally.

Pallant (2016) also highlighted that the scatterplot of the standardised residual should stay roughly in a rectangular line and most of the values should be centred to zero. The scatter plot is shown in figure 5.6 indicates a straight line from bottom left to top right. In the scatter diagram all the dots are approximately rectangular and most of the dots are around the '0' point.

Figure 5:5 Normal P-P Plot of Regression standardized residual

Figure 5:6 scatterplot of online shopping, attitudes, intentions and culture

5.3.3.4 Model 1 Evaluation

To be able to calculate the model evaluation it is necessary to know the R Square value. The R Square value highlights the differing values of the dependent variable. An R Square value that is close to +1 is known as a very strong positive relationship. An R Square value that is close to -1 has a very strong negative relationship. Table 5.28 has an R Square value of .352 which means that there is a 35% variance in the dependent variables. Value R is .593 which means that there is a positive relationship among the variables.

Statistical significance must also be checked. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is used to find the difference between group means and it is used to compare three or more group means. This study's first model F value is 54.514 (table 5.29) and its first p-value is .000. Pallant (2016) stated if the significant value of p is less than .0005 then the value has reached statistical significance. For this study, the value is less than .0005. So, the study first model has reached statistical significance.

The Model summary table informs the researcher about the variance in the dependent variables. For this research, the Model summary table (5.28) of the R Square value is .352. This means the percentage is 35.2%. Here, online grocery shopping has a 35.2% variance and therefore is acceptable because online shopping is a large sector. This study only focused on the grocery sector. If the research was undertaken for a variety of sectors the results may have been more accurate.

Table 5:28 Model Summary of online shopping, attitudes, intentions and culture

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.593 ^a	.352	.346	.42993

a. Predictors: (Constant), consumer, culture, Intentions, Consumer attitudes

b. Dependent Variable: online shopping

Table 5:29 ANOVA of online shopping, attitudes, intentions and culture

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	30.229	3	10.076	54.514	.000 ^b
	Residual	55.636	301	.185		
	Total	85.864	304			

a. Dependent Variable: online shopping

b. Predictors: (Constant), consumer, culture, Intentions, Consumer attitudes

5.3.3.5 Evaluating each of the independent variables

This section aims to discover which of the independent variables is a predictor for the dependent variable. To check this, it is important to look at the Beta under standardized coefficients. It is also important to draw a regression equation to check for unstandardized coefficient values listed as B. Table 5.30 indicates that the Beta's highest value is .397 which means that this variable has the strongest unique contribution in explaining the dependent variables. The lower Beta value .263 indicates that it has the lowest contribution. Same as, the sig. value column indicates that the intentions and consumer cultures are making a contribution towards online shopping.

The part correlation co-efficient value is .215 (consumer attitudes) multiplied by .215 (squaring the value with the same value) gives the researcher the value .04. This means that this value has 5 percent of the variation with the dependent variable (Pallant, 2016). This is the same as the consumer culture value which has .1 percent variance with the dependent variable.

Table 5.30 states that the Beta value constant is 1.358. It means that if consumer attitudes, intentions, and consumer culture stay at 'zero' online shopping will remain at 1.358. The highest Beta value after online shopping under the unstandardized co-efficient is .322 which indicates that by changing the consumer attitudes 1 will cause 1.358+.322 changes in online shopping. The p-value of consumer attitudes is 0.000 which shows a significant effect on online shopping. Therefore, is it clear that the Hypothesis (H2) is supported. The consumer culture category is also supported (H8). Same as intentions have a contribution to online shopping (p-value is smaller than the statistical significance level >0.05). Therefore, this Hypothesis (H3) also supported. The findings suggest that consumer attitudes, intentions and culture have a significant effect on online grocery shopping. Therefore, the model can be framed as:

$$\text{Online Shopping} = 1.358 + .322 (\text{ATT}) + .208 (\text{INTS}) + (0.024) (\text{CONC}) + \dots$$

Table 5:30 Coefficients online shopping, attitudes, intentions, and culture

Model 1	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.358	.179		7.579	.000	1.005	1.710					
Consumer attitudes	.322	.047	.397	6.783	.000	.229	.415	.553	.364	.315	.627	1.594
Intentions	.208	.046	.263	4.510	.000	.118	.299	.503	.252	.209	.632	1.581
Consumer culture	.024	.031	.352	2.752	.000	.085	.038	.003	.043	.035	.989	1.011

Dependent Variable: online shopping

Table 5:31 Case wise Diagnostics of online shopping, attitudes, intentions, and culture

Case Number	Std. Residual	Online shopping	Predicted Value	Residual
72	-3.445	1.83	3.3144	-1.48106

Dependent Variable: online shopping

The case wise diagnostics table standardised residual value should be above .3 or below -.3. For this study, the value is -3.445 (table 5.31) which is normal for this research. It is generally believed that 1 percent of the value can go to the outside of the range. On the other hand, the predicted value to show the relationship between online shopping and other variables is 3.3144. The study shows the relationship is 1.83. So, the researcher can assume that the prediction is roughly 55% accurate.

To check influence on the result Cook's distance is given. If the cook distance is larger than 1, there is a problem. For this study, the maximum value of Cook's distance is .046 (table 5.32). So, this suggests that there is no major problem in this research.

In Model 1 of this study, there are 3 independent variables. To check the Mahal. Distance, checking the critical value is important. Tabachnick and Fidell (2013) stated that if there are 3 independent variables the critical values for evaluating the Mahalnobis distance should not exceed 16.27. In this study, table 5.32 confirmed that the Mahal. Distance is 15.780 which suggests that it's not exceeding critical value.

Table 5:32 Residuals Statistics of online shopping, attitudes, intentions and culture

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.0706	3.8979	3.2222	.31533	305
Std. Predicted Value	-3.652	2.143	.000	1.000	305
Standard Error of Predicted Value	.025	.101	.047	.014	305
Adjusted Predicted Value	2.0649	3.9073	3.2216	.31540	305
Residual	-1.48106	1.24554	.00000	.42780	305
Std. Residual	-3.445	2.897	.000	.995	305
Stud. Residual	-3.458	2.913	.001	1.001	305
Deleted Residual	-1.49221	1.25936	.00055	.43327	305
Stud. Deleted Residual	-3.523	2.950	.001	1.005	305
Mahal. Distance	.020	15.780	2.990	2.544	305
Cook's Distance	.000	.046	.003	.005	305
Centred Leverage Value	.000	.052	.010	.008	305

Dependent Variable: online shopping

Figure 5:7 Regression standardized residual of online shopping, attitudes, intentions, and culture

This is the same for the second model, table 5.33 highlighted that the consumer trust in online shopping Tolerance value is .806 which is higher than .10 and VIF value $1.240 < 10$. It does mean that there is no multicollinearity. The Tolerance and VIF value for all other factors in this model are under the boundary. Therefore, there is no multicollinearity in this model. Significance value p is less than .005 for the variable's satisfaction and web selection but higher for the variable's Trust (H4) and technology (H9). Thus, ethnic consumer satisfaction (H5) and web selection (H6) with online shopping have been supported. The model can be formed as below:

Model 2: online shopping = 2.049 - .047(TST) + .205 (SAT) + .113(web) - .033(TECH) + ...

Table 5:33 Coefficient of online shopping, trust, satisfaction, web selection, and technology

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
2	(Constant)	2.049	.229		8.959	.000	1.599	2.499					
	Trust	.047	.055	.053	.860	.391	-.061	.156	.167	.050	.048	.806	1.240
	Satisfaction	.205	.060	.216	3.419	.000	.087	.322	.277	.194	.189	.764	1.309
	Web selection	.113	.032	.197	3.495	.000	.049	.115	.197	.064	.061	.714	1.400
	Technology	.033	.050	.041	.656	.513	-.065	.130	.152	.038	.036	.784	1.276

a. Dependent Variable: online shopping

Model 3: online shopping = 2.923 + .106 (ONLG) + ...

In terms of online grocery shopping, the Tolerance value is $1 > .1$ and the VIF value is $1 < 10$ (table 5.34). Hence, there is no multicollinearity. The significance value for online grocery shopping is less than .005. Therefore, the hypothesis (H7) is supported. It does mean that

perceived risk will have a negative influence on the ethnic consumer online grocery buying decision.

Table 5:34 Coefficient of online shopping and online groceries

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Zero-order	Correlations		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
3	(Constant)	2.923	.120		24.339	.000	2.687	3.160				
	Online groceries	.106	.041	.146	2.582	.000	.025	.188	.146	.146	.146	1.000 1.000

Dependent Variable: online shopping

Model 4: online shopping = 2.440 + .112 (Age) - 0.22 (Education) + ...-Gender

Literature in this study proved demographic characteristics influence the ethnic consumer’s online buying decision. Table 5.35 indicates Tolerance value for age is .968>.1 and VIF value 1.033<10. Hence, there is no multicollinearity. Same as for the education of the respondents there is no multicollinearity. Sig. value for age is less than .005. So, the hypothesis (H1b) is supported. On the other hand, Sig. value for education is greater than .005. Therefore, this hypothesis (H1c) is not supported.

The researcher undertook an Independent Sample T-test for online grocery shopping. The results show there is no significant difference between male and female consumers in the case of doing online grocery shopping. Pallant (2016) stated that if Sig. (2-tailed) is less than or equal to .05 there is a significant difference. And if the value is above .05, there is no significant difference. Table 5.36 shows the value sig. (2-tailed) is above .05. Thus, there is no significant difference between ethnic gender perspectives. Therefore, hypothesis (H1a) is not supported.

Table 5:35 Coefficient of online grocery shopping and demographic information

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Zero-order	Correlations		Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound		Partia 1	Part	Tolerance	VIF
4	(Constant)	2.440	.123		19.898	.000	2.199	2.681				
	Age of the respondents	.112	.032	.202	3.533	.000	.050	.175	.209	.199	.198	.968 1.033
	Education of the respondents	.022	.029	.043	.758	.449	-.035	.079	.079	.044	.043	.968 1.033

a. Dependent Variable: online grocery

Table 5:36 Independent Samples Test of online groceries

		Group Statistics				
Gender of the respondents		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	
Online groceries	Male	174	2.7958	.71961	.05455	
	Female	132	2.8542	.74746	.06506	

		Independent Samples Test								
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances			t-test for Equality of Means					
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Online groceries	Equal variances assumed	1.031	.311	-.691	304	.490	-.05838	.08446	-.22458	.10782
	Equal variances not assumed			-.688	276.481	.492	-.05838	.08490	-.22552	.10876

5.3.4 ANOVA Analysis of the Ethnicity and Gender

Descriptive statistics of ethnicity and gender are shown in table 5.37. Levene’s test (table 5.38) provides a test of one of the assumptions underlying analysis of variance for two or more groups. The important value is the Sig. level. If the Sig. value is less than .05 it suggests that the variance of the independent variable across the group is not equal. In this study Sig. value is greater than .05. Therefore, there is no violation of the homogeneity of variance assumption.

Table 5:37 Descriptive statistics of ethnicity and gender

Dependent Variable: online grocery shopping

Gender of the respondents	The ethnicity of the respondents	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Male	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	3.0552	.78147	93
	Indian/British Indian	2.7933	.85158	25
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	2.9023	.79871	29
	Chinese/British Chinese	2.9792	1.01746	8
	Other Asian	3.1528	.72551	24
	African/Black African	3.0873	.55682	21
	Other	3.1042	.46237	8
	Total	3.0159	.76419	208
Female	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	2.9463	.89437	36
	Indian/British Indian	2.7275	.89633	23
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	3.0833	.73050	20
	Chinese/British Chinese	3.2500	.53403	16
	Other Asian	2.8864	.72810	22
	African/Black African	2.8768	.59079	23
	Other	3.1863	.57095	17
	Total	2.9701	.75169	157
Total	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	3.0248	.81244	129
	Indian/British Indian	2.7618	.86456	48
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	2.9762	.76905	49
	Chinese/British Chinese	3.1597	.71977	24
	Other Asian	3.0254	.73111	46
	African/Black African	2.9773	.57801	44
	Other	3.1600	.53029	25
	Total	2.9962	.75814	365

Table 5:38 Levene's Test of Equality of Error Variances

		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
Online shopping	Based on Mean	1.308	13	351	.206
	Based on Median	1.189	13	351	.285
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	1.189	13	318.605	.286
	Based on trimmed mean	1.292	13	351	.215

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups.

a. Dependent variable: online shopping

b. Design: Intercept + Gender + nationality + Gender * nationality

The next step is to check the possibility of an interaction effect between gender and nationality (Gender*nationality). If the Sig. is less than or equal to .05, there is a significant interaction effect. However, in this study the interaction effect is not significant (Gender*nationality: Sig. = .706) (Table 5.39). This indicates that there is no significant difference in the effect of nationality and gender. To check the main effect of each of the independent variables the Sig. level of Gender and Nationality has been checked separately. Significant value for Gender and

Nationality is greater than .05. Therefore, there are no significant main effects on the relation between gender and nationality.

The effect size for the nationality variable is provided in the column labelled Partial Eta Squared (.017) (table 5.39). Using Cohen’s (2013) classification criterion, this can be classified as small. So, this effect reaches statistical significance, but the actual difference in the mean values is very small.

Table 5:39 Test of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: online grocery shopping

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	6.606 ^a	13	.508	.880	.574	.032
Intercept	2336.660	1	2336.660	4047.910	.000	.920
Gender	.018	1	.018	.032	.859	.000
Nationality	3.414	6	.569	.986	.435	.017
Gender * nationality	2.181	6	.364	.630	.706	.011
Error	202.615	351	.577			
Total	3485.827	365				
Corrected Total	209.221	364				

a. R Squared = .032 (Adjusted R Squared = -.004)

To check if there is any significant difference among the different nationality, a post-hoc test was conducted in this study. These tests systematically compare each group of nationality and indicate whether there is a significant difference in the means of each. For the post-hoc test, this study has provided multiple comparisons (table 5.40). This study focused on the Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test, as this is one of the more commonly used tests. If the multiple comparisons Sig. value is less than .05 this indicates that there is a statistically significant difference, these means the is no group means are equal. From this study, there is no value of less than .05. Therefore, the study can conclude that group means are equal across different ethnicities. The relationship between gender and ethnicities is also shown in figure 5.8.

Figure 5:8 Estimated marginal values of online shopping

Table 5:40 Multiple comparisons of the ethnicity of the respondents

Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: online shopping

Tukey HSD

(I) Ethnicity of the respondents

(I) Ethnicity of the respondents	(J) Ethnicity of the respondents	Mean			95% Confidence Interval	
		Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	Indian/British Indian	.2630	.12846	.387	-.1179	.6439
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	.0486	.12750	1.000	-.3295	.4267
	Chinese/British Chinese	-.1349	.16890	.985	-.6358	.3660
	Other Asian	-.0006	.13048	1.000	-.3875	.3864
	African/Black African	.0475	.13264	1.000	-.3458	.4409
	Other	-.1352	.16603	.983	-.6276	.3572
Indian/British Indian	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	-.2630	.12846	.387	-.6439	.1179
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	-.2144	.15429	.807	-.6719	.2432
	Chinese/British Chinese	-.3979	.18994	.358	-.9612	.1654
	Other Asian	-.2636	.15676	.629	-.7284	.2013
	African/Black African	-.2155	.15857	.823	-.6857	.2548
	Other	-.3982	.18739	.340	-.9539	.1575
Pakistani/British Pakistani	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	-.0486	.12750	1.000	-.4267	.3295
	Indian/British Indian	.2144	.15429	.807	-.2432	.6719
	Chinese/British Chinese	-.1835	.18930	.960	-.7449	.3778
	Other Asian	-.0492	.15598	1.000	-.5117	.4134
	African/Black African	-.0011	.15780	1.000	-.4690	.4669
	Other	-.1838	.18674	.957	-.7376	.3700
Chinese/British Chinese	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	.1349	.16890	.985	-.3660	.6358
	Indian/British Indian	.3979	.18994	.358	-.1654	.9612
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	.1835	.18930	.960	-.3778	.7449
	Other Asian	.1344	.19131	.992	-.4330	.7017
	African/Black African	.1824	.19280	.965	-.3893	.7542
	Other	-.0003	.21712	1.000	-.6442	.6436
Other Asian	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	.0006	.13048	1.000	-.3864	.3875
	Indian/British Indian	.2636	.15676	.629	-.2013	.7284
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	.0492	.15598	1.000	-.4134	.5117
	Chinese/British Chinese	-.1344	.19131	.992	-.7017	.4330
	African/Black African	.0481	.16021	1.000	-.4270	.5232
	Other	-.1346	.18878	.992	-.6945	.4252
African/Black African	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	-.0475	.13264	1.000	-.4409	.3458
	Indian/British Indian	.2155	.15857	.823	-.2548	.6857
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	.0011	.15780	1.000	-.4669	.4690
	Chinese/British Chinese	-.1824	.19280	.965	-.7542	.3893
	Other Asian	-.0481	.16021	1.000	-.5232	.4270
	Other	-.1827	.19029	.962	-.7470	.3816
Other	Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi	.1352	.16603	.983	-.3572	.6276
	Indian/British Indian	.3982	.18739	.340	-.1575	.9539
	Pakistani/British Pakistani	.1838	.18674	.957	-.3700	.7376
	Chinese/British Chinese	.0003	.21712	1.000	-.6436	.6442
	Other Asian	.1346	.18878	.992	-.4252	.6945
	African/Black African	.1827	.19029	.962	-.3816	.7470

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square (Error) = .577.

5.3.5 Hypothesis outcomes

This section explains the outcomes of the hypothesis in details. Summary of the hypothesis and result are shown in table 5.41.

Table 5:41 Summary of the Hypothesis testing results and literature

No.	Hypothesis	Results	Literature
H1a	H1a: There is a significant difference between the male and female in the factor influencing for online grocery shopping.	Not Supported	Wu (2003); Reynolds and Olson (2013); Foxall (2017); Anesbury et al. (2016); Harris et al. (2017); Freeman (2009); Hansen (2008); Kragh (1996)
H1b	H1b: There is a significant difference between the age group of people and factors influencing for online grocery shopping.	Supported	
H1c	H1c: Those with a higher level of education will have a higher online buying intention than those with a lower level of education.	Not Supported	
H2	Positive attitudes towards online grocery shopping are presumed to be positively related to purchase decision making among ethnic consumers.	Supported	Wang et al. (2016); Wessels and Drennan (2010); Wu (2003); Yavas (2001); Liu et al. (2013)
H3	There is a positive correlation between consumer attitude to a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase for the ethnic consumer.	Supported	Shim and Drake (1990); Weber and Roehl (1999); Liang and Huang (1998)
H4	Ethnic consumers' trust significantly predicts online grocery shopping intentions.	Not Supported	Zaltman and Moorman (1998); Campbell and Walker (2010); Chen and Barnes (2007); Salo and Karjaluoto (2007). Liu et al. (2013); Browaeys and Price (2015); Blomqvist et al. (2015)
H5	There is a positive significant relationship between ethnic consumer cultural satisfaction and online grocery shopping.	Supported	Shankar et al. (2002); Garbiano and Johnson (1999); Beverland and Farrelly (2010); Wu (2003); Omar et al. (2004); Ranaweera and Prabhu (2003)
H6	Websites that focus on ethnic cultural beliefs are proposed to have a positive impact on the likelihood of an ethnic consumer engaging in online shopping.	Supported	Singh et al. (2006); Browayes and Price (2015); Hong and Wyer (1989); Beverland and Farrelly (2010)
H7	Perceived risk assumed to have a negative impact on ethnic consumer online grocery purchase decision making.	Supported	Huang and Oppewal (2006); Miyazaki and Fernandez (2001); Hamlett et al., (2008); and Ayyub, (2015); Anesbury (2016)
H8	Ethnic consumer culture is expected to have a positive correlation with the promotional offer.	Supported	Guilherme and John (2015); Appiah (2004); Khairula et al. (1996); Nwankwo and Lindridge (2012); Katawetawarakas and Wang (2011)
H9	Ethnic consumers are expected to have difficulties in the ability to adapt with technology to do online shopping.	Not Supported	Maxwell (2012); Appiah (2004); Foxall (2017)

Hypothesis H1a: There is a significant difference between the male and female in the factor influencing for online grocery shopping. (Not supported)

Hypothesis H1b: There is a significant difference between the age group of people and factors influencing for online grocery shopping. (Supported)

Hypothesis H1c: Those with a higher level of education will have a higher online buying intention than those with a lower level of education. (Not Supported)

Hypothesis 1a is not supported by the survey and the research. The consumer demographic has a tangible effect on whether or not an online purchase decision is made (Wu, 2003; Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017; Liu et al., 2013). The previous researcher studied only on online shopping in general, but this study is based on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Thus, the findings of the study are different from the literature. ANOVA analysis and Independent sample T-test in this study proved there is no significant difference among ethnic gender in terms of online grocery shopping.

The occupation and income of the consumer also make a difference in the buying decision (Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017; Anesbury et al., 2016). This study did not discuss the income level of the respondents but have taken consideration of the secondary sources (section 3.2.1). Because, during the pilot questionnaire of this study, many respondents were not willing to answer this personal question (detailed in section 4.5.1.5). Therefore, it was removed from the questionnaire.

Hypothesis 1b is supported by the survey of this research. This study proved young people are more online grocery shopping oriented than older people (table 5.35, Sig. value is less than .005). This is also supported by the literature of this study (Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017). Hypothesis 1c is not supported in this study. The literature says high education led a consumer to higher online buying intentions. But in terms of ethnic consumer online grocery shopping, the hypothesis is not supported (table 5.35, Sig. value is greater than .005).

Hypothesis 2: Positive attitudes towards online grocery shopping are presumed to be positively related to purchase decision making among ethnic consumers. (Supported)

Hypothesis 2 is supported by the evidence found in the research. Consumer attitudes have a large influence on whether a purchase decision is made. These results are also supported by other researches. Wang et al. (2016) and Bianchi and Andrews (2012) indicated that having a good attitude is the main contributing factor behind making a purchase decision. They specified that the respondents currently purchasing their grocery online have positive attitudes about it.

Some consumers have the belief that online shopping costs more money than offline shopping. As a result, some consumers never try online shopping. Wu (2003) suggests that attitudes change based on a variety of factors. These factors are effectiveness and modernisation, purchase convenience, information abundance, multifunction and safety, quality, and the speed of delivery. The hypothesis is also supported by Yavas (2001). Yavas (2001) focused on price, which is an important factor in online buying decisions. The majority of the consumers in this study indicated that they do online shopping based on price, delivery time, and ease of shopping.

Liu et al. (2013) also support the hypothesis. They suggest that consumers are mainly influenced to do online shopping by the enjoyment and relaxation gained. Shopping in stores often involves a level of pressure on the consumer, whether that is from shop assistants or the fear of judgement from other shoppers. Online shopping has none of this pressure as the shopping can be done from the comfort of home. Participants were asked how they feel about online shopping, the convenience, delivery of the products, reliability of the products. The regression analysis in table 5.30 indicates that the Sig. value is .000 for the attitude's variable. Therefore, the study supports that ethnic consumers' positive attitudes towards online grocery shopping can lead them to purchase more.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive correlation between consumer attitude to a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase for the ethnic consumer. (Supported)

Hypothesis 3 has also been proven by this investigation (table 5.34). The consumer's attitude changes when a positive experience is a result of buying a product. Positive attitudes lead a consumer to buy a particular product. A positive previous experience leads to the intent to buy repeatedly (Shim & Drake, 1990). Weber and Roehl (1999) support Shim & Drake's argument. They demonstrated that there is a direct relationship between previous online shopping experience and online shopping intentions. Liang and Huang (1998) outlined that experience works as a mediator for online shopping intentions. Blomqvist et al. (2015) indicated experience changes consumer attitudes towards online grocery shopping. They stated if someone has bought grocery online is more likely to buy more. Because consumer in the online grocery sector can compare the price with the different supermarket to choose the cheapest product.

Consumer attitude creates a positive response towards a product and that attitudes lead to more consumers buying that product online. When an ethnic consumer has a positive mentality

towards a product it means they are more likely to buy that product. Muslim ethnic consumers often look for Halal products because of safety, religious value, health, and exclusivity (Amat et al., 2014). They specified that the advertising of Halal products changes Muslim consumers' attitudes to buy the products. Khairulla et al. (1996) define the term acculturation as when ethnic-cultural attitudes become diluted and mixed with the culture that they are living in. Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) describe that a person who was born and raised in the UK is extremely likely to be acculturated with British culture whereas an ethnic migrant is far less likely to be as acculturated. Highly acculturated consumers attitudes to a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase are different from less acculturate consumer. This study asked the respondents about accessing online shopping, time spends in the UK, returning online products and learning online shopping. Regression analysis (table 5.30) measured the intentions and the result shows that the Sig. value is .000. Hence, the study supports that there is a positive correlation between the consumer attitude towards a product and their subsequent likelihood of purchase, for ethnic consumers.

Hypothesis 4: Ethnic consumer trust significantly predicts online grocery shopping intentions. (Not supported)

Hypothesis 4 is not supported. The outcomes from the study showed that there is a lack of trust amongst ethnic consumers towards online grocery shopping. The P-value for the trust variable is greater than .005 (table 5.33) which means this hypothesis is not supported. Blomqvist et al. (2015) demonstrated a higher level of trust means a greater level of purchase intentions. Zaltman and Moorman (1998) stated that trust is built up from a repeated high standard of product or service. Campbell and Walker (2010) and Chen and Barnes (2007) suggest that to increase purchasing behaviour, building trust is important. Trust tends to increase with successive successful online purchases. Shankar et al. (2002) supported these arguments. They said that trust is important between different parties. A consumer buys a product when they think that their service provider is dependable (Salo & Karjaluoto, 2007).

Liu et al. (2013) described consumer demotivated to buy online grocery products if the perceived risk is high. Shopper build-up their trust against perceived risk during online grocery shopping. Trust is built up through a number of different mediums. Examples include word of mouth, good online experience when on the website, perceived risk, brand reputation, security, and quality of information. Chen and Barnes (2007) classified online and offline shopping. They explained that uncertainty, temporal, and impersonal problems are faced by the consumer when doing online shopping. These hinder consumers to build up trust with the online platform.

This study has measured consumer trust through a range of Likert scale statements. These include providing personal information, checking reviews and feedback, and making repeat purchases. This study has included a few statements to learn the ethnic consumer's views about online shopping. The majority of the respondents indicated that they do not feel safe enough to provide their personal information on websites (table 5.13). Most of the consumers check reviews and feedback before making any purchase decision. The majority of ethnic consumers do not like to provide their personal information on websites because of the lack of trust.

Hypothesis 5: There is a positive significant relationship between ethnic consumer cultural satisfaction and online grocery shopping. (Supported)

This study and literature in this study support the hypothesis. The P-value for the satisfaction variable is smaller than .005 (table 5.33) which means this hypothesis is supported. Ethnic consumers are mostly attracted to buy the products that contain the national image of their country (Maheswaran, 1994). Shankar et al. (2002) described that in order to satisfy an online consumer, it is necessary to make an alliance between two parties. If the two parties are satisfied with the services, they make repeat purchases. One factor that is necessary to satisfy consumers is that the product they purchase is of sufficient quality and related to their culture. Hong and Wyer (1990) discovered that consumer emotions and symbolic interactionism relates to products of the country of origin. To meet consumer cultural satisfaction, it is important to provide products from the ethnic minorities' countries of origin (Beverland and Farrelly, 2010). Ethnic consumers have an image of their nation which they reflect upon products from their country of origin. So, it is important to maintain the product quality as well as other related services.

Garbiano and Johnson (1999) suggest that consumer satisfaction can be classified in a number of different ways. Some consumers are casual online buyers (buy for enjoyment or special needs) and some are regular buyers (buy for regular needs). Some products have become part of the culture of particular countries and those products are almost always satisfying for customers of those countries to buy. Beverland and Farrelly (2010) outline in their theory that it is satisfying when a consumer buys a product of their country of origin. Wu (2003) suggests that purchasing decisions are strongly influenced by the cultural, social, personal, and psychological characteristics of an individual. Ranaweera and Prabhu (2003) claim that consumer satisfaction and trust in online services are positively related. When trust is built up, the loyalty level of customers increases. In order to increase trust levels from customers, companies need to build up satisfaction in their products. Omar et al. (2004) demonstrated that

ethnic consumer preferred to go to the shop where they believe to find products that fulfil their cultural satisfaction. They believed that quality, taste, and originality of a product can be found in their national products. This study found that the majority of ethnic consumers practice their own traditional culture (table 5.9). Similarly, 39% of the respondents specified that they found contradictions between the British lifestyle and the culture they practise (table 5.11). These above reasons are why consumer tend to buy products that fulfil their cultural satisfaction. Thus, the hypothesis is supported.

Hypothesis 6: Websites that focus on ethnic cultural beliefs are proposed to have a positive impact on the likelihood of an ethnic consumer engaging in online shopping. (supported)

Here the hypothesis has been proven. The P-value for this variable is smaller than .005 (table 5.33). This study found that websites that focus on ethnic cultural beliefs are more likely to encourage spending from ethnic people. The findings are also supported by Singh et al. (2006). They found that if any website valued local cultural beliefs, they tended to receive more business from ethnic peoples. Fujimoto et al. (2007) demonstrated maintaining cultural diversity is important by the emergence of new technology. Businesses that don't market towards ethnic consumers are likely missing out on a large share of the market. It is clear that more businesses should start to focus on advertising to ethnic peoples because ethnic consumers want to see that businesses focus on ethnic, cultural, and traditional beliefs when advertising.

Browaeys and Price (2015) suggest that some companies aim to focus on ethnic cultural needs. In cross-cultural management, companies want to handle their customers' needs and demands. Guerrier and Wilson (2011) demonstrated that diversity on the website is important to fulfil consumer satisfaction. Appiah (2004) suggested that ethnic groups tend to hold a set belief on language, religion, food, which products to use and media. Figures of the present study show that language accessibility helps ethnic consumers to browse and find the products that relate to their culture. More than 50% of the ethnic consumers (60.6%) indicated that they find it's easy when websites have language accessibility. It helps them to find a product and read its description. A small number of the respondents disagreed and 14.8% of the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed (table 5.15). Therefore, the study supports the hypothesis.

Hypothesis 7: Perceived risk assumed to have a negative impact on ethnic consumer online grocery purchase decision making. (Supported)

The study supports this hypothesis (table 5.34, Sig value is smaller than .005). The findings are also supported by many researchers. Harris et al. (2017) stated security of transaction and privacy, perceived complexity, unavailability to judge the products quality, postage and packing, sometimes some good offer to receive from the store, and lack of social contract are the main factor for online grocery shopping. Bianchi and Andrews (2012) indicated this risk (perceived risk) is identified as an inhibitor to online shopping, regardless of advance in technology and the increasing skill and competence of consumers on the internet. Mortimer et al. (2016) demonstrated during the online shopping process for food and groceries, some customers may experience some negative affect such as disappointment, displeasure, anxiety, sadness, frustration or anger over the transaction, which increase their perception of risk resulted reduces their intentions to repurchase from the online grocery retailer. Hensen (2008) found that consumers are more concerned about damaged items and cold and frozen items. Huang and Oppewal (2006) explained delivery charges have an impact on consumer buying decisions. This statement is also supported by Miyazaki and Fernandez (2001); Hamlett et al. (2008); and Ayyub, (2015). Anesbury et al. (2016) outline that selecting and choosing a grocery brand is easy. They also explained grocery product shopping depends on product comparisons. Returning any items is a hassle if the items are not of the right standard.

The ethnic population in the UK is less likely to buy groceries online. The present study demonstrated that 16.5% of ethnic consumers in the UK buy products online whereas 66.2% stated they do not buy online (table 5.7). Delivery charges, product delivery time, quality of the products, substitute items, missing items, damaged items, internet unavailability, or inability to use the internet is a barrier for ethnic consumers from buying online grocery products. Therefore, this study has proven that perceived risk on online groceries have a negative impact on ethnic consumers' online purchasing decision.

Hypothesis 8: Ethnic consumers' culture is expected to have a positive correlation with promotional offer. (Supported)

The study has supported the hypothesis which suggests that promotional offers are often accepted by ethnic consumers (table 5.30). Guilherme and John (2015) described that some companies divide consumers into different marketing groups. These dividers help them to plan sufficiently on how to apply marketing strategies to different people. Appiah (2004) suggests that moving towards marketing to the ethnic market is important because of the rising numbers of ethnic minorities in the UK. A study from Appiah (2004) found that categorising black ethnic consumers and then marketing to them greatly increased sales. Khairula et al. (1996)

demonstrated that it is essential to categorise ethnic groups and subcultural groups in the British market.

The study's result is supported by Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998). They found that promotional offers are very effective at helping to convince ethnic consumers to make purchases. Their study suggested that in order to market effectively to ethnic minorities, it is essential to advertise based on the cultural and social beliefs of those ethnic people. Jamal et al. (2012) explained that there are many different types of promotions that would appeal to ethnic consumers. This study's result shows that 21.5% of the respondents strongly agree that they almost always accept promotional offers from companies, whilst 34.1% of the respondents agree that they tend to accept promotional offers. Around 20% of the respondents stated that they are not interested in accepting promotional offers (table 5.10). It is therefore evident that almost 50% of respondents in this study accept promotional offers when they are offered by companies. Table 5.30 indicated that sig. value p is less than .005. Therefore, this hypothesis is supported.

Hypothesis 9: Ethnic consumers are expected to have difficulties in the ability to adapt with technology to do online shopping. (Not Supported)

The study does not support the hypothesis. Online shopping requires a technological device to place an order or check products. Familiarity with using a technological device helps a consumer to get the online experience very easily. The result of this study has some difference from the literature. Abbasi et al. (2011) highlighted that the usage of technology varies within the different cultural context. Their study stated that there is very little variation in the usage of technology in Western countries, including Japan. However, the lack of usage was found in people from non-Western countries. Fujimoto et al. (2007) explained that in the collectivist cultural context, especially people from South Asian backgrounds are more resistant to internet uses.

The Office for National Statistics (2011) found that ethnic consumers are young people in the UK. This study has collected data from a large number of young and educated individuals. Foxall (2017) demonstrated that young people are more technology-friendly than any other age group. Survey result from this study indicate that 30.4% of the respondents are from the age group 26-35 (table 5.4), 24.9% of the respondents have college-level education and 9.6% have a lower level of education or no education (table 5.2). A less educated person is generally considered to be less effective in technological activities. Some ethnic consumers in this study

have no or little education, and they are not using any technological devices. However, the number in this study is very small (.03%, detailed in section 4.5.1.6). The percentage of the student respondents in this study is 23.6% (table 5.3). Table 5.16 indicates that a majority of the ethnic consumers in this study are able to use online app systems to place an order or search for a product. Similarly, table 5.17 indicates that the majority of the respondents do not face any problem with the online payment system whereas 18.1% of respondents confirmed that they faced problems. Thus, this study can conclude that participants do not face much difficulty when adapting to technology to do online shopping. This is because the majority of the participants identified as educated and students.

5.4 SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

The study found some demographic factors affect how an ethnic consumer goes about buying online groceries. This study shows the influence of age factors on online grocery shopping. For instance, younger consumers are far more likely, statistically than old consumers to do online shopping. Literature in this study said that women tend to shop more than men, both online and offline (Wu, 2003; Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Foxall, 2017). But findings from this study oppose the literature in the context of ethnic consumer online grocery shopping by ethnic gender. The literature of this study said less education person tend to be less involved in online shopping. But this study opposes the literature because this study has studied ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Therefore, finding of the study is different from the literature. This study found attitudes and intentions have a large influence on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping intentions (Wang et al., 2016; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012; Liu et al., 2013; Blomqvist et al., 2015). A large factor behind whether an ethnic consumer uses online grocery shopping or not is trust and satisfaction. Consumer general distrust in online shopping restricts them from buying groceries online (Salo & Karjaluoto, 2007; Zaltman and Moorman, 1998; Campbell and Walker, 2010; Chen and Barnes, 2007). Cultural satisfaction is important among ethnic consumer and ethnic consumers tend to buy a product that holds the image of their country of origin (Beverland and Farrelly, 2010; Hong and Wyer, 1990). Satisfaction cannot be happening if the product on a website and face to face are not the same as described.

Perceived risk (e.g., security of transaction and privacy, perceived complexity, unavailability to judge the products quality and postage and packing) found to have a negative influence on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Other factors that stop people from shopping online are missing items, delay in delivery, problems with returning products, quality, substitute items,

and unavailability of the internet. Ethnic consumers tend to be easily drawn in by promotional campaigns (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998; Jamal et al., 2012; Appiah, 2004).

Culture makes a big difference in consumer buying decisions. If any company focuses on ethnic culture-related kinds of stuff on their websites, found positive results on their online buying decision (Browaeyns and Price, 2015; Fujimoto et al., 2007; Guerrier and Wilson, 2011). A product's ethnicity is important to the ethnic consumer's online shopping decision-making process. Moreover, this study found ethnic consumer have the ability to adapt to technology in order to do online grocery shopping. This is because this study has younger and student respondents.

The researcher developed two open-ended questions in this study. Based on the qualitative findings of the questionnaire the researcher has highlighted some key points which are related to ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Table 5.42 is a summary of the experience described by users of online shopping.

Table 5:42 Experience of online users

Users of online shopping	Positive experience	Negative experience
Quality	Quality of the products are the same as store shopping.	Sometimes quality is not the same.
Time	Easy to place an order online.	Internet unavailability or slow speed internet can cause problems and delays.
Return policy	Product returning is easy. Some company add return level with the products.	Some products have to be returned on the buyer cost. Sometimes conditional return policy applied.
Price	Online price is cheaper than the store price.	Price varies on companies. Some website put less price and some even expensive.
Website	Website put all the details of the products. Some products are easy to find because of the vertical order of the website. Search options help buyer to find the products easily.	The website often displays products clearly but it's very hard to know the quality of the product. Some websites take time to load if a lot of customers are on the website at one time.
Search option	Product searching is very easy.	Because of language difficulties, it can be hard to find the expected products.
Delivery	Products delivery is faster.	Sometimes products are left outside or are left with a neighbour. This can cause products to sometimes get lost or get damaged. On some occasions, the item is too big to be put in the letterbox. In those cases, collection points are required to collect the item. This cost a lot of time and effort for the consumer.
Promotional offers	There are plenty of promotional offered by companies.	Promotional products are not the same as other products. They often are of worse quality. Or you can be forced into buying more of a product than you need. Additionally, promotions often incentivize consumers to buy products they often don't really need.
Substitute products	Products substitution does not make any effect on online shopping behaviour. Substitutes product fulfils the desired demand.	Being sent a product that you didn't order is often a large inconvenience for consumers.
Security/payment methods	Payment is secure and safe. PayPal and other payment are reliable.	The internet contains some malicious websites that do not accept reliable payment methods. These websites will often take a double payment and also can sell your details on the dark web. Viruses are also a problem on these websites.
Availability	Internet shopping is available 24 hours a day and 365 days a year.	The internet can be a barrier to doing online shopping. There is a cost involved in browsing the internet. Sometimes having a bad internet connection can be a barrier to online shopping. Even a slow internet speed does not allow images to load on the online shopping websites.
Services experience	Online shopping is reliable, trusted and satisfied needs.	Some consumers become unhappy with the service they receive.
Brand trust	Online brands are good. Some of the websites are customers friendly, e.g., Amazon, eBay, Tesco.	Online Brand is expensive sometimes. They put the delivery charge and it's a hassle to return if the items are not good.
Social media	Social media helps to do online shopping.	Social media only show the products that the seller had to advertise.

The second open-ended question was for non-users of the online shopper. Several users have expressed their experience with not doing online shopping. The experience from non-users has been summarised in table 5.43.

Table 5:43 Experience of non-users of online shopping

Experience of Non-users of online shopping	
Lack of trust	Some ethnic consumers find it hard to trust online shopping due to the fact that they believe that shopping doesn't often come on time. Therefore, if any item is urgently needed, they often believe it is better to go to the store.
Quality	Many ethnic consumers believe that the quality of products bought online is not the same as store shopping. Sometimes some grocery products are sent that are not fresh or are a replacement product. This is an inconvenience for ethnic consumers.
Privacy	Ethnic consumers often believe that there is no privacy policy for online payment systems. In order to shop online, payments often must be made online from a bank account. However, many ethnic consumers do not have bank accounts and often do not know how to use these services.
Return policy	Returning a product is often a hassle. Therefore, some ethnic consumers do not like to go through the potential effort and would rather just purchase from a street shop.
Delivery	Ethnic consumers often believe that online shopping is unreliable due to the fact that they believe that they cannot rely on delivery. Waiting for the delivery all day can be problematic for ethnic consumers.
Technology	Technology is often not accessible for ethnic consumers due to the lack of experience in using technology and language difficulties.
Internet browsing	Some ethnic consumers have never browsed the internet, and many do not have internet facilities in their home.
Language	Language is often a barrier when doing online shopping. Many ethnic consumers do not understand what is written on websites.
Education	Some ethnic consumers have limited education which means even if they can speak English, they often can't read it to navigate the shops.
Cultural limitation	There is a cultural tradition of going to street shops which many ethnic consumers don't want to move away from.
Convenience	Some ethnic consumers find shopping in stores far more convenient due to the fact that they can easily buy products if and when they need them, whereas when shopping online, they have to wait to receive their products whilst also dealing with a difficult to navigate website.

In this research, 55 respondents do not do online shopping and 109 respondents who do online shopping occasionally (detailed figure in appendix 3). Therefore, 15.3% of ethnic consumers are not involved in online shopping. On the other hand, 30.3% of respondents are involved in online shopping occasionally. When comparing online shoppers and those who don't shop online the percentage is almost half and half. However, more respondents shop in stores when compared to ethnic consumers who do online shopping.

CHAPTER 6: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This chapter discusses the conclusions and findings that can be ascertained from the analysis. The findings have been tested using quantitative data analysis against the hypotheses that were proposed in the previous chapter. This chapter sums up the findings from the research conducted. The report will focus on the findings of the research according to the research objectives. There will be some recommendations for future research. The limitations are also included at the end of this chapter.

6.1 DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Consumer demographic information discusses in this section. An evolved conceptual framework has developed basis on the finding of this study. Moreover, mediator and moderator have been discussed in relation to online grocery shopping.

6.2 EVOLVING CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, the researcher designed a conceptual framework after reading the literature (figure 3.17). The conceptual framework is an analysis of previous studies. After completing primary data analysis, the research presents several factors that have an impact on ethnic consumer online grocery buying behaviour. An evolved conceptual framework has been designed from findings of this study. These factors allow a conceptual framework to be developed relating to ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour of groceries. The conceptual framework will help business developers, government organisations, and educational institutions to understand the factors that influence ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour in relation to online grocery shopping. The proposed conceptual framework and evolved conceptual framework have some differences. The proposed conceptual framework contextualises consumer attitudes, intentions, culture, trust, satisfaction, web selection and technology use. The results of the study indicate that perceived risk has a greater influence on ethnic consumers' online buying decision. Businesses need to strongly consider making websites that cater to ethnic minorities and the languages that ethnic minorities understand. When researching demographic factors this study found, gender and education don't influence on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping, but age has an influence. Consumers that have a strong ethnic identity tend to be easily drawn in by-products that are from their home countries or are associated with their home countries. Promotional packages are another determinant to attract the ethnic consumer into buying products. Similarly, culture, product origin, previous experience, and website impact ethnic

consumers' online buying decision. The diagram of the evolved conceptual framework is presented in figure 6.1 and discussion will follow in this chapter.

Figure 6:1 Evolving conceptual framework of ethnic consumer online grocery buying behaviour

6.3 DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

Demographic information of the consumer has been discussed in this chapter. This study discovered how demographic factors related to ethnic consumer online grocery shopping. Previous studies also showed how demography is playing an important role in the online buying process (Reynolds and Olson, 2013; Wood, 2011; Freeman, 2009; Anesbury et al., 2016; Office for National Studies 2011; Foxall, 2017). This study has gathered gender information. Fifty-seven percent of the respondents identified as male whereas forty-three percent identified as female. Reynolds and Olson (2013) suggest that women are more advanced when compared to men when doing online shopping. Freeman (2009) found that women tend to be more engaged in online shopping than men are. Similarly, Anesbury et al. (2016) mentioned the majority of online shoppers are young women with a high disposable income. On the other hand, Wood (2011) reports that men are more online shopping oriented. A census in 2011 showed that there are more women in the UK. However, this study shows there is no significant difference between male and female for online grocery shopping (table

5.36). This is because the study has researched ethnic online grocery shopping. Previous studies have researched consumers in general, but this study is conducted only amongst ethnic consumers. Due to the nature of the respondents (student and educated respondents), the findings are different from the previous studies. In this study, the researcher has shown an Independent sample T-test for the gender (table 5.36). The result indicates that there is no significant difference between men and women in this study. This research has been primarily collected from male respondents. If there was a better balance between genders, the data may have backed up previous research.

The present study shows that the educational level (table 5.2) of the respondents has interesting trends. A comparison showed a response rate from college-level respondents of 24%, whilst university level respondents had a slightly smaller share of response at 21.6%. The Office for National Statistics (2016) published a result of British educational qualifications that shows that 27% of England and Wales's population has a higher educational qualification. Research data in this study has been collected primarily from those with an education. A good proportion of respondents in this investigation were from higher education. This is because most of the data has been collected from UWS Paisley campus and UWS London campus. Moreover, some of the respondents who had less, or no education could not complete the research questions and the researcher had to act as a bilingual person (detailed in section 4.5.1.6). Reynold and Olson (2013) discussed the question of whether an individual of higher education is inclined to choose different products compared to someone who has less education. There are two categories that they class people into. They describe that educated people often buy products of a higher quality whereas a less educated person is often swayed by the superficial attractiveness of a product and/or advertising. This study indicates Sig. value for p is greater than .005 (table 5.35). Therefore, this study does not support the positive relation between education and online grocery shopping.

This study had a large proportion of students responding. Students generally are of a young age. The percentage of the student respondents in this study is 23.6% (table 5.3). The Office for National Statistics (2011) reported that young people make up the largest percentage of the ethnic demographic in this country. Reynolds and Olson (2013) suggest that young people are more online shopping oriented than older people. Foxall (2017) discover that the young are more technologically friendly than the older generation. Online shopping requires the use of technological devices, so it is those who are able to use technological devices who are more likely to shop online. Table 5.16 indicates that the majority of the ethnic consumer in this study

are able to use online app systems to place an order or search for a product. Similarly, table 5.17 indicates that the majority of the respondents do not face any problem with online payment systems whereas 18.1% of respondents confirmed that they face problems. Thus, the fact that most of the participants in this study have technological abilities to do online grocery shopping because they are young. Hypothesis 9 in this study also been rejected. Therefore, the ethnic consumer in this study has ability to use technological devices to do online grocery shopping. This is because the majority of the respondents in this study are young and student.

Respondents were asked about their current living status. This question helped to inform the research on how ethnic minorities have adapted to British culture. There is a clear trend between spending time in an unfamiliar place and gradually getting more accustomed to that place. There is also evidence that the culture of an unfamiliar place will eventually start to influence how someone behaves. Nwankwo and Lindridge (1998) explained a person who was born and raised in the UK is extremely likely to be acculturated with British culture whereas an ethnic migrant is far less likely to be as acculturated. Khairulla et al. (1996) identify that ethnic consumer culture becomes diluted when it is mixed with British culture (individuals' different acculturation processes are described in figure 3.11). The UK has the most advanced online shopping market anywhere in the world (Clark et al., 2015). Therefore, those who spend time in the UK have a reasonable chance of experiencing the online shopping market. The research has been collected primarily from ethnic people who have lived in the UK from 6-10 years (21.9%, table 5.5). So, it is expected that the vast majority of respondents know about online shopping in the UK.

This research had the highest response rate from those of a Bangladeshi or British-Bangladeshi background. The Office for National Statistics (2011) stated that those from Indian descent are the largest ethnic group in the UK with Pakistanis in 2nd position and Bangladeshis in 3rd (figure 5.1). Percentages of the additional ethnicities surveyed are as follows: Pakistani/British Pakistani 13.4%, Indian/British Indian 13.2%, Chinese/British Chinese 6.6%, other Asian 12.6%, African/Black African 12.1%, and all other 6.8% (table 5.6). Ofcom (2013) reported that the highest number of people of Bangladeshi ethnic origin lived in the Tower Hamlet area in London. The data was collected from the Tower Hamlets area in London. Thus, it is unsurprising that 35.3% of respondents are of Bangladeshi origin (table 5.6). Though there is a Bangladeshi heavy response to the survey, there is still a good spread of ethnicities surveyed. This means that the data represents the ethnic peoples of the UK. ANOVA analysis in this study shows there is no significant difference among ethnicities. The study also shows there is

less number (16.5%) of the ethnic population involved in online grocery shopping (table 5.7), whereas around 32.9% of the ethnic consumers do online shopping (detailed in the appendix 3).

Income has a direct effect on ethnic consumer online shopping. Income was not asked about in this research because during the pilot survey several respondents did not complete this question and requested for it to be removed from the questionnaire. This study has listed income group by ethnicity in table 3.2. This table indicates that a large number of ethnic consumers fall in the lower-income range. Kotler (2016) described that people of high-income tend to spend more than a group of people of low-income. Freeman (2009) identified that the majority of women do online shopping and that they have higher than average income. Hernandez et al. (2011) demonstrated that higher income causes internet users to perceive lower implicit risks in undertaking online purchases, and thereby this affects their demand for internet products and services. Low income discourages online transactions, and perceptions of self-efficacy, ease of use and usefulness should improve with rising incomes, due to the ability to withstand possible financial losses. Usually, income is reflected in the professional status or social class of the individual – different professional categories are accompanied by different incomes.

Religion has an impact on the ethnic consumer's buying process. This study did not ask directly about religion because the respondents did not feel comfortable answering the questions. However, this study has used secondary sources to show the impact on online grocery shopping. Ninety-two percent of the Bangladeshi community living in the UK are Muslim and they are the second-largest Muslim community after Pakistanis (Office for National Statistics, 2019). Most of the data for this study has come from Bangladeshi respondents followed by Pakistani, Indian, and other nationalities. Thus, the study can assume that majority of the respondents are Muslims. Similarly, the majority of the Indian nationalities are Hindus (Office for National Statistics, 2019). Jafari et al. (2014) described in the context of ethnicity and well-being that religiosity has a very large impact on what choices people make and what lifestyle they choose to lead. Being very religious implies that the individual has a strong connection with their culture and their ethnic background. Bukhari et al. (2020) stated that among Muslim consumers, Islamic rules administer their culture which assists as a direction in their daily lives. They specified that Islam, as a religion, controls Muslim consumer buying behaviour. This includes buying Halal food, spending money on general living, education, health, and aiding those in need. They also detailed that religion expressively governs cultural and social behaviours in Asian and Middle Eastern societies as compared to Western nations. Some ethnic

consumer identified they face some problems while maintaining a daily lifestyle because of the chosen religion. These include buying Halal food, working in British-run businesses, attending and social events.

Kotler and Armstrong (2015) highlighted that the consumer's online buying decision does not only depend on demographic characteristics but also social, cultural, personal, psychological, economic, situational, and technological characteristics.

6.4 DISCUSSION ABOUT ETHNICITY AND ONLINE GROCERY SHOPPING

This research has investigated how ethnic consumers engage with online purchasing. Some ethnic consumers are engaged in online grocery shopping, but the percentage is minimal (16.5%, table 5.7), which marketers need to rethink. However, others are put off from using online shopping for a number of reasons. Table 5.19 indicates that 35.72% of respondents stopped doing online shopping because of the language problem. Maxwell's (2012) findings also support this research's findings. Maxwell (2012) found that many Asians have a language barrier which prevents them from using internet facilities. Cui (2001) suggests that ethnic consumer's online shopping behaviour depends on media advertising. It is important for businesses to look at how ethnic consumers are responding to their business advertising.

The consumer's ethnic identity is an important factor to consider when deciding business marketing strategies. This research has indicated that ethnic groups tend to hold strong cultural beliefs. The study found that 39% of respondents feel a contradiction with the British lifestyle (table 5.11). Most of the ethnic people acknowledged that they practice their traditional ethnic culture of their country of origin (table 5.9). Twenty-one-point percent of the respondents strongly agree that they almost always accept promotional offers from companies whilst 34.1% of the respondents agree that they tend to accept promotional offers (table 5.10). Appiah's (2004) study supports the findings of this research. Appiah (2004) describes that groups with a strong ethnic identity tend to abide by traditional values to a greater extent than those with a weaker ethnic identity. The ethnicity of the consumer also affects their set beliefs. Ethnic consumers' satisfaction is often fulfilled by products that can also be bought in their country of origin (Beverland and Farrelly, 2010). Building up ethnic consumers' trust is important for the growth of the online market, as trust brings repeat purchases. Because ethnic consumers got to fear about the privacy and security of the online transactions resulted in less engaging on the online platform. Campbell and Walker (2010) stated that trust in a product, brand, or

company increases purchasing by consumers. Therefore, trust and satisfaction in products, brands and companies are important to build up an ethnic consumer online presence.

An increase in ethnic consumers' trust and satisfaction in online shopping is caused by a variety of factors. These factors include, but are not limited to, the product quality, the speed in delivery of the products, and privacy when purchasing. Ethnic consumers tend to buy products from stores rather than online (only 16.5% buy online). Part of the reason behind this is the fact that the size and colour of a product (product visualisation) can't always be accurately ascertained from an online purchase (table 5.42). Additionally, return policies are not always easy to use or understand and there are sometimes return costs. Customers may have to go to the post office, or another drop-off point to return the items, which is a clear inconvenience for most consumers.

Therefore, ethnic consumer's online grocery shopping habits depends on a number of components. Trust, satisfaction, products origin, quality, and delivery of the products are all critical factors. This study indicates there is no significant difference in online shopping in terms of nationality and gender. An ANOVA analysis of ethnicity and gender is shown in section 5.3.4. Table 5.39 indicates there is no significant difference between ethnicity and gender in terms of online grocery shopping. Table 5.38 reveals that group means of all the ethnicities are equal. Thus, this study shows there is no significant difference among ethnicities in terms of online grocery shopping.

6.5 ETHNIC CONSUMER CULTURE AND PURCHASE DECISION

An ethnic consumer's culture is the biggest influence on how they make online purchases. Ethnic consumers come from a culture that influences them to almost always looking for promotions when buying products. Studies (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998; Jamal et al., 2012) have proven the connection between ethnic consumers and them looking for promotions. When an ethnic consumer sees their cultural activities focusing on somewhere specific, it changes their mentality towards the organisation, and they start thinking positively. Products that come from the ethnic consumer's country of origin are also important for consumer cultural satisfaction. Hypothesis 6 in this study proved that ethnic consumer culture has relation to online grocery shopping.

Consumers become increasingly socialised with British culture the longer they spend in the UK. However, religious sentiments and strong set cultural beliefs are a hindrance towards the acculturation process. This causes a problem for marketers as a singular strategy will not appeal

to all consumers, because having a strong ethnic identity or strong ethnic cultural beliefs impacts what foods consumers buy, what entertainment materials consumers choose to experience, and whether or not consumers choose to join clubs. From consumers' initial cultural desires, consumers then begin to base their choices on their subjective and objective needs. The current study shows that 37.6% of ethnic consumers think that it is essential to formulate better business strategies for ethnic consumers. Studying and formulating separate business strategies is essential if the ethnic market is to be reached effectively.

This study identified age and attitudes as a moderator of ethnic consumer online grocery shopping propensity. Findings of this study and literature said young ethnic consumer are more activated towards online activities comparing to the older consumer. Attitudes towards online grocery shopping are most influential because higher positive attitudes lead to higher purchase intention of online groceries. The study found if someone has tried online grocery shopping previously, they are more likely to purchase groceries online again since their attitudes towards the action become more positive. Similarly, culture and living status in the UK works as a mediator. When an ethnic consumer acculturates with the British culture, they tend to buy more online. Acculturation depends on how long they are staying in the UK and how they are involved with activities with friends and family (figure 3.11). Promotional offers also work as a mediator for ethnic consumer's online shopping. This study found that the majority of ethnic consumers were attracted to promotional offers (table 5.10). The mediator and moderator of ethnic consumer's online grocery shopping are shown in figure 6.2.

Figure 6:2 Mediator and Moderator of ethnic consumer online grocery shopping

6.6 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research outcomes have been presented in table 6.1. Two of the columns show whether the research aim, and objectives have been achieved, or whether further research is required to definitively prove the hypothesis.

Table 6:1 Research Outcomes

Research aim	Research Objectives	Achieved	Future work
To examine the ethnic consumer's online buying behaviour in relation to grocery purchasing	Objective-1. To identify and assess the characteristics of an online ethnic consumer	Yes	Yes
	Objective-2. To evaluate how culture affects ethnic consumer's online buying behaviour	Yes	
	Objective-3. To examine factors for the ethnic consumer's adoption of technologies	Yes	Yes
	Objective-4. To investigate how the ethnic consumer builds up their trust in online purchasing with technology	Yes	

This research aims to discover the behavioural habits of ethnic consumers regarding online grocery shopping. The findings of this research are presented in the context of primary research and a literature review. This has added further justification to the findings. The primary research that was undertaken in this study was in the form of a questionnaire towards ethnic consumers in the UK. A number of different geographical areas were surveyed, and some people were surveyed online. The data has been analysed through inferential and descriptive statistics.

The aim of the research has been developed through the researcher's own experiences while managing an online business in the UK. The researcher as an ethnic consumer has experienced problems with online shopping and has realised that online shopping for ethnic consumers needs to be studied. The whole process of online grocery shopping for ethnic consumers has been comprehensively covered in this research. Table 6.1 indicates whether the objectives have been met during the research.

Limitations of this study have been highlighted later in this chapter. These limitations could serve as suggestions for future research. A number of recommendations have been suggested for government organisations (such as education ministry, trade ministry and the office for national statistics) and business in the public and private sector. The recommendation is also useful for international companies who are doing business in the UK or who are planning to set up a new online business that has customers in the UK. Though findings this study is mostly applicable to the UK it also can apply to ethnic minority countries in some extend.

6.6.1 Research objective 1

Objective-1. To identify and assess the characteristics of online ethnic consumers.

The study has achieved the objectives set out at the beginning of the study. This study has reviewed literature from previous research. The characteristics of ethnic consumers have been explored by looking at previous studies. The research attempts to highlight all the factors that relate to consumer buying intentions. Two types of characteristics have been repeatedly brought up during the literature survey (external and internal factors) (Kotler and Armstrong, 2015). External factors and internal factors are the key indicators in measuring ethnic consumer's online shopping characteristics. Some researchers have also shown interest in studying demographic characteristics, purchase preferences, benefit perceptions, and consumer lifestyles.

The buying behaviour that consumers exhibit often helps to predict the online grocery shopping characteristics that they will have. The buying process has a number of different stages. At each stage, consumers experience a new dimension of the online shopping environment. Ethnic consumers pass through the buying process in the same way as other consumers. Internal and external stimuli lead consumers when making purchase decisions. These internal and external stimuli also work in the online buying process. This research has categorised the positive and negative attitudes of ethnic consumers from their online grocery shopping experiences. Positive and negative aspects have been derived from the primary data analysis of this study, which has been summarised in tables 5.42, and 5.43. Some of the attitudes that ethnic consumers have are listed in figure 6.3.

Figure 6:3 Positive and negative aspects of an ethnic consumer about online grocery shopping

This research also suggested in the objective that some future work will be necessary for the best possible outcome. As a result of globalisation as well as of modern technological development, lifestyle and habits of the consumer have changed dramatically. Adaptation also makes a huge difference and cultural activity change by the adaptation process. Therefore, studying and researching ethnic consumer characteristics is necessary for the future.

6.6.2 Research objective 2

Objective-2. To evaluate how culture affects ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour.

The research has also met the expectation of this objective. The study has discovered how ethnic culture influences ethnic consumers' online buying behaviour. To find the cultural activities, the questionnaire was developed with the objective of asking about the effect of culture, and statements that are derived from the literature. To meet the objective, characteristics of the ethnic consumer are discussed in this research.

This study focuses on the individual's different acculturation processes (figure 3.11). Based on the acculturation process, ethnic consumerism is categorised on the lowest acculturation stage because ethnic consumers were found to have strong cultural and religious sentiment and risk concerns (section 6.3 and 6.5). At this acculturation stage, the consumer is normally bound by their native culture and without access to higher education. They have limited knowledge of the English language, it is certainly insufficient to adjust to modern cultural activities (Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). Ethnic consumers hold a strong set belief about their cultural values. To find the characteristics of an ethnic consumer ethnic identity, ethnicity, and the acculturations processes were researched. This study proved consumer who experiences satisfying outcomes from their online grocery shopping will develop a higher level of trust in online groceries (Bianchi and Andrews, 2012; Omar et al., 2009). Some of the satisfaction comes from product ethnicity (Roth and Romeo, 1992; Beverland and Farrelly, 2010). The national image of a country's products for grocery is important for the ethnic consumer. For example- some specific vegetables/groceries ethnic consumers always want to buy because they are used to having those very often in their home countries.

There are some risk factors discussed along with other cultural activities. Risk factors are a crucial part of the online buying decision process. Risk factors determine whether the consumer elects to shop online or go to the high street. From previous research, it is found that people who are born and raised in the UK are supposed to highly acculturate with British culture (Khairulla et al., 1996; Nwankwo and Lindridge, 1998). People who live longer in the UK also acculturate more strongly to British culture but there is still a gap present. Regarding culture, this study found the following conclusions on ethnic consumer online grocery shopping:

- They are highly bound to their native culture (table 5.9).
- They are interested in promotional offers (table 5.10).
- Ethnic culture and mainstream culture are contradictory (table 5.11).

- Advertising has a greater impact on the sale (table 5.12).
- Products ethnicity plays an important role for ethnic consumer online grocery shopping decision.

6.6.3 Research objective 3

Objective-3. To examine the factors that cause ethnic consumers to adopt technology or cause the lack of adoption of technology.

The aim of this objective was to find out what factors lead to ethnic consumers adopting technological services. The research found many factors that have an effect on the uptake of technology by ethnic consumers (figure 6.4). However, some future work needs to be done to further solidify the factors. The medium to carry out online grocery shopping is the internet and to be able to use the internet one must have a device capable of connecting to the internet (e.g., mobile phone, laptop, tablet, I-pad). However, if a user is not familiar with the device, they are less likely to browse the internet and as a result, will not be able to purchase online. This study found that the majority of the respondents are educated and have the ability to browse the internet using a mobile app (table 5.2 and 5.16).

The researcher was interested in the designing of websites and a technology-friendly app system for those with little experience of using the internet. The present study shows cultural diversity focusing on the website is important to influence ethnic consumer by the emergence of new technology (Fujimoto et al., 2007; Ranaweera and Prabhu, 2003; Omar et al., 2004; Wen, 2009; Bianchi and Andrews, 2012). Research shows that when a website focuses on ethnic cultural beliefs, the consumer is more likely to buy from these websites. Giving opportunities to use multi-language facilities also attracts the consumer to use online services. The secure payment system and privacy policy are also important factors in the adoption of online services. There are a few factors discussed in this study in relation to the adoption of technology (figure 6.4). These factors summarised form the findings of the study (table 5.42 and 5.43).

Figure 6:4 Factors in relation to the adoption of technologies

A positive mindset for consumers is created partly through brand familiarity. Social media has a large influence on people to start using online shopping. For example, Facebook, Instagram and TikTok bring new people to the online platform where consumers then see advertising from brands, and this will help convince them to use online services, including online grocery shopping. Wearable technology is a new platform to help persuade consumers to start using more online services (e.g., smartwatch, smart ring and video games).

6.6.4 Research objective 4

Objective-4. To investigate how ethnic consumers' trust is built up regarding online purchasing with technology.

The research has met the objective. Respondents were asked whether their trust in online grocery shopping has increased or if it has been decreased. Research has shown that a high level of trust increases online grocery purchasing and there is a significant relationship between consumer trust and online grocery shopping. Trust is built-up through customer reviews, repeated high quality in products, a good reputation of the business, privacy and security, website quality, delivery of the products. However, trust varies depending on the situation. Frequent online grocery users establish a high level of trust in the grocery e-retailer. Previous researchers have suggested several factors which work together to build up trust. These factors include brand reputation, security, quality of information, word of mouth, good online

experience, and perceived risk (Pavlou, 2003; Liu et al., 2013; Chen and Barnes, 2007; Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Pikkarainen et al., 2004). More a shopper trusts online grocery e-retailer will less likely experience perceived risk. But if consumer experience negative effects (e.g., disappointment, displeasure, anxiety, sadness, frustration or anger over transaction) from online grocery shopping will reduce their trust from purchase intention. Factors related to trust and satisfaction are summarized in figure 6.5.

Figure 6:5 Trust and satisfaction factors on online grocery shopping

This study focuses on ethnic cultural beliefs because trust and satisfaction with online shopping depending on the cultural context of the consumers. Ethnic consumers hold strong cultural beliefs. Therefore, their trust and beliefs will differ from mainstream consumers.

6.7 REVIEW OF GAPS IN THE LITERATURE AND FUTURE WORK

This study has found some gaps in the literature. The gaps have been identified during the literature review. Reviews of gaps in the literature have identified below:

1. This research has identified that there is a lack of research on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour of groceries. Consumer buying behaviour has been researched by many researchers (e.g., McKechnie, 1992; Browaeys and Price, 2015; Kotler et al., 2016). However, the grocery online buying behaviour of ethnic consumers has never been sufficiently researched. Therefore, this study primarily focuses on the online buying behaviour of ethnic consumers in relation to groceries.
2. Ethnic consumers tend to have a large disposable income (Anesbury et al., 2016). The percentage of ethnic consumers is increasing day by day. There have not been many

investigations into the disposable income of ethnic consumers and the opportunities in the British online markets that ethnic consumers have. Therefore, this study has a great amount of validity and importance.

3. Many ethnic consumers do not speak English as a first language and as a result, struggle to understand information on websites. This research has focused on designing and formatting websites for those people who have a language problem, in order to help them to shop online more effectively.

6.7.1 Research contribution

This study proposes two contributions: knowledge and practice/policymaking.

Knowledge: contribution to knowledge, in this study, is an evolved conceptual framework of online shopping. In the first stage, the research developed a conceptual framework for online grocery shopping. These developments bring into question the evolution of the conceptual framework. This evolved conceptual framework gives an idea about the ethnic consumer's online grocery shopping. New factors have been presented in this framework that emerged from the primary research. The researcher believes that the evolving conceptual framework provides an idea about ethnic consumers' online grocery buying behaviour and it is a first comprehensive framework. It is presented positive attitudes have a positive influence on ethnic consumer online grocery purchase intentions (Blomqvist et al., 2015). Perceived risk is an important factor for the ethnic consumer's online buying decision (Pavlou, 2003; Harris et al., 2017; Mortimer et al., 2016). There are some other factors in relation to online grocery shopping gathered in figure 6.3 and 6.4, including age, attitudes, culture, a familiarity with a product or online circumstances, product's origin, consumer reviews and feedback, promotional offer and technological usability.

Policymaking: this research will help policymakers. The findings of the research will be open to all businesses and government organisations (such as education ministry, trade ministry, the office for national statistics, ministry of planning, science and technology). This research will be helpful to businesses and government organisations because it gives a clear idea of how ethnic consumers conduct online grocery shopping. Organisations such as the trade ministry, planning ministry, the foreign ministry, and online and offline businesses can evaluate the evolved conceptual framework and can reformulate their business and social strategies in accordance with the findings. Additionally, new businesses who are planning to conduct research in the UK can follow this research to make their business strategies. Educational

providers and conference and seminar organisers can look at this research for their business development.

Managers of the online grocery retailers will be mostly benefitted from this study. They can use the data and findings from this research to understand ethnic consumer's needs. This study shows, trust brings long terms-satisfaction among ethnic consumers resulted in intentions to buy online groceries. The managers of the businesses should consider the risk mitigation strategy, such as making online grocery shopping easier to shoppers by customising the e-retailing websites to suit their own needs or more clearly articulating the benefits of online grocery shopping (Mortimer et al., 2016). This study identifies perceived risk on online grocery is a potential barrier for ethnic consumer purchase intentions. Therefore, managers should try to minimize all potential obstacle to influence an ethnic consumer to do online grocery shopping. Cultural satisfaction needs to prioritise more because ethnic consumer holds strong cultural beliefs. Ethnic consumers buy grocery products which mostly reflects their country of origin (e.g., rice, vegetables, fish, meat, utensils)

6.8 RESEARCH LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study has successfully achieved its aim and objectives. The researcher has tried to eliminate all of the limitations but there are inevitably some limitations present in this research which one should address as a researcher. Here is a summary of the limitations below:

1. Studying consumer behaviour is a broad term. In the UK there is a large number of populations of ethnic minorities. According to a national census, the largest minority populations are Indian, followed by Pakistanis and Bangladeshis (Office for National Statistics, 2018). The questionnaire was mainly asked to those of Bangladeshi descent. This should have been more generalised to include other ethnic minorities in order to get a balanced viewpoint amongst different subgroups of ethnic minorities.
2. The research was undertaken in the UK. Populations of ethnic minorities live all over the country. The largest percentage of the population of ethnic minorities live in London, Birmingham, and Manchester. The researcher collected data from London, Brighton, and UWS Paisley campus. For better outcomes, data could have been collected from other cities. Gender should have been better balanced to include men and women.
3. This research discovered that most of the respondents are students and well educated. Students generally are advanced with technology and they have a general idea of online

shopping. Depending on student purchasing power and age the research findings has generalised with ethnic consumers with caution. Future research could put emphasis on more data from people of different backgrounds.

4. A further limitation of this study is with the research methodology. The research was collected and then quantified through the quantitative research method. Data has been collected through a questionnaire and an online platform. The online and self-administered data together had 365 respondents. If the sample size was larger, the research would have more validity and reliability.
5. The research question was developed in English and there was no translation for ethnic consumers. Translating research questions in multiple languages requires more time and effort. When translated, there is a possibility to get a poor translation of the research instrument (survey questionnaire). In some cases, the researcher worked as a bilingual person for the Bangladeshi community. The researcher also requested help from friends of different nationalities. The researcher could translate the research questionnaire to make it easier for all types of respondents, especially for respondents who are non-English speakers.

Future research should move towards testing actual purchasing behaviour in place of self-reports. Specifically, research should determine whether people shop more online when overnight delivery, in-store pick-up, and/or a video stream are available. Future methods should also involve participants using and purchasing from websites with various properties. Given the somewhat unique nature of the results of the video stream condition, research should look to see if visual uncertainty plays a unique role in trust or purchasing. Some suggestions for future research can be made from the results of this investigation:

1. This research is based on ethnic consumers in the UK. The output of this research is therefore based on ethnic consumers residing in the UK. If future research is conducted in other countries, it should look for different approaches when researching because every country has a different demographic, culture, and social background. The findings of this study may not be generalisable to other countries where grocery shopping provisions and behaviours may not be directly comparable.
2. This research is based on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour of groceries. Future studies can choose different product categories such as clothing or electronics.

3. Future research may have to establish how they can add to this research. This is because the researcher, in this study, defined ethnic consumers based on previous literature and articles. Specific subgroups of ethnic consumers were selected for this study, that can be used in future research.
4. This study found general outcomes for all ethnic consumers living in the UK. The study did not produce separate results for each subset of ethnic consumers. Future study can focus on studying different ethnic groups separately and can then compare the result with the ethnic minority group as a whole, as well as with mainstream consumers.
5. The research was conducted in English, which is not convenient for many ethnic consumers. Future studies can develop multilingual questionnaires for different subgroups of ethnic consumers.
6. Future research should include comparative studies. Direct comparison between emerging economies and highly developed economies will show existing differences and provide perspective both within one's domestic market as well as between markets.

6.9 PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATION

The findings of the research are highly important for business practitioners. To improve business, it is essential to target all consumer levels in the market. Targeting, selecting, and formulating a business strategy according to consumer demand is an astute approach for businesses. Some of these approaches are given below:

1. Consumers have concerns about availability and whether or not the product will be delivered when the consumer is available to access the product. Businesses can focus on delivering all essential products quickly and in the time, frame specified by the consumer.
2. Quality of the products is important for all types of businesses. Grocery products must be fresh and used by the sell-by date. Products must be available according to ethnic consumer demand (e.g., products relating to their culture). Products based research is important to understand ethnic consumer needs in relation to their culture.
3. In some cases, finding a product online is very hard. In comparison to the average consumer, ethnic consumers have less knowledge about product names and categories. Products should be categorised logically, and multilingual search options are necessary in order to locate the products easily. Image search options can be developed to find the desired product more quickly. For example, a business can improve an image visualisation link to search for the desired product.

4. There should be more return collection points to increase convenience for the consumer. Additionally, the refund application process should be quicker and more hassle-free.
5. It is very essential to target the potential market. Ethnic consumers in the UK have a huge disposable income. Neglecting ethnic consumers could be the biggest loss in the online market. During different religious and cultural festivals ethnic consumer spend a lot of money to celebrate (e.g., Eid, Ramadan, Puja, Diwali, Chinese New Year).
6. Implementing virtual assistance is important for the ethnic consumer, such as creating software which will be able to understand customers' voices and transform them into an understandable language for everyone (speech recognition, natural language understanding, and question answering).
7. Private enterprises, in addition to academics, may be interested in the relationship between trust and online behaviour. Web designers who integrate website features that serve to enhance trust could likely see tangible results in the form of increased visitors and sales. Website loading time should be minimised to load the website within a few seconds.

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APPENDICES

This chapter contains a layout of all the appendices which did not fit into the main part of the research. The appendices include questionnaire of the research, crosstabulation and graphical presentation of the SPSS outcomes from the data collected.

APPENDIX 1: INFORMATION SHEET & CONSENT FORM

Consent form	
Title of Study: A study of Ethnic consumer online buying behaviour of groceries	
Introduction: This research is about to find the ethnic consumer online buying behavior of groceries. <u>You are requested as a participant because the study is about ethnic minority people in the U.K. especially South Asian. The questionnaire may take 10-20 minutes. Your kind participation will help me to complete my Doctorate Degree successfully.</u>	
Purpose of Study. <ul style="list-style-type: none">The purpose of the study is to find the ethnic minority people attitudes of online purchasing and what are the strategies to attract them	
Research questions <ol style="list-style-type: none">Do ethnic consumers behave differently when they shop online?How do ethnic consumers accept the technology that is needed when making online purchase decisions?	
Privacy This paper is very confidential, and no name will use. There is high anonymity. Any information provided will be kept strictly confidential and will be kept in a locked file, and all electronic information will be coded and secured using a password-protected file.	
You are most welcome to ask any questions regarding this research. If you have any further questions about the study, at any time please feel free to contact me, [SHAMIM AHMED] at [REDACTED]. If you have any other concerns about my research area as a research participant that has not been answered by me, you may contact Dr Ahmed Beloucif. T: [REDACTED] E: [REDACTED]	
Participants name (Print):	
Participants Sign:	Date:
Researcher Name: Shamim Ahmed	
Researcher sign:	Date:

APPENDIX 2: QUESTIONNAIRE OF THE RESEARCH

Study of Ethnic Consumer Online Buying Behaviour of Groceries

Dear Sir/Madam,

Thank you for agreeing to take part of my research on ethnic consumer online buying behaviour. I am a student of University of the West of the Scotland and as part of my doctoral research I am conducting a survey. The survey is to find out ethnic consumer online buying behaviour in relation to groceries purchasing.

The survey questionnaire will take approximately 10 minutes. All the data collected will be kept confidential and all information will use for academic purpose only.

I would really appreciate your valuable time and kind help.

Note: Please complete the questions with tick Marks (✓) or write your comments where appropriate.

General Information

1 What is your gender?

- Male Female

2 What is your educational qualification?

- School level College Level University Graduation
 Masters Doctorate Other, please specify.....

3 What is your occupation?

- Student Public Service Self-employed
 Retired Businesses Other, please specify.....

4 Which age group you are belong too?

- 18-25 26-35 36-45
 46-55 56-65 66+

5 How long have you been lived in the UK?

- Since birth 0-5 years 6-10 years 11-15 years
 16-20 years 21-25 years 26 years and above

6 Which ethnic group you are belong too?

- Bangladeshi/British Bangladeshi Indian/British Indian Pakistani/British Pakistani
 Chinese/British Chinese Other Asian, please specify.....
 African/Black African All other, please specify.....

Part 1: Users of Online Shopping

Section 1: Online Shopping

7 To understand your online activity please answer the following statements. Please tick one number to indicate frequency of internet uses.

1 2 3 4 5
 Never Occasionally Fairly many times Very Often Always

I browse internet (If Never, please go to Part 2 on page 4)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

I do online shopping (If Never, please go to Part 2 on page 4)

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Language barrier stop me to do online shopping

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

8 To know the online users experience on online purchasing please tick one number below.

1 2 3 4 5
 Very Poor Poor Satisfactory Good Very Good

Quality of the online products	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Value of online products	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Reliability of online services	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 2: Consumer Attitudes and Intentions

9 The following statements reflects attitudes and intentions of a consumer towards online shopping, please tick one number in what extent you Disagree or Agree with the statements.

1 2 3 4 5
 Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

Speed of delivery services in online shopping is accurate	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I feel safe and secure to do online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Online shopping is easy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I can save my time and energy on online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I manage to buy cheapest products on online comparing to street shop	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Returning a product bought online is easy and simple	<input type="checkbox"/>				
On online products, warranty is same as store shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I can access online shopping 24 hours a day	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I get my money back if any item is missing or damaged on online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 3: Online Groceries and Consumer Culture

10 The following statements are based on online groceries purchasing and consumer cultural orientation, in what extent you Disagree or Agree please indicate by ticking one number below.

1 2 3 4 5
 Strongly Disagree Disagree Neutral Agree Strongly Agree

I buy most of my groceries online	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Buying online groceries is easy and hassle free	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I never faced any difficulties on online groceries products	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Delivery charges on online groceries affect my purchase decision	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Online grocery products are fresh same as supermarket shop	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Products substitution does not impact my online grocery shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I exercise my culture of origin	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It is essential for me to purchase a product contain my culture of origin	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I accept promotional offered by companies	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I found contradiction between British lifestyle and my cultural beliefs	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Ethnic marketing strategy will improve my online shopping experience	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Section 4: Consumer Trust, Satisfaction, Web Selection and Technology use

11 The following statements reflect consumer trust, satisfaction and web selection process to do online shopping. Please tick one number to indicate in what extent you Disagree or Agree.

	1	2	3	4	5
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I only trust well known website for online grocery shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Unfamiliarity of a website restrict me to purchase online	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I prefer to provide personal information on website	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Customer's reviews and feedback effects on my online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Trust build-up repeat purchase among consumer	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Cultural beliefs on website motivate to increase my trust on online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not bother about the security issues of the website	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The services I received from online shopping are satisfactory	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Satisfaction of a product arises based on where it made from (origin of the products)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Customer satisfaction helps to increase loyalty level	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I feel satisfied if the products are same as described	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I find language accessibility and cultural practice on website is easy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do online purchase where website shows green padlock	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I prefer to buy from user friendly website	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Details information of a product affect my selection of online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				
On online I can access large number of products than a supermarket	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Speed of website selected for shopping boost the online shopping behaviour	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Familiarity using a new technology helps to do better online shopping experience	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do most of my purchasing through mobile app system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I struggle to pay using online payment system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Gathering information about a product is necessary before you do online shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>				

12 Do you have any comments about your online shopping experience? Please state in the box below-

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

APPENDIX 3: SPSS OUTPUT GRAPHS AND TABLES

Figure: Age of the respondents' bar chart

Figure: Education of the respondent's bar chart

Figure: Occupation level of the respondents

Figure: Online shopping and gender of the respondents' bar chart

Table: Online shopping among ethnic consumers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Never	55	15.1	15.3	15.3
	Occasionally	109	29.9	30.3	45.6
	Fairly many times	76	20.8	21.1	66.7
	Very often	67	18.4	18.6	85.3
	Always	53	14.5	14.7	100.0
	Total	360	98.6	100.0	
Missing	System	5	1.4		
Total		365	100.0		

Figure: Living status in the UK

Figure: Browsing Internet * Doing online shopping bar chart

Table: Gender of the respondents * Browsing Internet Crosstabulation

		Never	Occasionally	Fairly many times	Very often	Always	
Gender of the respondents	Male	9	26	41	53	78	207
	Female	9	20	31	46	51	157
Total		18	46	72	99	129	364

Figure: Age of the respondents*Browsing internet bar chart

Figure: Bar chart-language barrier and gender of the respondents

Figure: Bar chart- online shopping*Age of the respondents

Figure: Bar chart- Browsing internet and ethnicity of the respondents

Figure: Bar chart- online shopping and ethnicity of the respondents

Figure: Education level and online shopping cross tabulation bar chart

Figure: Bar chart- online shopping and occupation of the respondents

